

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

See example on page 3

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Akiyama, Minoru, Takeharu Tsuge, and Yoshiharu Doi, “Environmental life cycle comparison of polyhydroxyalkanoates produced from renewable carbon resources by bacterial fermentation”, Polymer Degradation and Stability Vol. 80, No. 1, 2003, pp. 183–194
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Soybean oil mill, compared to corn
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	P(3HB-co-5mol% 3HHx) granulate
Functional unit	1 kg of PHA
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	substituent of common polymers such as polyethylene, polypropylene or polystyrene
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	No co-products
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	
Data quality	SuperPro Designer1 v4.5 was utilized for the whole fermentation process. It is characterized by designing and optimizing integrated processes including chemical and pharmaceutical, biochemical and environmental processes.
Impact assessment method	Not mentioned

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Damage categories (endpoint)	Not mentioned
Impact categories (midpoint)	CO ₂ emission and cumulative energy required
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Fig. 1. Cumulative energy use and CO₂ emissions of soybean oil before the fermentation stage.

Fig. 2. Cumulative energy use and CO₂ emissions of glucose before the fermentation stage.

Fig. 3. The process flowsheet for fermentative production of polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA).

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Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Fernández-Dacosta, Cora, John A. Posada, Robbert Kleerebezem, Maria C. Cuellar, and Andrea Ramirez, “Microbial community-Based polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) production from wastewater: Techno-Economic analysis and ex-Ante environmental assessment,” Bioreso
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Techno-economic analysis
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Organic matter from waste water
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	PHB
Functional unit	1 kg of PHB production
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	substituent of common polymers such as polyethylene, polypropylene or polystyrene
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	No co-products
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	Netherlands
Data quality	The processing units and operating conditions are selected from either data available at laboratory or pilot scale, or from literature review. The mass and energy balances are obtained from conducting process modelling in ASPEN Plus software.
Impact assessment method	Not mentioned

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Damage categories (endpoint)	Not mentioned
Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming potential and non-renewable energy usage
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Fig. 1. Process flow diagrams. (a) WW fermentation to PHB. R-101: acidification fermenter, R-102: selection fermenter, R-103: accumulation fermenter, T-101: buffer tank. (b) Alkali-surfactant. H-201: preheater, R-201: alkali reactor, H-202: cooler, C-201: hydrocyclone, C-202: centrifuge, M-301: mixing tank, C-301: centrifuge, M-302: mixing tank, C-302: centrifuge, C-401: centrifuge, D-401: air dryer. (c) Surfactant-hypochlorite. H-201: preheater, R-201: surfactant reactor, H-202: cooler, C-201: hydrocyclone, C-202: centrifuge, H-301: pre-cooler, R-301: SDS crystallisation reactor, F-301: filter, R-401: hypochlorite reactor, C-401: centrifuge, M-501: mixing tank, C-501: centrifuge, M-502: mixing tank, C-502: centrifuge, C-601: centrifuge, D-601: air dryer. (d) DCM solvent route. C-201: centrifuge, F-201: filter, D-201: air dryer, R-201: DCM reactor, F-202: filter, D-202: solid phase dryer, H-201: DCM evaporator, H-202: DCM condenser, R-301: ethanol precipitation reactor, F-301: filter, D-301: dryer, H-301: condenser, V-401: vacuum distillation.

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Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Harding, K, J Dennis, H Vonblotnitz, and S Harrison, “Environmental analysis of plastic production processes: Comparing petroleum-Based polypropylene and polyethylene with biologically-Based poly-β-Hydroxybutyric acid using life cycle analysis,” Journal
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Sucrose from cane sugar
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	PHB
Functional unit	1000 kg of polymer product
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	substituent of common polymers such as polyethylene, polypropylene or polystyrene
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	No co-products
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	
Data quality	The inventory data for the life cycle assessment (LCA) of poly-β-hydroxybutyric acid production was based on the laboratory study of Harrison (1990) which was linked to a pilot scale process.
Impact assessment method	CML 2 Baseline 2000 V2.03

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Damage categories (endpoint)	Not mentioned
Impact categories (midpoint)	Abiotic depletion, Global warming, Ozone layer depletion, Photochemical oxidation, Acidification, Eutrophication, Fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity, Marine aquatic ecotoxicity, Terrestrial ecotoxicity
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

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K.G. Harding et al. / Journal of Biotechnology 130 (2007) 57–66

Fig. 1. Process flowsheet for PHB production.

Table 4
Process conditions for the production of 1000 kg of PHB

	Unit	
Seed media		<i>Cupriavidus necator</i> , sucrose (10 kg/m ³), (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ (1.8 kg/m ³), K ₂ HPO ₄ (1.9 kg/m ³), NaHPO ₄ (1.56 kg/m ³), MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O (0.8 kg/m ³), FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O (0.008 kg/m ³), trace salts solution (CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O, ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O, MnSO ₄ ·H ₂ O, CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O)
Fermentation media		Sucrose (270 kg/m ³), H ₃ PO ₄ (0.8 dm ³ /m ³), (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ (1.1 kg/m ³), K ₂ SO ₄ (1.4 kg/m ³), MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O (1.6 kg/m ³), trace salts (Na ₂ SO ₄ , MnSO ₄ ·H ₂ O, ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O, CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O), PPG.EEA 142 antifoam (0.375 kg/m ³)
Sterilisation	S-100	139 °C (continuous sterilisation) – including heat integration
Microbial growth	R-100	Temperature: 30 °C; pH: 7 Reactor volume: 9.4 m ³ (working) Total reaction time: 80 h Aeration: 0.6 vol/vol/min Agitation energy: 0.5 kW/m ³ Biomass (PHB) concentration: 150 (106) g/l Polymer concentration: 71% PHB
Cell disruption	H-100	High pressure homogenisation 3 passes; 70 MPa; 16 °C Energy efficiency of breakage: 1.25 J/mg biomass disrupted
Enzyme addition	R-200	Re-suspensions equivalent to 150 kg/m ³ Optimase L660 (MKC) – alkaline serine protease enzyme Agitation energy: 0.8 kW/m ³ Temperature: 70 °C; pH: 8 Residence time: 2 h
(Non-ionic) detergent addition	R-201	Synperonic NP8 Agitation energy: 0.8 kW/m ³ Temperature: 70 °C; pH: 7 Residence time: 2 h
Water washing (I)	V-300 C-300	Number of washes: 4 Wash volume: 1/3 of reactor volume (3.1 m ³) Centrifugation: 20 min; 10,000 g Power required: 2.11 kW/m ³ (per wash)
H ₂ O ₂ addition	V-301	Concentration: 1.20% v/v
Water washing (II)	V-400 C-400	Number of washes: 2 Wash volume: 1/3 of reactor volume (3.1 m ³) Centrifugation: 20 min; 10,000 g Power required: 2.11 kW/m ³ (per wash)
Spray drying	O-500	Initial moisture content: 11% Final moisture content: 0.1% Drying rate: 4.8 GJ/t
Downstream processing recovery: 95%		

References: Perry et al. (1984), Engler (1985), Harrison (1990), Baker and McKenzie (2005).

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1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Madival, Santosh, Rafael Auras, Sher Paul Singh, and Ramani Narayan, “Assessment of the environmental profile of PLA, PET and PS clamshell containers using LCA methodology”, Journal of Cleaner Production, Vol. 17, No. 13, 2009, pp. 1183–1194.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Corn (starch)
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	PLA thermoformed clamshell containers, compared to PET and PS ones.
Functional unit	1000 containers of capacity 0.4536 kg (1 lb) each for the packaging of strawberries
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	None (only processes for the production of resins had allocation rules defined in the database module, and no separate allocation rule was considered).
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	North America
Data quality	Secondary data (Ecoinvent, literature).
Impact assessment method	IMPACT 2002+
Damage categories (endpoint)	Human health; Ecosystem quality; Resources.
Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming; Aquatic acidification; Aquatic eutrophication; Aquatic ecotoxicity; Ozone depletion; Non-renewable energy; Respiratory organics; Land occupation; Respiratory inorganics.

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2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Fig. 1. Life cycle inventory flow chart for PLA, PET and PS thermoformed containers from cradle to gate, cradle-to-grave, and cradle-to-cradle.(T – transport, T/R – transport with refrigeration).

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1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Zhang, Yanan, Hu, Guiping and Brown, Robert C., “Life cycle assessment of a commodity chemical production from forest residue via fast pyrolysis”, International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment, Vol. 19, 2014, pp. 1371-1381.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Forest residues (mixed wood)
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	- Main products: <i>commodity (bulk) chemicals</i> , i.e. aromatics and olefines (benzene, toluene, xylene, ...), via bio-oil extracted through fast pyrolysis; - By-products of fast pyrolysis: <i>non-condensable gases</i> , combusted to provide heat for the pyrolysis process; <i>biochar</i> , used as coal substitute (50% of coal heating value); - By-products of bio-oil upgrading process: <i>pyrolytic lignin</i> , used as coal substitute (50% of coal heating value)
Functional unit	1 kg of commodity chemicals (composition: ethylene, propene, butylene, toluene, xylene, ethylbenzene, styrene, indene and naphthalene)
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Bulk (commodity) chemicals from pyrolytic bio-oil, biochar, pyrolytic lignin
Possible applications	Surfactant agent for moisturizing creams
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (<i>to be detailed in the report section</i>) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Agricultural stages are not taken into account as wood residues are referred to as wastes, however carbon capture is taken into account during biomass growing
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	No allocation considered: the only output seems to be the amount of produced chemicals (1 kg); no allocation is provided for the biochar and pyrolytic lignin by-products
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	- iLUC effects are explicitly said not to be considered in the study; dLUC is not clearly assessed/explained: it's not part of the impact categories studied

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Geographic location, if defined	General biorefinery case study in the USA (according to the chosen electricity mix inventory data) - distances between wood residues collection areas and the biorefinery are hypothesized according to secondary data
Data quality	Secondary data from literature (modified Aspen Plus model in combination with a greenhouse gases, regulated emissions and energy use in transportation (GREET) model) and LCA built-in Ecoinvent V.2.2 database
Impact assessment method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Special focus on <i>GHG balance</i> (IPCC 2007 GWP 100a method) and <i>cumulative energy demand</i> (CED) to estimate energy input; - Other impact categories according to <i>TRACI 2</i> (Tool for the Reduction and Assessment of Chemical and other Environmental Impacts) method
Damage categories (endpoint)	None
Impact categories (midpoint)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GHG emissions; - Cumulative energy demand; - TRACI 2 impact categories: ozone depletion, smog, acidification, eutrophication, carcinogenics, noncarcinogenics, respiratory effects and ecotoxicity
Other information or comments	<p>Note that biochar generated in pyrolysis and pyrolytic lignin from the two-stage hydrotreating/FCC path contribute to the overall impact assessment as <i>credits</i>, which reduce fossil energy input (coal substitute);</p> <p>In parallel, negative GWP contributions come also from carbon fixation by biomass (assumed that the atmosphere can take up 0.942 kg CO₂ per kg of forest residue during the biomass growth [Hsu et al. 2010])</p>

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Flow Diagram:

Life cycle stages:

- 1) Biomass (forest residue) collection, transportation and grinding down to 3 mm diameter particles;
- 2) Biomass pre-processing in a steam dryer to remove water from the matrix;
- 3) Bio-oil production through fast pyrolysis (bio-oil vapors recovered using a condenser and an electrostatic precipitator), producing non-condensable gases as by-product that are combusted to provide sufficient heat for the pyrolyzer. Bio-char is obtained during the solid removal step through cyclones and it is treated as coal substitute with an assumed heating value that is 50% of the displaced coal. Ashes formed during combustion are separated through cyclones and disposed off in sanitary landfills;
- 4) Bio-oil upgrading is provided through a two-stage hydrotreating and FCC (Fluidized Catalytic Cracking) pathway, enabling the obtainment of commodity chemicals from the aqueous phase of the bio-oil;
- 5) The water-insoluble fraction (mainly pyrolytic lignin) is assumed to be a coal substitute and consumed locally

Life cycle inventory tables:

Table 2 Inventory data of biomass transportation

Item	Amount	Unit
Outputs		
Delivered forest residue	2,670	Metric ton
Input from material		
Truck 40 t	710,000	tkm
Collected forest residue	2,670	Metric ton

Table 3 Inventory data of biomass preprocessing

Item	Amount	Unit	Description
Outputs			
Pretreated forest residue	2,140	Metric ton	
Materials and fuels			
Delivered forest residue	2,670	Metric ton	
Steam	255	Metric ton	On-site steam average
Electricity for chopping	44,600	kWh	Medium voltage, at grid/US with US electricity
Electricity for grinding	109,000	kWh	Medium voltage, at grid/US with US electricity
Electricity for compressor	170,000	kWh	Medium voltage, at grid/US with US electricity
Emission to air			
Water	523	Metric ton	

Table 4 Inventory data of bio-oil production

Item	Amount	Unit	Description
Outputs			
Forest residue bio-oil	1,040	Metric ton	
Char	219	Metric ton	
Avoided products			
Coal	110	Metric ton	Hard coal supply mix, at regional storage/US S
Resources			
Air	2,165	Metric ton	
Process water	9,590	Metric ton	Water, process, unspecified natural origin/kilogram
Materials and fuels			
Pretreated forest residue	2,140	Metric ton	
Electricity for pyrolysis	450,000	kWh	Medium voltage, at grid/US with US electricity
Emission to air			
N ₂	1,660	Metric ton	
O ₂	21.7	Metric ton	
CO ₂	928	Metric ton	
Water	432	Metric ton	
Waste or emissions to treatment			
Ash	11	Metric ton	Disposal, wood ash mixtures, pure, to sanitary landfill

Table 5 Inventory data of bio-oil upgrading

Item	Amount	Unit	Description
Outputs			
Chemicals	243	Metric ton	
Avoided products			
Coal	117	Metric ton	Bituminous coal, combusted in industrial boiler, NREL/US
Resources			
Air	370	Metric ton	
Process water	2,840	Metric ton	Water, cooling, unspecified natural origin/kilogram
Materials and fuels			
Bio-oil	1,040	Metric ton	
Electricity for upgrading	103,000	kWh	Medium voltage, at grid/US with US electricity
Natural gas	60	Metric ton	From onshore and offshore production including pipeline and LNG, consumption mix
Zeolite powder	0.79	Metric ton	At plant/RER S
ZnO catalyst	0.24	Metric ton	At plant/RER with electricity U
Heat	116,000	MJ	Natural gas, at industrial furnace >1,000 kW/RER U
Emission to air			
N ₂	284	Metric ton	
O ₂	14.2	Metric ton	
CO	39	Metric ton	
CO ₂	395	Metric ton	
Water	388	Metric ton	
Sulfur	1.56	Metric ton	
SO ₂	0.263	Metric ton	
Waste or emissions to treatment			
Wastewater	1,010	m ³	Treatment, sewage, to wastewater treatment, class 3/with US electricity

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1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Razza, Francesco, Francesco Degli Innocenti, Antonio Dobon, Cesar Aliaga, Carmen Sanchez, and Mercedes Hortal, “Environmental profile of a bio-based and biodegradable foamed packaging prototype in comparison with the current benchmark”, <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 102, 2015, pp. 493–500.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Tapioca (starch), compared to fossil base and to corn and potato (starch) in sensitivity analysis.
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Foam for cushioning packaging (in form of port-hole spacer). Co-products: feed products from starch production.
Functional unit	The production, use and disposal of 100 port-hole spacers.
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Potato and corn starch production in Germany: economic allocation between starch and feed products. Tapioca starch production in Thailand and corn starch production in Italy: mass allocation between starch and feed products.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	dLUC included in sensitivity analysis for tapioca starch base scenario. Emission factors taken from PAS 2050:2011, related to Malaysia (since there were no available data for Thailand), considering "grassland" or "forest land" as previous land use.
Geographic location, if defined	Europe. Starch production from tapioca takes place in Thailand, from corn in Germany or Italy, from potato in Germany.
Data quality	Primary data for prototype granule production. Secondary specific data for raw material production. Mix of primary and secondary data for EPS granule expansion. Calculation tool developed by Ecoinvent v2.2 for emissions to air, water, etc. from packaging waste treatments. Ecoinvent v2.2 for data for EPS

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

	granules and all background inventory data.
<i>Impact assessment method</i>	Customized method set: IMPACT 2002+ (Inventory level categories); IPCC 2007 (Global Warming); Int.EPD® System (other emission-related categories); CML 2001 (resource-related categories).
<i>Damage categories (endpoint)</i>	
<i>Impact categories (midpoint)</i>	Non-renewable Energy Resource consumption; Global Warming (100 years); Eutrophication; Acidification; Stratospheric Ozone Depletion; Photochemical Ozone Formation; Depletion of abiotic resources.
<i>Other information or comments</i>	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Fig. 1. System boundaries. This figure shows the life cycle system boundaries considered in this LCA for both packaging materials (EPS and Prototype), including a description of the main processing steps as well as the end-of-life scenarios.

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Cherubini, Francesco and Ulgiati, Sergio, “Crop residues as raw materials for biorefinery systems - A LCA case study”, Applied Energy, Vol. 87, 2017, pp. 47-57.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Agricultural residues: <i>corn stover</i> and <i>wheat straw</i> (source of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin)
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Several co-products (bio-refinery process): - Chemicals (e.g. phenols); - Bioethano; - Biomethane; - Electricity and heat
Functional unit	Amount of agricultural residues treated per year by each biorefinery system (corn stover and wheat straw as feedstock): 477 kt(dry)/year
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Pyrolytic oil, from which phenols are extracted; bio-fuels as other co-product (not relevant for the aim of the project)
Possible applications	Surfactant agent for moisturizing creams
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (<i>to be detailed in the report section</i>) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Agricultural stages are not taken into account as all environmental burdens are associated to grains production (corn stover and wheat straw are considered as by-product with zero allocation contribute). However, additional need for fertilizers is accounted for when assessing the impact of Land Use Change related to residues removal from agricultural soil
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	No allocation needed: feedstock biomass is considered as sort of a waste (all environmental burdes associated to primary output of agricultural production, i.e. grains)
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	- iLUC is mentioned as a real consequence, but not further investigated: the removal of agricultural residues from lands reduces the crop grain productivity yields: on one hand, this missing might be faced with increase in N-based

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	<p>fertilizers addition; on the other hand these "missing" cereals might be produced somewhere else (by an expansion of agricultural land).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - dLUC is estimated according to a study that modelled the effects of crop rotation and straw removal frequency on two different soil types [Gabrielle, B. and Gagnaire, N, 2008]: the differences across rotations are generally more important than those related to straw management for a given rotation - the removal of straw implies limited consequences on field emissions. <p>However, LUC impact has been accounted for considering a reference land use as "agricultural land" where corn stover and wheat straw are left on the ground and ploughed back to the field. Main GHG implications are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decrease in crop grain productivity yields, because of a lower net mineralization of N in soils: increase of synthetic fertilizer application to balance the nutrient removed (manufacture impact, methane soil emissions, volatilization of N as NH₃, leaching to groundwater as nitrate); - Decrease in N₂O emissions from land with increasing crop residue removal, because straw return to soil increases soil's denitrification potentials and its capacity to produce N₂O: this must be accounted for when assessing N₂O emissions from additional fertilizer use: the net emission is lower than the one estimated through IPCC factors; - Decrease in Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) due to a change in soil carbon stocks, in comparison with reference land use: loss of soil carbon emitted as CO₂. SOC decreasing trend is assessed according to IPCC factors (parameters considered: col temperate/moist, high clay activity soil, long term cultivated land, full tillage, high C inputs to soil without manure) and the reduction is modelled by means of the software tool RothC [Skjemstad JO et al., 2004], considering a "payback time" of 20 years as suggested by IPCC guidelines for many bioenergy crops.
Geographic location, if defined	Undefined - distances between agricultural land, plant, consumer and final disposal are hypothesized according to secondary data
Data quality	Secondary data from literature and LCA databases (Ecoinvent and ETH-ESU 96)
Impact assessment method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Special focus on <i>GHG balance</i> (100 year time horizon kt CO₂ eq.) and <i>energy balance</i>, i.e. <i>cumulative primary energy demand</i>, distinguished into non-renewable energy, renewable energy (biomass), other renewable energy (hydropower, solar, wind ...); - <i>Energy Return on Investment</i> (EROI), index give by the ratio between energy out and the non-renewable energy in; - Other impact categories according to CML classification method (<i>CML 2 baseline 2000 V.2.03</i>)
Damage categories (endpoint)	Not clear: probably none
Impact categories (midpoint)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GHG emissions (including LUC effects); - Cumulative primary energy demand; - CML impact categories: abiotic depletion, global warming (GWP100), ozone layer depletion, human toxicity, freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity, marine aquatic ecotoxicity, terrestrial ecotoxicity, photochemical oxidation, acidification, eutrophication
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Flow Diagram:

Life cycle stages:

- 1) Residues (corn stover and wheat straw) collection from agricultural land, baled and loaded on trucks (transportation to the biorefinery);
- 2) Conversion of residues to pellets after drying;
- 3) Biomass pretreatment (uncatalyzed steam explosion) in order to depolymerize hemicellulose and separate ligning;
- 4) Enzymatic cellulose hydrolysis to glucose monomers;
- 5) Fermentation and distillation of sugars to bioethanol;
- 6) Anaerobic digestion of wastewater;
- 7) Flash pyrolysis of lignin followed by phenol separation from the resulting pyrolytic oil;
- 8) Final combustion (heat and power production) of process residues, fraction of lignin not pyrolyzed, pyrolytic char and remaining pyrolytic oil after phenol extraction;
- 9) Bioethanol is distributed to fuelling stations and to fuel passenger cars
- 10) Biomethane is fed to the national natural gas grid, delivered to final applications replacing natural gas (boiler burning);
- 11) Phenols are transported to producers of resins and finally disposed of via incineration.

Life cycle inventory table not available

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Tsiropoulos, I., A.p.c. Faaij, L. Lundquist, U. Schenker, J.f. Briois, and M.k. Patel, “Life cycle impact assessment of bio-based plastics from sugarcane ethanol”, Journal of Cleaner Production, Vol. 90, 2015, pp. 114–127.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Sugarcane
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Bio-based HDPE and partially bio-based PET, compared to the petrochemical counterparts. Co-products from sugarcane ethanol production: sugarcane trash, filtercake, surplus electricity and bagasse from sugar mills and distilleries. Co-products in bio-MEG(monoethyleneglycol) production: diethylene, triethylene and heavier glycols (DEG,TEG,HEG)
Functional unit	1) 1 kg of bio-based HDPE; 2) 1 kg partially bio-based PET
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Co-products from sugarcane ethanol product-system: system expansion and economic allocation (tab.1). Co-products in bio-MEG production: mass allocation.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Accounting for dLUC and iLUC for Brazilian bio-HDPE and bio-PET, using different factors from literature and obtaining a range (low-high). Not accounted for Indian bio-PET due to lack of publicly available reliable data.
Geographic location, if defined	Bio-HDPE: production in Brazil for European market. Bio-PET: from sugarcane to bio-MEG Brazil, or India, or partly in Brazil (sugarcane to ethanol) and partly in India (ethanol to bio-MEG); from bio-MEG to bio-PET Europe, for European market.(fig. 1)
Data quality	Primary data for bio-ethylene production in Brazil and bio-MEG production in

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	India. Secondary data for other processes.(fig.1)
Impact assessment method	Impact 2002+; IPCC for GHG emissions; Pfister et al. (2009) for water use (endpoint).
Damage categories (endpoint)	Human health; Ecosystem quality; Water use.
Impact categories (midpoint)	GHG emissions; Non-renewable energy use; Land use; Freshwater eutrophication; Water use (inventory).
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Fig. 1. Main process steps in bio-HDPE (left) and bio-PET (right) production for further use in Europe. Data for processes marked with highlighted boxes are based on literature sources, databases or industry averages. Data for processes marked with clear boxes are based on primary producers or technology licensors. Dashed arrows indicate international transport.

Approach ^a	Products	Description	Credits/allocation factors [per kg _{ethanol}]
System expansion, conservative (SE-C)	- Energy outputs: electricity (Brazil, India) - Material outputs: ethanol and bagasse (Brazil), sugar, molasses and bagasse (India)	- Displacement of <i>low</i> CO ₂ emission intensity grid power - Economic allocation between material outputs	Brazil: 0.16 kWh (0.22 kg CO _{2eq} /kWh) India: 0.5 kWh (0.55 kg CO _{2eq} /kWh), sugar 91.5%, molasses 8%, bagasse 0.5%
System expansion, optimistic (SE-O)	- Energy outputs: electricity, heat from bagasse (Brazil, India) - Material outputs: ethanol (Brazil), sugar, molasses and bagasse (India)	- Brazil: Displacement of <i>high</i> CO ₂ emission intensity power from natural gas and oil-based heat - India: Displacement of <i>high</i> CO ₂ emission intensity grid power and coal-based heat - Economic allocation between material outputs	Brazil: 0.16 kWh (0.65 kg CO _{2eq} /kWh), 0.9 MJ _{heat} (0.09 kg CO _{2eq} /MJ _{heat}) India: 0.5 kWh (1.1 kg CO _{2eq} /kWh), 0.38 MJ _{heat} (0.13 kg CO _{2eq} /MJ _{heat}), sugar 92%, molasses 8%
Economic allocation, conservative (EA-C) and optimistic (EA-O)	- Material outputs: ethanol, electricity and bagasse (Brazil). Sugar, molasses, electricity and bagasse (India)	- Economic allocation between material outputs	Brazil: ethanol 97.5%, electricity 2%, bagasse 0.5% India: sugar 85%, molasses 7.5%, bagasse 0.5%

Table 2. Allocation approaches chosen for multifunctional processes in sugarcane processing in Brazil and India

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Papong, Seksan, Pomthong Malakul, Ruethai Trungkavashirakun, Pechda Wenunun, Tassaneewan Chom-In, Manit Nithitanakul, and Ed Sarobol, “Comparative assessment of the environmental profile of PLA and PET drinking water bottles from a life cycle perspective”, <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 65, 2014, pp. 539–550.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Cassava (glucose)
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Poylactic acid (PLA) bottles, compared to similar fossil-PET bottles. By-products: cassava stems (cassava cultivation); cassava pulp (cassava starch production); gypsum (PLA production).
Functional unit	1000 units of 250-ml drinking water bottles
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Cassava starch production: mass allocation between cassava starch and cassava pulp in terms of starch content.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	Thailand
Data quality	Primary data collected at the actual sites in Thailand, including cassava plantations and harvesting, cassava starch production, and bottle production plants. Secondary data for other processes (ecoinvent, research reports, LCI databases of Thailand).
Impact assessment method	The CML 2 baseline 2000 method and the cumulative energy demand method.

Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming; Acidification; Eutrophication; Human toxicity potential; Fossil energy demand.
Other information or comments	

2)

Fig. 1. The system boundary for PLA bottles system.

Fig. 2. The system boundary for PET bottles system.

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Leceta, I., A. Etxabide, S. Cabezudo, K. De La Caba, and P. Guerrero, “Bio-based films prepared with by-products and wastes: environmental assessment”, Journal of Cleaner Production Vol. 64, 2014, pp. 218–227.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Soybeans (soy protein); crustacean shell waste (chitosan); marine seaweeds (agar).
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Packaging films. By-products (whey, solids) of soy protein production from soy flour. Co-products: soy oil from soybeans, separated from soy flour; biodiesel from soy oil, separated from glycerol (used in film manufacture).
Functional unit	1 mc of film
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Soy protein isolate (SPI) production from soy flour: mass allocation between SPI and by-products (whey, solids).
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Not mentioned.
Geographic location, if defined	Europe
Data quality	Primary data (laboratories) for bio-based film manufacture and extraction of agar from algae. LCI of raw material extraction for chitosan from literature. Ecoinvent v2.0 database for other processes.
Impact assessment method	Eco-Indicator 99 (Hierarchist)
Damage categories (endpoint)	Human health; Ecosystem quality; Resources.
Impact categories (midpoint)	Carcinogens; Respiratory organics; Respiratory inorganics; Climate change;

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2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

SPI films system boundary

Fig. 1. System boundaries for soy protein isolate films.

Chitosan films system boundary

Fig. 2. System boundaries for chitosan films.

Fig. 3. System boundaries for agar films.

Fig. 4. System boundaries for polypropylene films.

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Chen, Luyi, Rylie E.o. Pelton, and Timothy M. Smith, “Comparative life cycle assessment of fossil and bio-based polyethylene terephthalate (PET) bottles”, Journal of Cleaner Production, Vol. 137, 2016, pp. 667–676.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Twelve scenarios were considered with different feedstocks for the two precursors: ethylene glycol (corn, switchgrass, wheat straw, fossil) and terephthalic acid (corn stover, forest residues, fossil).
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) bottles. Co-products and by-products: timber; DDGS (ethanol).
Functional unit	1 kg of PET bottles
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Forest resource extraction: mass allocation between timber and forest residues. Ethanol production: system expansion to avoid allocation of co-products (avoided impacts of corn grain, soybean meal and urea production).
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	United States
Data quality	Secondary data (Ecoinvent database, PlasticsEurope database, U.S. Life Cycle Inventory database, literature). Interviews with industrial collaborators for newly designed processes.
Impact assessment method	TRACI v2.1, except for ozone depletion (ReCiPe v1.08) and eutrophication (only terrestrial eutrophication according to ILCD Handbook)
Damage categories (endpoint)	

Impact categories (midpoint)

Climate change; Human health particulates; Smog; Acidification; Fossil fuel depletion; Ecotoxicity; Terrestrial eutrophication; Ozone depletion.

Other information or comments

2)

Fig. 1. Cradle-to-Gate system boundary for 100% bio-based PET bottles. Grey boxes represent the product output flow of each intermediate production process. White boxes indicate the more detailed account of the novel wood-based isobutanol and paraxylene production processes and life cycle inventories that are a primary focus in this study.

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Belboom, Sandra, and Angélique Léonard, “Does biobased polymer achieve better environmental impacts than fossil polymer? Comparison of fossil HDPE and biobased HDPE produced from sugar beet and wheat”, <i>Biomass and Bioenergy</i> , Vol. 85, 2016, pp. 159–167.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Sugar beet and wheat compared to fossil oil
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	High-density polyethylene (HDPE). Co-products and by-products: sugar beet pulps; gluten and liquid feed from wheat.
Functional unit	1 t of HDPE
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Sugar beet transformation (byproduct: sugar beet pulps), Wheat transformation (coproducts: gluten, liquid feed): energy allocation between ethanol and coproducts (mass and economic allocation in sensitivity analysis).
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Not included
Geographic location, if defined	Belgium
Data quality	Primary data for wheat transformation process (Belgian industrial plant using wet milling technology) and ethylene polymerization process (Belgian industrial plant). Secondary data for other processes.
Impact assessment method	Customised method set, including categories of both the ILCD 2011 and ReCiPe 2008 methods with a midpoint hierarchist perspective.
Damage categories (endpoint)	

Impact categories (midpoint)	Climate change; Ozone depletion; Particulate matter; Photochemical oxidation; Acidification; Terrestrial eutrophication; Freshwater eutrophication; Land use; Mineral, fossil and ren resource depletion; Mineral depletion; Fossil fuel depletion.
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

For the biobased routes, six stages are modeled: (1) crop cultivation, (2) crop transportation from field to plant, (3) biobased ethanol production, (4) biobased ethanol dehydration, (5) biobased ethylene polymerization and (6) end-of-life.

For fossil polymer, (7) production of ethylene using steam cracking of naphtha has been assessed.

Fig. 1. Boundaries of systems: from cultivation or oil extraction to end-of-life. Production of all energy and chemical consumptions as well as associated emissions are taken into account in the modeling of every system but not shown on this figure.

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Secchi, Michela, Castellani, Valentina, Collina, Elena, Mirabella, Nadia, and Sala, Serenella, “Assessing eco-innovations in green chemistry: Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of a cosmetic product with a bio-based ingredient”, Journal of Cleaner Production, Vol. 129, 2016, pp. 269-281.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	"Lampante" fraction of olive oil (olives physical extraction)
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	- Main product: day face cream with Sun Protection Factor (SPF) about 6-10 - Bio-product from refinery of "lampante" fraction of olive oil: "palmitic/stearic triglycerides" (INCI name), patent WO 2012/131624A1 - mixture of vegetable triglycerides containing saturated fatty acids with chain length C16-18 - "Lampante" fraction of olive oil is considered as a by-product of the olive oil industry
Functional unit	Production of 1 kg of final product (day face cream with a Sun Protection Factor - SPF - about 6-10)
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	- Innovation I: Substitute for dimethicone and caprylic/capric triglyceride, if used along with C17-21 alkane - Innovation II: Substitute for dimethicone and caprylic/capric triglycerid, if used along with 2 preformulated ingredients for yield optimization. Pref. ingredient 1: C15-17 alkane palmitic/stearic triglycerides, titanium dioxide, zinc oxide; Pref. ingredient 2: C21-28 alkane, hydrated silica, glass bubbles
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Allocation performed only to assess Italian "lampante" oil production within the overall olive oil production process: - Physical allocation considered (i.e. mass of the Italian "lampante" oil exported out of the total amount of oil exported from Italy) for the olive oil production

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

	<p>process (suggested by the ILCD handbook [EC-JRC, 2010];</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Economic allocation tested to verify the choice: no significant difference in the two options has been found
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	<p>iLUC is not considered; dLUC is considered as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - main analysis: it is one of the chosen impact categories (16 totally), as suggested by <i>ILCD</i> impact assessment method [EC-JRC, 2011]; - sensitivity analysis with <i>ReCiPe 2012</i> (?) impact categories: "Agricultural land occupation", "Urban land occupation", "Natural land transformation"; - sensitivity analysis with <i>CML 2012</i> impact categories: "Land competition"; - sensitivity analysis with <i>Impact 2002</i> impact categories: "Land occupation"
Geographic location, if defined	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Olive oil supplier: Imperia (Italy), nearest commercial site to the face cream production plant; - Face cream production plant: Oreggio (VA, Italy), - Other feedstock 1 (vegetable glycerin): Kuantan (Malaysia); - Other feedstock 2 (Octocrylene and Butyl methoxydibenzoylmethane): Mumbai (India); - Other feedstock 3 (glass bubbles): New York (USA); - Other feedstock 4 (titanium dioxide and zinc oxide): Berlin (Germany), closest manufacturing plant
Data quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cosmetic production: primary data (company) for energy & water consumption, secondary data (ecoinvent v2.2) for Italian energy mix; - New bio-based ingredient manufacturing (including olive tree cultivation): secondary data. Inventory data for the lampante oil transformation have been estimated using stoichiometric equations from technical literature (third approach by Hirschier et al. (2005); - Other ingredients preparation: secondary data (ecoinvent v2.2). Proxy inventory adopted (based on similarity of molecular structure, synthesis, manufacturing or refining processes) for a number of ingredients not listed in the database
Impact assessment method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - main analysis: <i>ILCD</i> impact assessment method [EC-JRC, 2011]: 16 impact categories; - sensitivity analysis with <i>ReCiPe 2012</i> (?) impact assessment method: 18 impact categories ("Environmental Mechanism Part 1"); - sensitivity analysis with <i>CML 2012</i> impact assessment method: 23 impact categories; - sensitivity analysis with <i>Impact 2002</i> impact assessment method: 15 impact categories
Damage categories (endpoint)	It seems no endpoint damage category is considered
Impact categories (midpoint)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - main analysis: <i>ILCD</i> impact assessment method [EC-JRC, 2011]: 16 impact categories: Climate change, Ozone depletion, Human toxicity-cancer effects, Human toxicity-non cancer effects, Particulate matter, Ionizing radiation HH, Ionizing radiation E, Photochemical ozone formation, Acidification, Terrestrial eutrophication, Freshwater eutrophication, Marine eutrophication, Freshwater ecotoxicity, Land use, Water resource depletion, Mineral & fossil & renewable resource depletion; - sensitivity analysis with <i>ReCiPe 2012</i> (?) impact assessment method: 18 impact categories ("Environmental Mechanism Part 1"): Climate change, Ozone depletion, Human toxicity, Photochemical oxidant formation, Particulate matter formation, Ionising radiation, Terrestrial acidification, Freshwater eutrophication, Marine eutrophication, Terrestrial ecotoxicity, Freshwater ecotoxicity, Marine ecotoxicity, Agricultural land occupation, Urban land occupation, Natural land transformation, Water depletion, Metal depletion, Fossil depletion; - sensitivity analysis with <i>CML 2012</i> impact assessment method: 23 impact categories: Abiotic depletion, Acidification, Eutrophication, Global warming 100a, Upper limit of net global warming, Lower limit of net global warming, Ozone layer depletion 20a, Human toxicity 20a, Freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity 20a, Marine aquatic ecotoxicity 20a, Terrestrial ecotoxicity 20a, Marine sediment ecotoxicity 20a, Freshwater sediment ecotoxicity 20a, Average European kgNOx eq., Average European kgSO2-eq, Land competition, Ionising radiation, Photochemical oxidation, Photochemical oxidation low NOx, Malodours air, Equal benefit incremental reactivity, Max incremental reactivity, Max ozone incremental reactivity; - sensitivity analysis with <i>Impact 2002</i> impact assessment method: 15 impact

categories: Carcinogens, Non-carcinogens, Respiratory inorganics, Ionizing radiation, Ozone layer depletion, Respiratory organics, Aquatic ecotoxicity, Terrestrial ecotoxicity, Terrestrial acid/nutri, Land occupation, Aquatic acidification, Aquatic eutrophication, Global warming, Non-renewable energy, Mineral extraction

Other information or comments

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Flow Diagrams:

Life cycle stages:

- 1) Olive tree agricultural process and olives harvest;
- 2) Olive oil production process, obtaining the "lampante" olive oil fraction as by-product (main products are virgin olive oil and extra virgin olive oil);
- 3) Distillate production: degumming, neutralization, separation of soaps by centrifugation, washing and continuous drying, discoloration and filtration, deodorization in high vacuum;
- 4) Wet fractionation of the distillate;
- 5) Transesterification of the solid fraction (palmitic/stearic acids), neutralization of saturated triglycerides, bleaching of the neutral soapy mixture: obtaining palmitic stearic saturated tryglicerides;

- 6) Saponification of the liquid fraction (oleic/linoleic acids and unsaponifiables): obtaining unsaturated triglycerides and unsaponifiable fraction;
- 7) Palmitic/stearic saturated triglycerides and unsaponifiable fraction together form the palmitic/stearic triglycerides needed for the cream;
- 8) Pre-formulated ingredient 1 of innovation II: blending of four compounds (C15-17 alkane, palmitic/stearic triglycerides, titanium dioxide, zinc oxide);
- 9) Pre-formulated ingredient 2 of innovation II: mixture of three substances (C21-28 alkane, hydrated silica, glass bubbles)

Life cycle inventory table not available

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Martinez, S., Bessou, C., Hure, L., Guilbot, J. and Helias, A., “The impact of palm oil feedstock within the LCA of a bio-sourced cosmetic cream”, Journal of Cleaner Production, Vol. 145, 2017, pp. 348-360.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Palm oil
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Main product: bio-sourced moisturizing cream made of alkyl polyglucoside (APG) surfactant based on palm oil; Co-products (economic allocation): Kernel (18.7%) and Crude Palm Oil (81.3%), Crude Palm Kernel Oil (92.5%) and Palm Kernel Cake (7.5%), Refined Palm Kernel Oil (99.22%) and Free Fatty Acids (0.78%), Cetaryl Alcohol (27.9%) and Methyl Ester (62.38%) and Glycerol (9.68%)
Functional unit	Preparation and use of one 30 g jar of cosmetic cream
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Surfactant agent for moisturizing creams
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	5 economic allocations (as described above), including the cosmetic cream price that represents 4.66% of an average shopping basket
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC is not considered; dLUC is considered as follows: Applied ILCD recommendations (2011, v1.06) about selection of impact characterisation methods: 12 midpoint impacts, including "Land Use" indicator [Brandao and Milà i Canals, 2013; Koellner et al., 2013; Milà i Canals et al., 2007a,b]. The indicator measures the change in the amount of organic matter in soil (30 cm depth) as a proxy to quantify how the use of a land area may impact the soil properties and functions; expressed in kg C deficit. It integrates the impact due to land <i>transformation</i> and <i>occupation</i> (restoration delay of potential

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	<p>Soil Organic Carbon + further actual degradation/improvement of SOC) relatively to a reference state.</p> <p>Gain/loss of SOC for transformation and occupation of the land are computed with ad-hoc formula, which consider the time needed to revert the SOC level in the reference state (i.e. relaxation time).</p>
<i>Geographic location, if defined</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Palm plantation: Malaysia - Palm oil transformation into cetaryl alcohol (transesterification & hydrogenation): Germania - Wheat production providing D-glucose: Northern France - Production of alkyl polyglucose (APG): Northern France - Final cream production: Southern France - Cream consumption: Europe market
<i>Data quality</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Background inventories: Ecoinvent v.3 database - Palm oil feedstock: mixed primary and secondary data from literature (plantation management and industrial plant) - Other biomass feedstock: Ecoinvent v.3 database - Industrial processing of cosmetic cream: primary data from a site-specific industry and secondary data for background processes (e.g. electricity production)
<i>Impact assessment method</i>	<p>ILCD recommendations (2011, v1.06) [EC-JRC, 2011]; 15 out of 16 impact categories used (not included "Water Depletion" due to inconsistencies between the water depletion impact assessment method and Ecoinvent v.3 database)</p>
<i>Damage categories (endpoint)</i>	<p>3 endpoint damage categories. Not clear which of the whole 15 impact categories are considered as endpoint (not specified the type of choice from ILCD recommendations). Probably: Climate Change, Human toxicity - cancer effects, Human toxicity - non-cancer effects</p>
<i>Impact categories (midpoint)</i>	<p>12 midpoint impact categories. Not clear which of the whole 15 impact categories are considered as midpoint (not specified the type of choice from ILCD recommendations). Probably: Freshwater ecotoxicity, Freshwater eutrophication, Terrestrial eutrophication, Marine eutrophication, Mineral, fossil & renewable resource depletion, Ozone depletion, Particulate matter, Photochemical ozone formation, Ionizing radiation HH, Ionizing radiation E, Land Use</p>
<i>Other information or comments</i>	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Flow Diagram:

Fig. 1. Overview of the global system for 1 jar of cosmetic cream.

Life cycle stages (baseline scenario):

- 1) Nursery stage of oil palm seeds, including production of polybags in polyethylene, production of PVC irrigation pipes, fertilizers, pesticides and road transport of seeds, fertilizers, pesticides between Malaysian port and nursery;
- 2) Palm seedlings transplanted in the oil palm plantation and cultivated for 25 years, density of 142 palms/ha;
- 3) Palm Fresh Fruit Bunches (FFB) harvested the whole year, starting the third plantation year;
- 4) Collected FFB are sent to the palm oil mill and sterilized within 24h;
- 5) Pulp from mesocarp and kernel is separated and processed with a screw press obtaining Crude Palm Oil (CPO);
- 6) Pressed mesocarp fibers and crushed kernel shells are burnt in the boiler to provide heat and power;
- 7) Pressing of kernel allows for the extraction of Crude Palm Kernel Oil (CPKO);
- 8) Palm Oil Mill Effluent (POME), which comprehends sterilization condensates and clarification waters, is conventionally treated in open anaerobic ponds (emitting biogenic methane to the air);
- 9) CPKO is chemically refined (degumming with acid and cleansing with bleaching earth);
- 10) Undesirable components (e.g. FFA) are stripped under vacuum (de-acidification and deodorization steps) producing Refined Palm Kernel Oil (RPKO);
- 11) RPKO is transported from Malaysia to France by trans-oceanic freight ship, then to Germany by train;
- 12) Transesterification of RPKO with methanol with sodium hydroxide;
- 13) Methanol is recovered and recycled in the process;
- 14) C-8/14 Methyl Ester is split from the C-16/18 Methyl Ester by distillation separation;

- 15) Continuous catalysed hydrogenation of the C-16/18 Methyl Ester under high temperature (250-300°C) and high Hydrogen pressure (25-35 MPa);
- 16) C-16/18 alcohol distilled to reach purity of more than 95%;
- 17) Meanwhile wheat is produced, harvested, washed and ground into flour (France);
- 18) Starch and gluten are separated and the resulting starch milk is hydrolyzed;
- 19) Demineralization, discoloration, concentration by evaporation and crystallization to obtain anhydrous D-glucose;
- 20) Crystallized D-glucose undergoes a Fischer Glucosylation with sodium hydroxide;
- 21) Unreacted glucose is removed by decantation and centrifugation;
- 22) Production of the palm-based surfactant: shaping of Alkyl Polyglucoside (APG) by pearlizing, starting from Cetearyl alcohol and crystallized D-glucose. Packaging (plastic bags and plastic film) is considered to be recovered with high recycling rate in the cosmetic cream plant, the remaining is incinerated;
- 23) Cream production: addition of water, Argan oil phase, Alkyl Polyguoside (APG) with emulsification process;
- 24) Packaging of the cream in a 30g jar made of HDPE and a tight fitting lid made of HDPE;
- 25) Each jar is packaged in a small cardboard box, wrapped in a HDPE film;
- 26) Transport to retailers and then to consumers;
- 27) Consumption phase;
- 28) Waste management phase: recycling (low), incineration and landfilling.

Life cycle inventory table:

Table 1
Life Cycle Inventory for the production of 23.57 kg of RPKO (from 1000 kg of FFB).

	Unit	FFB	Kernels	CPKO	RPKO
Output products					
FFB	kg	1,000 ^b			
Kernels	kg		53.2 ^b		
CPKO	kg			23.88 ^b	
RPKO	kg				23.57 ^b
CPO	kg		199.8 ^b		
EFB	kg		225 ^b		
POME	kg		672.5 ^b		
Palm kernel cake	kg			27.72 ^b	
Free Fatty Acid	kg				0.24 ^b
Input					
Soil transformation	m ²	20.9 ^b			
Soil occupation	m ² year	521.9 ^b			
Energy use					
Diesel: agriculture machinery	L	2.37 ^a	0.57 ^b		
Electricity from the grid	MJ		0.8 ^b	10.03 ^b	2.99 ^b
Electricity produced	MJ		31 ^b		
Heat (steam)	MJ				7.73 ^b
Material use					
Water	L		1,300 ^b	9.55 ^b	16.5 ^b
Oil palm seedling	Transplant	0.33 ^a			
Amonium sulfate	kg	8.05 ^a			
Urea	kg	0.41 ^a			
Ammonium nitrate	kg	0.76 ^a			
Ammonium chloride	kg	0.72 ^a			
Nitrogen fertilizer, as N	kg	3.49 ^a			
Potassium chloride, as K ₂ O	kg	11.60 ^a			
Potassium fertilizer, as K ₂ O	kg	4.50 ^a			
Phosphate rock, as P ₂ O ₅	kg	6.55 ^a			
Phosphate fertilizer, as P ₂ O ₅	kg	0.64 ^a			
Glyphosate	kg	0.34 ^a			
[Sufonyl]urea compounds	kg	0.15 ^a			
Bipyridylum compounds	kg	0.10 ^a			
Pyretroid compounds	kg	2.15 × 10 ^{-2a}			
Organophosphorus compounds	kg	6.40 × 10 ^{-2a}			
Dimethylamine	kg	3.10 × 10 ^{-2a}			
Pesticide unspecified	kg	2.13 ^a			

Phosphoric acid	kg				5.89×10^{-3b}
NaOH	kg				6.83×10^{-2b}
Bleaching earth	kg				1.06×10^{-1b}
Transport					
FFB to mill, lorry	tkm	50			
Fertilizer from plant to port, ship	tkm	171.95 ^b			
Pesticides from plant to port, ship	tkm	14.14 ^b			
Fertilizer from port to plantation, lorry	tkm	5.10 ^a			
Pesticides from port to plantation, lorry	tkm	0.15 ^a			
Raw material and ancillaries, lorry	tkm		0.1 ^b		
Kernel, lorry	tkm			4.2 ^b	
Palm kernel cake, lorry	tkm			1.1 ^b	
Phosphoric acid	tkm				5.89×10^{-3b}
NaOH	tkm				6.84×10^{-2b}
Bleaching earth	tkm				1.06×10^{-1b}
Diesel	tkm				3.77×10^{-2b}
Fodder fat	tkm				4.71×10^{-2b}
Emissions to air					
CO ₂	kg	0			
CO ₂ land transformation	kg	0 ^d			
NH ₃	kg	4.50×10^{-1c}	4.24×10^{-2b}		
N ₂ O	kg	$7.57 \times 10^{-2b,c}$	6.81×10^{-3b}		
NOx	kg	9.35×10^{-2e}	2.72×10^{-1b}		
CH ₄	kg		8.74 ^b		
H ₂ S	kg		5.79×10^{-2b}		
SO ₂	kg		2.4×10^{-3b}		
CO	kg		6.71×10^{-1b}		
Particulates, < 2.5 um	kg		1.51×10^{-1b}		
Acetaldehyde	kg		1.2×10^{-4b}		
Arsenic	kg		1.9×10^{-6b}		
Benzene	kg		1.73×10^{-3b}		
Benzene, ethyl-	kg		5.72×10^{-5b}		
Benzene, hexachloro-	kg		1.37×10^{-11b}		
Benzo(a)pyrene	kg		9.52×10^{-7b}		
Cadmium	kg		1.33×10^{-6b}		
Chlorine	kg		3.42×10^{-4b}		
Chromium	kg		7.54×10^{-6b}		
Chromium VI	kg		7.62×10^{-8b}		
Copper	kg		4.20×10^{-5b}		
Dioxin, 2,3,7,8 Tetrachlorodibenzo-p-	kg		5.90×10^{-11b}		
Formaldehyde	kg		2.48×10^{-4b}		
Hydrocarbons, aliphatic, alkanes, C10, branched	kg		1.73×10^{-3b}		
Hydrocarbons, aliphatic, unsaturated	kg		6×10^{-3b}		
Lead	kg		4.76×10^{-5b}		
m-Xylene	kg		2.28×10^{-4b}		
Manganese	kg		3.24×10^{-4b}		
Mercury	kg		5.72×10^{-7b}		
Nickel	kg		1.14×10^{-5b}		
NMVOC, non-methane volatile organic compounds	kg		1.71×10^{-3b}		
PAH, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons	kg		2.12×10^{-5b}		
Phenol, pentachloro-	kg		1.54×10^{-8b}		
Phosphorus	kg		5.72×10^{-4b}		
Toluene	kg		5.72×10^{-4b}		
Zinc	kg		5.72×10^{-4b}		
Emissions to water					
NO ₃ ⁻	kg	4.78 ^e		7.16×10^{-5b}	
PO ₄ ³⁻	kg	3.94×10^{-2f}			
P	kg				1.88×10^{-3b}
Emissions to soil					
Lead	mg	51.9 ^{A,R}			
Cadmium	mg	140 ^{A,R}			
Chromium	mg	1,480 ^{A,R}			
Nickel	mg	265 ^{A,R}			
Copper	mg	292 ^{A,R}			
Zinc	mg	2,460 ^{A,R}			
Mercury	mg	0.682 ^{A,R}			
Arsenic	mg	73.8 ^{A,R}			
Thallium	mg	3.93 ^{A,R}			
Glyphosate	kg	0.338 ^{A,R}			
Metsulfuron-methyl	kg	0.148 ^{A,R}			
Paraquat	kg	0.104 ^{A,R}			
Cypermethrin	kg	$2.15 \times 10^{-2A,R}$			
Glufosinate ammonium	kg	$3.20 \times 10^{-2A,R}$			
Methamidophos	kg	$3.20 \times 10^{-2A,R}$			
Carbofuran	kg	$3.50 \times 10^{-2A,R}$			
Dimethylamine	kg	$3.10 \times 10^{-2A,R}$			
Waste to treatment					
Waste water	kg				16.5 ^b
Bleaching earth to landfill	kg				1.51×10^{-1b}

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Jorge Cristobal, Cristina T. Matos, Jean-Philippe Aurambout, Simone Manfredi, and Boyan Kavalov, “Environmental sustainability assessment of bioeconomy value chains”. Biomass and Bioenergy, Vol. 89, 2016, pp 159-171. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2016.02.002
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Three value chains: (1) sugar production from sugar beet and sugar cane ; (2) biobased alcohols from industrial and agricultural waste, MSW, energy crop, forestry wood and residues and micro algae; and (3) polyhydroxyalkanoates from oil crops, lignocellulosic crops and residues, starch and sugar crops, and sugar and/or fatty acid rich wastes.
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Sugar (sugar molase, bagasse), alcohols: ethanol/methanol/butanol (glycerol), PHAs (bagasse, corn meals, energy surplus)
Functional unit	Sugar : 1kg of extractable sugar produced. Ethanol : driving a passenger car (flexible fuel vehicle) for 1 km. PHAs : 1 kg of polymer produced.
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Sugar and sugar molases for food/fuel/biopolymers/organic and amino acids. Alcohols for fuels/solvents. PHAs for coating/packaging.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Cane sugar: environmental impacts are divided between co-products acc. to their market price. Ethanol use phase: E85 blend.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Soil organic matter model: kg C deficit.
Geographic location, if defined	UE
Data quality	Literature review (peer reviewed)
Impact assessment method	Climate change: Bern model. Ozone depletion: EDIP model. Ecotoxicity for aquatic fresh water: USEtox model. Human toxicity and cancer effects: USEtox model. Human toxicity - non-cancer effects: USEtox model. Particulate matter/respiratory inorganics: RiskPoll model. Ionising radiation: human health effects: Human health effect model. Photochemical ozone formation: LOTOS-

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

	EUROS model. Acidification: Accumulated exceedance model. Eutrophication – terrestrial: Accumulated exceedance model. Eutrophication – aquatic and freshwater: EUTREND model. Eutrophication – aquatic-marine: EUTREND model. Resource depletion – water: Swiss ecoscarcity model. Resource depletion – mineral, fossil: CML2002 model. Land transformation: Soil organic matter model.
Damage categories (endpoint)	See above : human health impacts in terms ionising radiation, climate change, ozone depletion, photochemical ozone creation.
Impact categories (midpoint)	See above : e.g. ozone depletion potentials, global warming potentials, photochemical ozone (smog) creation potentials.
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

The authors discuss a number of LCA-based studies on environmental profile of different bioeconomy value chains. The paper (1) maps and analyses accessible LCA data relative to bioeconomy value chains in order to identify knowledge gaps; (2) provides a more robust and complete picture of the environmental performance of three exemplary bioeconomy value chains (i.e. one per each bioeconomy pillar). The case studies which are inter-related due to the use of sugar as feedstock: sugar production (for the food and feed pillar); bioalcohols production via fermentation (for the bioenergy pillar); and polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) production (for the bio-based product pillar) (Fig.1.)

Fig. 1. Flowcharts of production processes: sugar, alcohols, and PHAs.

The authors conclude that LCA data from EU research projects are limited and/or aggregated. As the results, it:

- reduces the feasibility of performing comparisons,
- points out high variability in published LCA results,
- shows that the individual LCA studies differ from each other with respect to several methodological assumptions: definition of the system boundaries, functional unit, energy recovery, carbon emissions and storage and allocation methods. All these differences influence considerably the environmental performance and the overall interpretation and comparison of results become rather challenging,
- they present low uniformity in the way the results are presented has been observed (e.g. different terminologies are used for the same impact),
- can lead to misinterpretation of results.

All the findings the strong need for methodological harmonisation and coherence for LCA of bioeconomy value chains.

Example of summary table

2

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ²	Spyros Foteinis, Victor Kouloumpis, and Theocharis Tsoutsos, “Life cycle analysis for bioethanol production from sugar beet crops in Greece”. Energy Policy, 39, 2011, 4834–4841.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Sugar beet
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Main : ethanol, by-product : animal feed
Functional unit	Dimensionless Pt, MJ/L
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Biofuel
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Mass allocation: 8000 kg of animal feed reduces environmental impact by 17%. 1000 kg of manure reduces environmental impact by 3.57% and 420.7 kg CO ₂ e/ha (substitution of synthetic fertilizers)
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Yes
Geographic location, if defined	Greece
Data quality	Poor
Impact assessment method	CML 2 baseline method, Eco-indicator 99
Damage categories (endpoint)	Human health, ecosystem quality, resources
Impact categories (midpoint)	Carcinogens, respiratory organics, respiratory inorganics, climate change, radiation, ozone layer, ecotoxicity, acidification/eutrofication, land use and resource depletion

² The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Other information or comments

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

The whole process is divided into three main phases: cultivation (LCA load: 31.9%), transportation to ethanol plant (23%) and processing to ethanol (17.1%). The flowchart is presented in the figure 2. Co-product (animal feed) reduces environmental load by 17.1%. There were compared few variants: bioethanol production, sugar production, conventional fuel (gasoline), biodiesel (Greek cultivation).

Fig. 2. Flowchart of life cycle stages and their environmental loads (sugar beet to ethanol).

Tool: SimaPro7.14. Functional unit 146.4 GJ equal to 6800 L or 5440 kg of EtOH equal to 65 t of sugar beet equal to yield per 1 ha. Eco-indicator 99 was used to classify loads into 10 categories: carcinogens, respiratory organics, respiratory inorganics, climate change, radiation, ozone layer, ecotoxicity, acidification/eutrofication, land use and resource depletion. Then the categories were aggregated into 3 damage categories – human health, ecosystem quality, and resources and measured in the dimensionless Eco-indicator points (Pt). Acc. to eco-indicator 99 methodology the three perspectives were characterised: Hierarchist, Individualistic, and Egalitarian on the basis of time perspective, manageability, and required level of evidence. In the study the Egalitarian perspective was taken into account considering that problems can lead to catastrophe and considers all possible effects, following the precautionary principle. Besides, CO₂ emissions were assessed acc. to CML 2 baseline method.

Inventory data.

Table 1
Nutrients and pesticides consumed per ha and 1 L of bioethanol.

Nutrients	Quantity per ha	Quantity for the production of 1 L of bioethanol	Pesticides	Quantity per ha (kg)	Quantity for the production of 1 L of bioethanol (g)
Water	4500 L	0.662 L	Maneb	10.000	1.471
Fertilizers			Desmedipham	0.233	0.034
Nitrogen (N)	120 kg	0.018 kg	Phenmedipham	0.233	0.034
Potassium (K ₂ O)	200 kg	0.030 kg	Ethofusanate	0.233	0.034
Phosphorus (P ₂ O ₅)	100 kg	0.015 kg	Metamitron	2.470	0.363
			Parafinic oil	3.500	0.515
			Haloxypoph	0.133	0.020
			Methidathion	2.000	0.294

Table 2
Energy used for the machinery in the stage of sugar beet cultivation.

Agricultural process	Machinery used	times per ha	Minutes of tractor operation per ha	Diesel (L/ha)	Diesel energy per ha (MJ)	Energy needs for the production of 1 L of bioethanol (J)
Plowing	Tillage, plowing	1	40	6.0	231.6	34.1
Planting	Planting	1	50	6.7	258.6	38.03
Irrigation	Irrigating	1	-	-	-	-
Fertilizing	Fertilizing, by broadcaster	6	360	45.0	1737.0	255.4
Tillage	Tillage, harrowing, by spring tine harrow	1	20	3.0	115.8	17.03
Harvest	Harvesting, by complete harvester, beers	1	100	13.8	532.7	78.3

Chosen findings:

- 1 kg of produced sugar beet can absorb 0.32 kg CO₂ (C sequestration)
- Differentiation in bioethanol production was presented on the basis of synthetic fertilizer and manure application. Those findings were compared with sugar production (marginal differences) and gasoline (42% less in the case of bioethanol production) and biodiesel (less impact than bioethanol, differences depend on the oilseed crop)
- Ethanol from sugar beet can be an equal environmental alternative to biodiesel.

Example of summary table

3

Item	Case study
Reference <i>(full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”³)</i>	Hubert Halleux, Stephane Lassaux, Robert Renzoni, Albert Germain, “Comparative Life Cycle Assessment of Two Biofuels. Ethanol from Sugar Beet and Rapeseed Methyl Ester”, <i>The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment</i> , 13(3), 2008, 184–190.
Type of study <i>(check at least 1)</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Sugar beet for ethanol & rapeseed for methyl ester
Bio-products and form <i>(please cite all co- and by-products)</i>	Main product from sugar beet: ethanol, by-product : animal feed (pulp) Main product from rapeseed : ethyl ester, by-product : animal feed (rapeseed meal)
Functional unit	100 km covered with a middle-size and recent car
Product family <i>(check at least 1)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Biofuels, animal feed
Boundaries <i>(check all included stages)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps <i>(to be detailed in the report section)</i> <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach <i>(leave blank if unclear)</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting <i>(check 1)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Mass: kg/kg (production, equivalent protein peas, equivalent wheat). The values of rapeseed meal and sugar beet pulps have been estimated in the function of their protein, sugar and starch contents. Rapeseed: millipoint/100 km (allocation coefficient 36.5 for rapeseed meal and 13.6 for glycerin)
Inclusion of land use change <i>(please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)</i>	Yes, but separately from other impacts. The credit equal to the surface that would have been used for the equivalent wheat and protein peas production. (the credit of rapeseed meal is higher than in the case of pulps of sugar beet.)
Geographic location, if defined	EU
Data quality	medium
Impact assessment method	Eco-Indicator 99, SimaPro 7.1 databases (LCI of extraction, production, distribution of fossil fuels (petron and diesel))
Damage categories (endpoint)	Normalisation factor: the impact of an average European person and weighting

³ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

	factors are 400 for human health, 400 for ecosystem quality and 200 for resources.
Impact categories (midpoint)	Carcinogenic effects, inorganic respiratory effects, organic respiratory effects, global warming, ecotoxicity, acidification and eutrophication, fossil fuel
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

The study perform the LCA of the production and use of ethanol from sugar beet and rapeseed methyl ester.

The system boundaries include: cultivation and processing for biofuels, extraction and refining for fossil fuels), but also the final use of the fuel and the valorization of the different by-products. This valorization is taken into account by subtracting the impacts of the production of the chemicals or animal feed, which these by-products substitute.

The functional unit: 100 km covered with a middle-size and recent car.

The Eco-Indicator 99 method has been used to estimate environmental impact categories: Carcinogenic effects, inorganic respiratory effects, organic respiratory effects, global warming, ecotoxicity, acidification and eutrophication, fossil fuel.

The chosen cultural perspective is the hierarchist one. Normalization factor is the impact of an average European person and weighting factors are 400 for human health, 400 for ecosystem quality and 200 for resources.

LCI: Fossil fuels: Simapro 7.1 databases. Energy consumption and exhaust emissions of vehicles (Tab.1), mass balance of the crops and mass (Tab.2) and energy balance of RME production (processing) (Tab.3) come from different literature sources.

Equivalencies of the by-products with reference animal feed:

- rapeseed 2224 kg/ha: equivalent protein peas 1.87 kg/kg, wheat -0.97 kg/kg
- pulps from sugar beet (dried) 3060 kg/ha: equivalent protein peas 0.58 kg/kg, wheat -0.28 kg/kg.

Acc. to the study, in comparison with fossil fuels RME reduce environmental impacts by 59% and ethanol by 30%.

In the recommendation the authors point out that:

The production of biofuels allows an improvement of the environmental impacts in comparison to fossil fuels. However, impacts are still considerable, especially for ethanol from sugar beet, where improvements should be made to reduce the energetic consumption of the processing.

The impacts of arable land consumption have only been taken into account qualitatively, but RME had a lower impact than bio-ethanol. The addition of this impact to the other environmental impacts would have been unfavorable to the two biofuels in comparison to fossil fuels and could have changed the conclusions of this study.

Conclusions and Outlook. The choice of functional units significantly affects the final results. Thus the functional unit in a descriptive LCA should reflect as nearly as possible the actual situation associated with a product system. Considering the current situation of constrained ethanol fuel supply, the E10 fuel application offers better environmental performance in natural resources used, nonrenewable energy and global warming unless the fuel economy of an E85 fueled vehicle is close to that of an E10 fueled vehicle

Table 1: Energetic consumption and exhaust emissions of vehicles [11,14]

	Petrol	Diesel	Ethanol	RME
Consumption (MJ/100 km)	223,5	183,1	223,5	183,1
CO ₂ (fossil) (kg/100 km)	16,6	13,4	–	0,74
CH ₄ (mg/100 km)	2,4	7,6	2,4	7,6
N ₂ O (mg/100 km)	0,129	0,0645	0,129	0,0645
NO _x (mg/100 km)	10,2	25,6	6,35	28,2
Particulates (mg/100 km)	0,5	3,56	0,5	1,89
NM VOC (mg/100 km)	2,53	9,59	6,36	3,17

Table 2: Mass balance of the crops (kg/ha) [3,4,5,12]

	Rapeseed	Sugar beet
N fertilizer	144	135
K ₂ O	74	212,5
P ₂ O ₅	74	125
Pesticides	2,3	5,3
Fuel consumed	111,3	101
RME produced	1406	–
Ethanol produced	–	4104

Table 3: Mass and energy balance of RME production [6,12,13]

	Heat (MJ/t RME)	Electricity (kWh/t RME)	Chemicals (kg/t RME)	By-products (kg/t RME)
Drying	812	33	–	–
Extraction	2317	106	Hexane: 2,7	Meal: 1582
Refining	162	11	–	–
Esterification	947	37	Methanol: 109	Glycerin: 100

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ⁴	Benedikt Buchspies, Martin Kaltschmitt, “Life cycle assessment of bioethanol from wheat and sugar beet discussing environmental impacts of multiple concepts of co-product processing in the context of the European Renewable Energy Directive”, Biofuels, Vol 7, No 2, 2016, pp. 141-153, DOI: 10.1080/17597269.2015.1122472
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	maize grain (USA), maize stover (USA), sugarcane (North-East of Brazil and Centre-South of Brazil), sugar beet and wheat (France)
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Main product: ethanol from different feedstock as a solvent in household and personal care products Co-product: stover in maize grain production, straw in wheat production
Functional unit	1 kg ethanol (water content 5%) Reference: 1 kg of ethanol produced from fossils in Western Europe.
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Sugar and sugar molasses for food/fuel/biopolymers/organic and amino acids. Alcohols for fuels/solvents. PHAs for coating/packaging.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Based on economic value.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	LUC estimations for all crops were assessed
Geographic location, if defined	USA, Brasil, France
Data quality	Medium
Impact assessment method	Indicators from the ReCiPe method; Ecoinvent 2.2 datasets for bioenergy production
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	ReCiPe : terrestrial acidification potential (TAP), freshwater eutrophication potential (FEP), marine eutrophication potential (MEP), photochemical oxidant formation potential (POFP) and agricultural land occupation (ALO).With regard to the assessment of GHG emissions, global warming potentials (GWP) from carbon

⁴ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

dioxide (CO₂) and methane for 100-year period for a 100-year period, accounting for methane oxidation in the atmosphere and considering biogenic CO₂ emissions as neutral, with the exception of those resulting from land use change (LUC).

BES: biodiversity damage potential (BDP), climate regulation potential (CRP), biotic production potential (BPP), freshwater regulation potential (FWRP), erosion regulation potential (ERP), water purification potential through physicochemical filtration (WPPPCF) and water purification potential through mechanical filtration (WPP-MF) (Saad et al. 2013).

Water use was inventoried but not reported.

Other information or comments

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

The aim: to assess ethanol as a feedstock for the chemical industry; to assess a relatively high number of production routes; to incorporate a full set of novel impact categories focusing on BES (biodiversity and ecosystem services); and thorough sensitivity and uncertainty analyses are carried out to ensure the robustness of the results. The product system of the study is presented in the figure 1.

Fig. 1. The product system of the study.

Functional unit : 1 kg of ethanol (5% of water). The key data used are set in the Table 1.

Land use (land occupation) was directly obtained from the yield and the cultivation period, which is 7 months for maize, 8 months for wheat and 5 months for sugar beet. Sugarcane is cultivated for 5.5 years, after which a fallow period of 6 months is required before fields can be replanted. The latter was also taken into account as occupation. The expected biome within each country and region was determined by expert judgement : two biomes were considered for maize, assuming a 50/50 split. Generic characterisation factors for BES were used for this type of land. Generic factors were also used for occupation flows associated to fossil-based ethanol.

LUC attributable to each crop was determined at a country level. The GHG emissions due to LUC were calculated according to Flynn et al. (2012), taking into account the climate zone, soil type, land use, crop type and country.

GHG emissions from end-of-life. Ethanol is used as a solvent in household and personal care products. As a consequence, ethanol will be degraded after being discharged to the environment, either to air, or to water via urban sewage. In the study, it was considered release to air by evaporation after use, which is a plausible assumption given the relatively low boiling point of ethanol (78.4 °C). After release, part of the ethanol is degraded abiotically to CO₂ in air but part is also expected to end up in water bodies, where it could be degraded to methane if anaerobic conditions are present. Emissions of CO₂ and methane following release of ethanol to air were estimated as 1.85 and 0.023 kg per kg ethanol, respectively. This equals to 0.58 and 2.49 kg CO₂eq per kg of bio-ethanol and fossil ethanol, respectively, after applying the GWP values.

Several aspects were subject to a sensitivity analysis to check their influence on the results of the ReCiPe impact indicators: allocation in ethanol production, pre-harvest burning of sugar cane, maize grain drying, GHG emission from LUC, choice of biomes.

Conclusions: environmental impacts from bio-based ethanol are highly dependent on the characteristics of the production chain considered, as well as on modelling and scenario choices, such as the choice of allocation factors, or the need to dry the product after harvest. The key factors found in the study are the net product yield per hectare and year (combination of agricultural yield plus yield in the processing stage) and especially modelling of emissions caused by LUC. Given the increasing

importance of bio-based products in the global economy, the authors call the LCA community to **initiate a debate to harmonise the modelling of LUC emissions**.

Table 1 Key figures for the cultivation and processing of the different feedstocks under study (Flury and Jungbluth 2012)

Cultivation	Unit	Sugarcane, BR CS	Sugarcane, BR NE	Maize grain, US	Maize grain and stover, US ^a	Sugar beet, FR	Wheat, FR
Yield, main product	kg/ha	82,697	57,677	9,703	9,703	84,649	6,605
Allocation	%				81 %		100 %
Co-product					Stover		Straw
Yield, by-product	kg/ha				4,676		0
Allocation	%				19 %		0 %
Seed	kg/ha	6,616	4,614	21	21	2	135
N-fertiliser	kg/ha	76	31	157	167	103	150
P ₂ O ₅ fertiliser	kg N/ha	25	22	67	73	68	24
K ₂ O fertiliser	kg P ₂ O ₅ /ha	102	75	82	120	146	23
Lime	kg/ha	305	213	366	366	0.1	12
Pesticides	kg/ha	6	4	3	2.5	3	3
Diesel	kg/ha	129	90	46	46	160	68
Land burned in pre-harvest	%	70 %	70 %				
Land transformation	ha/ha	0.032	0.032				0.016
Transport, total	tkm/ha	2,771	1,933	479	479	1,432	338
Water consumption	m ³ /ha	1,884	4,579	3,168	3,168	184	87
Processing	Unit	Sugarcane, BR CS	Sugarcane, BR NE	Maize grain, US	Maize stover, US ^a	Sugar beet, FR	Wheat, FR
Feedstock input	kg/kg ethanol	15.4	15.4	2.5	3.9	16.9	2.5
Chemicals	kg/kg ethanol	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.21	0.43	0.02
Electricity	kWh/kg ethanol			0.17		0.09	0.1
Heat	MJ/kg ethanol			2.6			5.1
Transport	tkm/kg ethanol	0.33	0.33	0.19	0.43	0.98	0.27
Water consumption	L/kg ethanol	-6.1	-6.1	-0.3	4.9	6.5	0.31
Allocation factors:							
Ethanol	%	50 %	50 %	84 %	87 %	89 %	73 %
Electricity	%	8 %	8 %		13 %		
Sugar	%	41 %	41 %				
Vinasse	%	0.30 %	0.30 %				
Filter cake	%	0.30 %	0.30 %				
DDGS	%			16 %			27 %
Pulp	%					11 %	
Overall ethanol yield	kg/ha	2,693	1,873	3,299	4,350	4,423	1,914

^a Cultivation data refers to maize cultivation and harvesting of both grain and stover. Allocation is then applied to determine the burdens of stover. Processing data refers to stover only

1) Summary table

See example on page 3

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ⁵	Vercalsteren An, Boonen Katrien, “Life Cycle Assessment study of starch products for the European starch industry association (Starch Europe): sector study”, Report no. 2015/SMAT/R/0083, Flemish Institute for Technological Research NV “VITO”, pp. 30
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	wheat, maize, potatoes
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	starch slurries, liquid glucose, fiber rich feed
Functional unit	the production of 1 ton d.s. (dry substance) of reference products at the starch plant exit gate
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	dry mass allocation for starch products and energy allocation for energy production in CHP unit
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Direct Land Use Change Assessment Tool (Version 2014.1 - 21 January 2014) developed by Blonk Consultants was used
Geographic location, if defined	EU 27
Data quality	secondary data for agricultural production, primary data for starch and starch products
Impact assessment method	methods recommended by ILCD (2011) and the PEF Guide were used (table 1)
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Climate Change, Ozone Depletion, Ecotoxicity for aquatic fresh water, Human Toxicity – cancer effects, Human Toxicity – noncancer effects, Particulate Matter/Respiratory Inorganics, Ionising Radiation – human health effects,

⁵ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

	Photochemical Ozone Formation, Acidification, Eutrophication – terrestrial, Eutrophication – aquatic, Resource Depletion – water, Resource Depletion – mineral fossil, Land Use/ Transformation
Other information or comments	link to the study: https://www.starch.eu/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/LCA-study-summary-report-2015-update.pdf

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Figure 2: Generic presentation of system boundaries

The following life cycle stages are included in a cradle-to-gate approach:

1. Cradle-to-raw materials/upstream processes: These are all the processes upstream of the starch production stage, starting with the resource extraction. This includes:
 - agricultural processes: growing of maize, wheat or potatoes, including soil cultivation, sowing, weed control, fertilisation, pest and pathogen control, harvest and drying (when relevant);
 - the production of energy;
 - the production of chemicals needed for manufacturing starch industry products (caustic soda, hydrochloric acid etc.);
 - Transport steps: Transport of raw materials from the field/plants to the starch plants is included here.
2. Factory alone/gate-to-gate/core processes: This focuses on Starch Europe member companies producing the reference products. The processes that are included depend on the specific starch industry product, e.g. dry cleaning, wet cleaning, rasping, steeping, degerminating, grinding/flour milling, dough preparation, separation, sieving, dewatering, washing, refining, mixing & drying, evaporation, drying, solubilizing, pressing, protein separation, conversion, hydrogenation, special polyol process, maltodextrine process, crystallization, fermentation and distillation.

Tab. 1. Overview of the environmental impact categories and impact assessment models for PEF

EF Impact Category	EF Impact Assessment Model	EF Impact Category indicators	Source
Climate Change	Bern model - Global Warming Potentials (GWP) over a 100 year time horizon.	kg CO ₂ equivalent	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2007
Ozone Depletion	EDIP model based on the ODPs of the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) over an infinite time horizon.	kg CFC-11 (*) equivalent	WMO, 1999
Ecotoxicity for aquatic fresh water	USEtox model	CTUe (Comparative Toxic Unit for ecosystems)	Rosenbaum et al., 2008
Human Toxicity - cancer effects	USEtox model	CTUh (Comparative Toxic Unit for humans)	Rosenbaum et al., 2008
Human Toxicity – non-cancer effects	USEtox model	CTUh (Comparative Toxic Unit for humans)	Rosenbaum et al., 2008
Particulate Matter/Respiratory Inorganics	RiskPoll model	kg PM _{2,5} (**) equivalent	Humbert, 2009
Ionising Radiation – human health effects	Human Health effect model	kg U 235 equivalent (to air)	Dreicer et al., 1995
Photochemical Ozone Formation	LOTOS-EUROS model	kg NMVOC (***) equivalent	Van Zelm et al., 2008 as applied in ReCiPe
Acidification	Accumulated Exceedance model	mol H ⁺ eq	Seppälä et al., 2006; Posch et al., 2008
Eutrophication – terrestrial	Accumulated Exceedance model	mol N eq	Seppälä et al., 2006; Posch et al., 2008
Eutrophication – aquatic	EUTREND model	fresh water: kg P equivalent marine: kg N equivalent	Struijs et al., 2009 as implemented in ReCiPe
Resource Depletion – water	Swiss Ecoscarcity model	m ³ water use related to local scarcity of water	Frischknecht et al., 2008
Resource Depletion – mineral, fossil	CML2002 model	kg antimony (Sb) equivalent	van Oers et al., 2002
Land Use/ Transformation	Soil Organic Matter (SOM) model	Kg (deficit)	Milà i Canals et al., 2007
(*) CFC-11 = Trichlorofluoromethane, also called freon-11 or R-11, is a chlorofluorocarbon. (**) PM _{2,5} = Particulate Matter with a diameter of 2,5 µm or less. (***) NMVOC = Non-Methane Volatile Organic Compounds			

1) Summary table
See example on page 3

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ⁶	Zucaro, Amalia, Forte, Annachiara, Fagnano, Massimo, Bastianoni, Simone., Basosi, Riccardo, Fierro, Angelo, «Comparative attributional life cycle assessment of annual and perennial lignocellulosic feedstocks production under Mediterranean climate for biorefinery framework », Integrated Environmental Assessment and Management, vol. 11, no. 3,2015, pp. 397-403. doi: 10.1002/ieam.1604
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Fiber sorghum, giant reed
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	
Functional unit	system boundary and functional unit were set as 1 ha of cropped land and 1 kg of drybiomass harvested, respectively, in the year 2012
Product family (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	ethanol, feedstock for integrated biorefineries
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	n/a
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	n/a
Geographic location, if defined	Southern Italy
Data quality	primary data for yield, diesel consumption, typology, and application rate of mineral fertilizers, irrigation system, and the amount of water ; secondary for the rest of the input
Impact assessment method	ReCiPe H Ver 1.08 midpoint
Damage categories (endpoint)	

⁶ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Impact categories (midpoint)

climate change, ozone depletion, terrestrial acidification, freshwater eutrophication, marine eutrophication, photochemical oxidant formation, particulate matter formation, water depletion, fossil depletion

Other information or comments

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Tab. 1. Input and output flows for the annual fiber sorghum (FS) and perennial giant reed (GR) cultivations

Input			GR	FS	Unit
Seedbed preparation ^a					
Ripping and hoeing	Combined rotary harrow	Diesel oil	12	20.5	L ha ⁻¹
Pre-plant fertilization	Combined fertilizer spreader	Diesel oil	5	5	L ha ⁻¹
		Urea 46% (as N)	–	50	kg ha ⁻¹
		Triple superphosphate (as P ₂ O ₅)	150	150	kg ha ⁻¹
		Potassium sulphate (as K ₂ O)	150	150	kg ha ⁻¹
Crop establishment ^a					
Seeding	Rhizomes planting GR; seeds machinery FS	Diesel oil	12	10	L ha ⁻¹
		Seeds	–	17	kg ha ⁻¹
		Rhizomes ^b	10 000	–	rhizomes ha ⁻¹
Rescue irrigation	Pump irrigation system	Diesel oil	26	26	L ha ⁻¹
		Water (well in ground)	560	560	m ³ ha ⁻¹
Field maintenance					
Late N fertilization	Combined fertilizer spreader	Diesel oil	5	5	L ha ⁻¹
		Urea 46% (as N)	120	100	kg ha ⁻¹
Harvest					
	Mower	Diesel oil	15.8	16.5	L ha ⁻¹
	Swath, by rotary windrower	Diesel oil	–	8	L ha ⁻¹
	Baling	Diesel oil	66	46	L ha ⁻¹
	Loading bales	Diesel oil	70.5	40	L ha ⁻¹
Final removal ^c					
	Mower	Diesel oil	6.4	–	L ha ⁻¹
	Pressurized sprayer	Diesel oil	2.6	–	L ha ⁻¹
		Roundup (as glyphosate)	2.7	–	kg ha ⁻¹
	Potato digger	Diesel oil	70	–	L ha ⁻¹
	Combined rotary harrow	Diesel oil	70	–	L ha ⁻¹
Output: Harvested biomass (d.w.)—dry weight			30	30	t ha ⁻¹

^aAgricultural practices performed for GR only in the first year of cultivation and therefore to be properly shared for the whole lifetime.

^bA specific record for GR rhizome preparation was implemented in SimaPro based on primary data about machineries and related fuel consumption, used for rhizomes explantation (earthing up, 70L diesel oil ha⁻¹), collection and transport (combine harvester, 2.2 L diesel oil ha⁻¹), and cutting (band saw by tractor supply).

^cAgricultural practice performed only for GR at the end of the fifteenth year of cultivation and therefore to be properly shared for the whole lifetime.

Figure 1. System boundaries and functional units for fiber sorghum (FS) and giant reed (GR) from raw materials and energy to create 1 kg of dry biomass per hectare. Blue boxes include the annual practices for crop management, whereas the white dotted boxes represent the farm boundaries. For GR, the agricultural practices were performed once for crop establishment and final dismissing, which were properly shared for the crop's lifetime (15 years). DFE = direct field emissions; SOC = soil organic carbon

1) Summary table

See example on page 3

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ⁷	Gilani, Banafsheh, Stuart, Paul R., Life cycle assessment of an integrated forest biorefinery: hot water extraction process case study, <i>Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining</i> , Vol. 9, No. 6, 2015, pp. 677-695. doi: 10.1002/bbb.1570
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): techno-economic analysis
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	forest biomass (woodchips)
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	biogas, concentrated hemicellulose (70% d.m.), concentrated hemicellulose (50% d.m.), acetate salt, C5 sugars, furfural
Functional unit	310 000 tons per year of dilute hemicellulose stream
Product family (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	heat, hemicellulose for animal feed, hemicellulose for C5 sugars, solvents for extraction of lubricating oil
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	system expansion
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	n/a
Geographic location, if defined	Canada
Data quality	secondary and primary data
Impact assessment method	IMPACT 2002+ method (version 2.15)
Damage categories (endpoint)	human health, ecosystem quality, climate change, and resources
Impact categories (midpoint)	
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

⁷ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Figure 1. Simplified block flow diagram for HWE-based biorefinery process options.

Fig. 2. System boundary for "C5-sugars and acetate salt" process option.

1) Summary table

See example on page 3

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ⁸	Mandegari, Mohsen Ali, Farzad, Somayah., von Rensburg, Eugene, and Görgens, Johann. F, «Multi - criteria analysis of a biorefinery for co-production of lactic acid and ethanol from sugarcane lignocellulose, Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining, doi: 10.1002/bbb.1801 (in press)
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): economic assessment
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	sugar cane bagasses and brown leaves
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	ethanol, lactic acid
Functional unit	different FU (check below)
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	intermediate chemicals, for example pyruvic acid, acetaldehyde; (ii) production of biodegradable polymers such as poly lactic acid (PLA) exploited in the food industry (packaging) as well as pharmaceutical industry, for example internal drug dosing (iii) manufacture of hygiene products for cosmetic industry; and (iv) use in the food and beverage sector as a preservative.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	not clear (check below)
Inclusion of land	n/a

⁸ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

use change <i>(please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)</i>	
Geographic location, if defined	South Africa
Data quality	The main input and output data for each stage of biorefinery were collected from simulation results developed by Aspen Plus®, whereas inventory of sugarcane cultivation and bagasse production were developed using data from literature
Impact assessment method	CML-IA baseline 3.2
Damage categories (endpoint)	abiotic depletion, global warming potential (GWP100), acidification, eutrophication, ozone depletion (ODP), photochemical oxidation (POCP), terrestrial and aquatic ecotoxicity, human toxicity
Impact categories (midpoint)	
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Allocation and Functional Unit

“Under the current study, the allocation procedure is not avoidable for unit-pro-cesses generating multiple co-products, for example sugar mill producing sugar, molasses, bagasse, and filter cake. Moreover, allocation by physical relationships (either mass or energy content) cannot reflect the underlying relationships between the co-products under an economic-value driven multi-product system.”

To provide a reference flow for all investigated scenarios, a biorefinery with the capacity to process 65 t/h DM bagasse and trash was simulated for the scenarios. Whereas, for the com-parison of scenarios with LA production, ‘1 tonne LA produced’ was defined as the functional unit. The scenarios were compared with the baseline situation where bagasse is combusted for electricity production, and here the functional unit was expressed as ‘1 MWh electricity produced.

Scenario 1 (EtOH and Electricity production)

Scenario 2 (LA and Electricity production)

Scenario 3 (EtOH from cellulose, LA from hemicellulose and Electricity production)

Scenario 4 (EtOH from hemicellulose, LA from cellulose and Electricity production)

Fig. 1. Schematic block flow diagram of the studied biorefinery scenarios.

Fig. 2. System boundary

Table 1. Overall mass and energy balance of the developed biorefinery scenarios.

Parameter	Unit	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4
		EtOH from slurry	LA from slurry	EtOH from cellulose, LA from hemicellulose	LA from cellulose, EtOH from hemicellulose
Bypass of lignocellulose to boiler	%	35	40	40	40
Feedstock to biorefinery (DM)	t/h	42.25	39	39	39
Ethanol production rate	kg/h	11002	-	7478	2020
	liter/h	14160	-	9624	2600
Lactic acid production rate	kg/h	-	19223	4647	14419
Net power to grid	MW	7.1	7.5	5.7	6.5
	MWh/y	46000	48000	30000	42000
Cooling demand	MW	54.2	45.8	49.4	47.2
Heating demand*	MW	69.1	67.6	68.4	67.7
Power demand*	MW	2.0	2.2	2.1	2.1

* Sugar mill consumption (heating: 86.0 MW and power: 11.0 MW)³⁵ was excluded.

1) Summary table

See example on page 3

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ⁹	Tao, Ling, Tan, Eric C. D., McCormick, Robert, Zhang, Min, Aden, Andy, He, Xin., and Zigler, Bradley T., Techno-economic analysis and life-cycle assessment of cellulosic isobutanol and comparison with cellulosic ethanol and n-butanol, <i>Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining</i> , 8(1), 30-48. doi: 10.1002/bbb.1431
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): techno-economic assessment
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	corn stover
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	isobutanol, n-butanol, ethanol, acetone
Functional unit	1 km traveled by a flex-fuel passenger car
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	biofuel-gasoline blends,
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	check below
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	n/a
Geographic location, if defined	United States
Data quality	process modeling outputs from AspenPlus software
Impact assessment method	GWP 100
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	GHG
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

⁹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Allocation

The share of environmental burdens associated with the corn stover production was allocated using the product-purpose approach. With the product purpose allocation method, all environmental burdens associated with corn grain production were assigned to the corn grain. Any additional burdens required to harvest the stover (e.g. additional nutrient replacement) were assigned to the corn stover.

Neither cellulosic isobutanol nor ethanol process plants were assumed to make any liquid co-product. However, during cellulosic n-butanol production, the biorefinery also produced acetone and ethanol. Ethanol was a liquid fuel and acetone was considered as a chemical solvent and feedstock. Both co-products were treated as an avoided product using the product displacement method. The same method was used for excess electricity production.

Table 2. Key parameters for corn stover production.

Parameters	Values
Corn stover yield (dry t/ha)	5.38
Dry matter loss during harvesting (%)	5.00
Nitrogen application (kg N/t of stover removed)	9.00
Phosphorus application (kg P ₂ O ₅ /t of stover removed)	0.99
Potassium (kg K ₂ O/t of stover removed)	15.0
N ₂ O conversion rate of N fertilizer (%)	1.33
Harvest moisture (%)	20.0

Table 3. Key parameters for corn stover conversion.

	Ethanol	Isobutanol	N-butanol
Conversion outputs			
Biofuel yield (L/DMT)	330	242	200
Co-product outputs			
Acetone (L/DMT)	–	–	8.09
Ethanol (L/DMT)	–	–	35.8
Electricity export (kWh/MJ)	0.023	0.020	0.025
Conversion inputs (consumption)			
Sulfuric acid (g/MJ)	3.37	3.50	4.29
Ammonia (NH ₃) (g/MJ)	1.79	1.86	2.27
Corn steep liquor (CSL) (g/MJ)	1.97	2.04	2.50
Diammonium phosphate (g/MJ)	0.24	0.25	0.31
Caustic soda (NaOH) (g/MJ)	3.83	3.99	4.88
Lime (CaOH) (g/MJ)	1.52	1.61	1.97
Enzyme loading (g/MJ)	23.5	24.4	30.0
Sugar for enzyme production (g/g enzyme)	0.17	0.17	0.17
NH ₃ for enzyme production (g/g enzyme)	0.01	0.01	0.01
CSL for enzyme production (g/g enzyme)	0.01	0.01	0.01

Table 4. GHG emissions and fossil energy consumption for producing petroleum-based acetone and corn grain-derived ethanol as well as US electricity grid as modeled in SimaPro.

	GHG emissions	Fossil energy	Displacement factor
Petroleum-based acetone	2.22 kg CO ₂ -eq/kg	64.8 MJ/kg	1 kg of cellulosic acetone displaces 1 kg of petroleum-based acetone
Ethanol from corn grain	2.05 kg CO ₂ -eq/kg	20.8 MJ/kg	1 kg of cellulosic ethanol displaces 1 kg of corn-based ethanol
Average US electricity mix*	0.78 kg CO ₂ -eq/kWh	9.08/kWh	1 kWh of electricity from biorefinery displaces 1 kWh of US average grid electricity

* Coal (47%), natural gas (17%), Oil (3.3%), nuclear power (20%), biomass (1.1%), wind (0.35%), solar (0.015%), hydroelectric (8.2%), and others (2.5%).

Figure 2. Distance and allocations for fuel product transport from biorefinery to pump

Fig. 3. Iso-butanol fermentation with simultaneous stripping and purification process block flow diagram

1) Summary table

See example on page 3

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹⁰	González-García, Sara., Hospido, Almudena., Agnemo, Roland., Svensson, Patrik., Selling, Eva., Moreira, Ma Teresa., and Feijoo, Gumersindo, « Environmental Life Cycle Assessment of a Swedish Dissolving Pulp Mill Integrated Biorefinery », Journal of Industrial Ecology, Vol.15, No. 4, pp. 568-583.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	blend of spruce and pine wood (80% and 20%, respectively)
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	dissolving cellulose, ethanol, lignosulfates
Functional unit	1 tonne of air-dried (10% moisture content), high-quality dissolving cellulose
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	production of cellulosic fibers (rayon and acetate), specialty papers (photographic papers, filters), viscose clothing and hygiene products as an alternative to cotton, specialty cellulose for pharmaceuticals, food industry as a binding agent, dispersants in concrete, brick, ceramic products, dye pigment, acetic acid or ethyl acetate
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	economic
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	n/a
Geographic location, if defined	Sweden
Data quality	mixed data (check below)
Impact assessment method	CML 2 baseline 2000 V2.1 method
Damage categories (endpoint)	

¹⁰ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Impact categories (midpoint)

abiotic depletion, global warming, ozone layer depletion, human toxicity, freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity, marine aquatic ecotoxicity, terrestrial ecotoxicity, photochemical oxidants formation, acidification, eutrophication

Other information or comments

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Fig. 1. Subsystems included in the system under study

Table 1 Data sources for the life cycle inventory

<i>Subsystem</i>	<i>Data required</i>	<i>Data sources</i>	<i>Collecting method</i>
Subsystem S1	Fuel use	Forest workers (González-García et al. 2009a, 2009c)	Questionnaires
	Fertilizer use	Research reports (Audsley et al. 1997; Arrouays et al. 2002; EMEP and CORINAIR 2006; Dones et al. 2007; Nemecek et al. 2007; Spielmann et al. 2007)	Interviews
	Labor use		Literature review
	Consumable materials transport (mode, capacity, and distance)		
	Nutrient-related emissions		
Subsystem S2	Production capacity	Research reports (Althaus et al. 2007; Doka 2007; Dones et al. 2007; Spielmann et al. 2007)	Questionnaires
	Chemicals use	Agnemo (2009)	Interviews
	Consumable materials transport (mode, capacity, and distance)	Assumptions (see table 4)	Literature review
	Energy requirements		
	Biological treatment plant (WWTP)		
	Landfill operation		

Table 2 Summary of energy and chemicals consumption in forestry (S1) per functional unit

<i>Stage</i>	<i>Silviculture operations</i>	<i>Logging operations</i>	<i>Secondary hauling</i>
Diesel ^a	1.67 kg	19.81 kg	32.45 kg
Fertilizer ^b	4.88 kg	—	—

Note: kg = kilograms.

^aTotal diesel requirements for agricultural activities, transport of inputs, and workers (average distance: 35 kilometers [km]).

^bAmmonium nitrate with dolomite and 27% of nitrogen.

Table 3 Global inventory data for biorefinery (S2) per functional unit

Input/ output	Source/ destination	Type	Item	Value
Input	Technosphere	Materials—biomass	Green logs (50% moisture)	6.11 m ³
Input	Technosphere	Materials—chemicals (100% purity)	H ₂ O ₂	64.72 kg
Input	Technosphere	Materials—chemicals (100% purity)	NaOH	107.80 kg
Input	Technosphere	Materials—chemicals (100% purity)	H ₂ SO ₃	3.32 kg
Input	Technosphere	Materials—chemicals (100% purity)	EDTA	2.47 kg
Input	Technosphere	Materials	Fuel oil	36.32 kg
Input	Technosphere	Energy	Electricity	1325 kWh ^a
Input	Technosphere	Energy	Steam	4,962 kWh ^b
Input	Technosphere	Transport	20–28-tonnes lorry	18.31 t km
Input	Technosphere	Transport	16-tonnes lorry	1.55 t km
Input	Environment	Materials	Water	185.6 m ³
Output	Technosphere	Materials to product	Bleached pulp ^c	1.00 tonne
Output	Technosphere	Materials to product—chemicals	Ethanol	59.52 kg
Output	Technosphere	Materials to product—chemicals	Lignosulfonates	23.81 kg
Output	Technosphere	Energy	Steam (avoided)	380 kWh
Output	Technosphere	Waste to treatment	Ashes (to landfill)	7.24 kg
Output	Technosphere	Waste to treatment	Green liquor dregs (to landfill)	8.30 kg
Output	Technosphere	Waste to treatment	MSW (to landfill)	0.355 kg
Output	Technosphere	Waste to treatment	Scrap (to landfill)	1.55 kg
Output	Technosphere	Waste to treatment	Sludge (to land farming)	60.00 kg
Output	Technosphere	Waste to product	CO ₂ (to carbonic acid)	28.57 kg
Output	Environment	Emissions to air ^d	CO ₂ fossil	100.14 kg
Output	Environment	Emissions to air ^d	CO ₂ biogenic	2.69 ton
Output	Environment	Emissions to air ^d	NO _x	2.29 kg
Output	Environment	Emissions to air ^d	TRS	1.34 kg
Output	Environment	Emissions to air ^d	Particulates	1.09 kg
Output	Environment	Emissions to water ^e	COD	41.87 kg
Output	Environment	Emissions to water ^e	BOD ₅	9.48 kg
Output	Environment	Emissions to water ^e	N	1.01 kg
Output	Environment	Emissions to water ^e	P	0.020 kg
Output	Environment	Emissions to water ^e	TSS	4.08 kg

Note: m³ = cubic meters; H₂O₂ = hydrogen peroxide; kg = kilograms; NaOH = sodium hydroxide; H₂SO₃ = sulfurous acid; EDTA = ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid; kWh = kilowatt hour; t km = tonnes per kilometer; MSW = municipal solid waste; CO₂ = carbon dioxide; NO_x = nitrogen oxides; TRS = total reduced sulfur; COD = chemical oxygen demand; BOD₅ = biochemical oxygen demand; N = nitrogen; P = phosphorus; TSS = total suspended solids.

^aFrom those, only 956 kWh are taken from the grid, and the remaining comes from cogeneration units.

^bFrom recovery boilers.

^cTen percent moisture and air dried (AD).

^dDirect emissions from the recovery boilers stage.

^eDirect emissions from the wastewater treatment plant (WWTP).

1) Summary table

See example on page 3

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹¹	Souza, Alexandre., Watanabe, Marcos Djun Barbosa, Cavalett, Otavio, Ugaya, Cassia Maria Lie, and Bonomi, Antonio, « Social life cycle assessment of first and second-generation ethanol production technologies in Brazil », The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment, (in press), doi: 10.1007/s11367-016-1112-y
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	sugar cane
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	ethanol
Functional unit	change in ethanol final demand of R\$ 1 billion
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	economic
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	n/a
Geographic location, if defined	Brazil
Data quality	Data from model in the Virtual Sugarcane Biorefinery, process-based inventory of evaluated scenarios
Impact assessment method	UNEP/SETAC SLCA guidelines
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	job creation, occupational accidents, wage profile, education profile, gender profile

¹¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Fig. 1. Systems boundaries

Fig. 2. Inventory compilation based on process and input-output approaches

Table 1 Main characteristics of the vertically integrated production scenarios considered in this study

Scenario	Sugarcane planting system	Sugarcane harvesting system	Straw recovery	Outputs	Context
1G-basic	Semi-mechanized	Manual, with pre-harvesting burning	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> First-generation ethanol 	Represents current sugarcane production with relatively outdated technologies ^a
1G-optimized	Mechanized	Mechanized, without pre-harvesting burning	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> First-generation ethanol Electricity 	Represents a modern current technology
1G2G	Mechanized	Mechanized, without pre-harvesting burning	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> First- and second-generation ethanol Electricity 	Represents future technology

^a Sugarcane pre-harvesting burning still takes place either in some regions of Brazil such as the Brazilian Northeast region or areas where harvester operation is limited due to high slope (above 12 %). In center-south region, mechanized harvesting represents more than 88 % of the total harvested area (Nunes Junior 2014)

Table 2 Stakeholder categories, subcategories, and inventory indicators considered in this study

Stakeholder categories	Subcategories	Inventory indicators	Inventory data	Data source
Local community	Local employment	Number of jobs	Manual and mechanized necessary working hours	Modeled using the VSB (Bonomi et al. 2012)
	Access to material resources/ access to immaterial resources/delocalization and migration/cultural heritage/ safe and healthy living conditions/respect of indigenous rights/community engagement/secure living conditions	–	–	–
Workers	Health and safety	Number of occupational accidents	Incidence of occupational accidents per thousand workers of each Brazilian economic sector	MPS (2015)
	Fair salary	Average wages	Costs of the agricultural and industrial working hours	Modeled using the VSB (Bonomi et al. 2012)
		Wage value profile	Wage profile of each Brazilian economic sector	MTE (2015)
	Equal opportunities/ discrimination	Woman in the labor force participation rate	Woman participation in each Brazilian economic sector	MTE (2015)
Education degree profile ^a		Education profile of each Brazilian economy sector	MTE (2015)	
	Freedom of association and collective bargain/child labor/working hours/forced labor/social benefits/social security	–	–	–
Consumer	Health and safety/feedback mechanism/consumer privacy/transparency/end of life responsibility	–	–	–
Society	Public commitments to sustainability issues/ contribution to economic development/preventions and mitigation of armed conflicts/technology development/corruption	–	–	–
Value chain actors	Fair competition/promoting social responsibility/supplier relationships/respect of intellectual property rights	–	–	–

^a Education profile is not a default inventory indicator in UNEP/SETAC (2009) guidelines. It was included in this study considering the high education inequality in Brazilian work force and data availability on the education of workers in Brazilian economic sectors

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹²	Krzyżaniak, Michał, Stolarski, Mariusz Jerzy., Szczukowski, Stefan, and Tworkowski, Józef, “Life Cycle Assessment of New Willow Cultivars Grown as Feedstock for Integrated Biorefineries”, <i>Bioenergy Research</i> , Vol. 9, No. 1, pp. 224-238. doi: 10.1007/s12155-015-9681-3
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	short rotation coppice willow
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	
Functional unit	1 tonne of dry biomass
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	n/a
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	
Geographic location, if defined	Europe – Poland
Data quality	Primary and secondary data
Impact assessment method	CML 2 baseline 2000
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Abiotic depletion, Acidification, Eutrophication, Global warming (GWP 100), Freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity, Terrestrial ecotoxicity
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

¹² The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Fig. System boundary

Table 2 The inputs for setting up and running 1 ha of a plantation of willow and its re-establishment

Specification	Materials (kg)	Tractor	Machinery	Power (max/used) (kW)	Operating time (h)	Diesel (kg)	Source
Chemical weeding (1) Herbicide spraying (glyphosate)	1.44	New Holland TM 130 HP	Krukowiak sprayer, working width 18 m	95.6/47.8	0.2	2.04	OR
Disking (2x)	-	New Holland TM 130 HP	Kvermeland disk harrow, working width 4 m	95.6/60.2	1.4	17.96	OR
Winter ploughing	-	New Holland TM 175 HP	Kvermeland PG 100 plough, working width 2 m	128.6/90.0	1.5	29.30	OR
Fertilisation (fertilisers PRP sol)	300	New Holland TM 130 HP	Rauch 3.0 Mg spreader, working width 18 m	95.6/47.8	0.4	4.07	OR
Harrowing (2x)	-	New Holland TM 130 HP	Harrow, working width 6 m	95.6/52.6	1.0	11.20	OR
Planting	337.5	New Holland TM 130 HP	4-row step planter	95.6/62.1	1.3	17.21	OR
Chemical weeding (2) Herbicide spraying (acetochlor)	1.58	New Holland TM 130 HP	Krukowiak sprayer, working width 18 m	95.6/47.8	0.2	2.04	OR
Mechanical weeding (2x)	-	New Holland TM 130 HP	Mechanical weeder P 430/2, working width 3 m	66.0/33.0	2.0	14.06	OR, [36]
Chemical weeding (3) Herbicide spraying (quizalofop-P-ethyl) (2x)	0.13	New Holland TM 130 HP	Krukowiak sprayer, working width 18 m	95.6/47.8	0.2	2.04	OR
Fertilization:		New Holland TM 130 HP	Rauch 3.0 Mg spreader, working width 18 m	95.6/47.8			
ammonium nitrate (7x)	90				0.65	6.62	OR
triple superphosphate+ potassium chloride (7x)	30+60				0.65	6.62	
Plantation re-establishment	-	New Holland TM 175 HP	Rototiller FV 4088, working width 40 cm	128.6/90.0	6.0	117.21	OR, estimation

OR own research

Table 3 Inputs for harvest, loading and transport of willow chips per 1 ha per one 3-year harvest cycle

Cultivar	Specification	Tractor/harvester power (kW max/used)	Machinery	Operating time (h)	Diesel (kg)	Source
Start	Single stage harvest	Claas Jaguar 830 (236/212.4)	–	2.1	105.1	OR
	Field transport	New Holland TM 130 HP (95.6/47.8)	T 169/2 tractor trailer, loading capacity: 4 Mg of chips	6.2	63.0	OR
	Loading	Manitou Scopic MLT 735 (90.5/45.3)	–	0.82	4.55	OR, Estimation
	Road transport (25, 50, 100 km)	–	Lorry with 80 m ³ trailer	–	(7389, 14777, 29554 tkm) ^a	EcoInvent
Tur	Single stage harvest	Claas Jaguar 830 (236/212.4)	–	1.0	53.3	OR
	Field transport	New Holland TM 130 HP (95.6/47.8)	T 169/2 tractor trailer, loading capacity: 4 Mg of chips	3.1	31.9	OR
	Loading	Manitou Scopic MLT 735 (90.5/45.3)	–	0.42	2.31	OR, Estimation
	Road transport (25, 50, 100 km)	–	Lorry with 80 m ³ trailer	–	(3836, 7672, 15344 tkm) ^a	EcoInvent
Turbo	Single stage harvest	Claas Jaguar 830 (236/212.4)	–	2.1	108.7	OR
	Field transport	New Holland TM 130 HP (95.6/47.8)	T 169/2 tractor trailer, loading capacity: 4 Mg of chips	6.4	65.1	OR
	Loading	Manitou Scopic MLT 735 (90.5/45.3)	–	0.85	4.71	OR, estimation
	Road transport (25, 50, 100 km)	–	Lorry with 80 m ³ trailer	–	(7638, 15278, 30555 tkm) ^a	EcoInvent
UWM 006	Single stage harvest	Claas Jaguar 830 (236/212.4)	–	4.3	220.1	OR
	Field transport	New Holland TM 130 HP (95.6/47.8)	T 169/2 tractor trailer, loading capacity: 4 Mg of chips	13.0	131.9	OR
	Loading	Manitou Scopic MLT 735 (90.5/45.3)	–	1.73	9.54	OR, estimation
	Road transport (25, 50, 100 km)	–	Lorry with 80 m ³ trailer	–	(15290, 30580, 61159 tkm) ^a	EcoInvent
UWM 035	Single stage harvest	Claas Jaguar 830 (236/212.4)	–	1.5	76.4	OR
	Field transport	New Holland TM 130 HP (95.6/47.8)	T 169/2 tractor trailer, loading capacity: 4 Mg of chips	4.5	45.8	OR
	Loading	Manitou Scopic MLT 735 (90.5/45.3)	–	0.60	3.31	OR
	Road transport (25, 50, 100 km)	–	Lorry with 80 m ³ trailer	–	(5418, 10826, 21672 tkm) ^a	EcoInvent
UWM 043	Single stage harvest	Claas Jaguar 830 (236/212.4)	–	3.5	179.0	OR
	Field transport	New Holland TM 130 HP (95.6/47.8)	T 169/2 tractor trailer, loading capacity: 4 Mg of chips	10.5	107.2	OR
	Loading	Manitou Scopic MLT 735 (90.5/45.3)	–	1.40	7.76	OR, estimation
	Road transport (25, 50, 100 km)	–	Lorry with 80 m ³ trailer	–	(12462, 24924, 49847 tkm) ^a	EcoInvent
UWM 155	Single stage harvest	Claas Jaguar 830 (236/212.4)	–	0.9	45.5	OR
	Field transport	New Holland TM 130 HP (95.6/47.8)	T 169/2 tractor trailer, loading capacity: 4 Mg of chips	2.7	27.3	OR
	Loading	Manitou Scopic MLT 735 (90.5/45.3)	–	0.36	1.97	OR, estimation
	Road transport (25, 50, 100 km)	–	Lorry with 80 m ³ trailer	–	(3302, 6604, 13209 tkm) ^a	EcoInvent
Average	Single stage harvest	Claas Jaguar 830 (236/212.4)	–	2.2	112.6	OR
	Field transport	New Holland TM 130 HP (95.6/47.8)	T 169/2 tractor trailer, loading capacity: 4 Mg of chips	6.6	67.5	OR
	Loading	Manitou Scopic MLT 735 (90.5/45.3)	–	0.88	4.88	OR, estimation
	Road transport (25, 50, 100 km)	–	Lorry with 80 m ³ trailer	–	(3836, 7672, 15344 tkm) ^a	EcoInvent

OR own research

^a units for biomass transport: tonne-kilometre

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹³	Groot, Wim J., and Borén, Tobias, "Life cycle assessment of the manufacture of lactide and PLA biopolymers from sugarcane in Thailand", The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment, Vol. 15, No. 9, 2010, pp. 970-984.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	sugar cane
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	L-lactide, D-lactide, PLLA, and two PLLA/PDLA blends
Functional unit	1 tonne of material at the factory gat
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Bioplastics
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	System expansion for the electricity co-product in the sugar mill process. For all other valuable by-products, economic was used.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	
Geographic location, if defined	Thailand
Data quality	secondary data mostly regarding
Impact assessment method	
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

¹³ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the production chain from agriculture to PLA

Lactic acid, lactide, and PLA plant description

– The steam is produced from natural gas (Dones et al. 2007). Data on green house gases (GHG) emission from steam production form various energy sources

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹⁴	Cosate de Andrade, Marina F., Souza, Patricia M.F., Cavalett, Otavio, and Morales, Ana R. "Life Cycle Assessment of Poly(Lactic Acid) (PLA): Comparison Between Chemical Recycling, Mechanical Recycling and Composting", Journal of Polymers and the Environment, Vol. 24, No. 4, 2016, pp. 372-384
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Poly(Lactic Acid) waste
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	
Functional unit	1 kg of residual PLA
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	bioplastic recycling and composting
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	n/a
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	n/a
Geographic location, if defined	Brasil
Data quality	data based on lab scale experiments, secondary data from industry and literature
Impact assessment method	Recipe, Cumulative, Energy Demand (CED)
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Climate change, human toxicity and fossil depletion
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

¹⁴ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Fig. 1. PLA life cycle. Dashed line indicate the product system under study

Fig. 2. PLA mechanical recycling

Table 1 Mechanical recycling inventory

Product	Amount	Unit	Reference	Comments
Recycled PLA	0.96	kg	Based on industry data	
<i>Energy use</i>				
Electricity mix, Brazil, 2013/BR U	2649	kJ	Based on lab scale experiments and industry data	
<i>Input</i>				
Water, process and cooling, unspecified natural origin	0.169	kg	Based on lab scale experiments and industry data	Replacement of the evaporated water
Lime, hydrated, loose, at plant/CH U	0.0017	kg	Garraín et al. [23]	Water treatment
Aluminum sulfate, powder, at plant/RER U	0.00205	kg	Adapted from Garraín et al. [23]	Water treatment
Chemicals organic, at plant/GLO U (chain extender)	6.04	g	Based on lab scale experiments	Extrusion process
Chromium steel product manufacturing, average metal working/RER U	12.00	mg	Based on lab scale experiments	Recycling equipment
Steel product manufacturing, average metal working/RER U	5.59	mg	Based on lab scale experiments	Recycling equipment
Transport, municipal waste collection, lorry 21t/CH U	0.026	ton km	Perugini et al. [24]	Collection of residual PLA and transportation to the recycling plant
<i>Emissions</i>				
Packaging waste, plastic (residual PLA)	0.04	kg	Based on industry data	Send to landfill
Heat, waste	286.6	kJ	Based on lab scale experiments	

Reference flow of 1 kg of residual PLA

Fig. 3. Hydrolysis step in PLA chemical recycling

Table 2 Chemical recycling inventory

Product	Amount	Unit	Reference	Comment
Recycled PLA	0.97	kg	Based on lab scale experiments and Martinez, 2011 [25]	
<i>Energy use</i>				
Electricity mix, Brazil, 2013/BR U	11,211	kJ	Based on lab scale experiments and Martinez [25]	
<i>Input</i>				
Water, process and cooling, unspecified natural origin	0.0485	kg	Based on lab scale experiments	To replace evaporated water
Lime, hydrated, loose, at plant/CH U	0.0017	kg	Garraín et al. [23]	Water treatment
Aluminum sulfate, powder, at plant/RER U	0.0021	kg	Adapted from Garraín et al. [23]	Water treatment
Aluminum sulfate, powder, at plant/RER U (Water for reaction)	1.50	kg	Based on lab scale experiments	Amount of water used in hydrolysis reaction
Chemicals inorganic, at plant/GLO U	0.282	g	Based on lab scale experiments	Considered as chemicals inorganic
Chromium steel product manufacturing, average metal working/RER U	0.980	g	Based on lab scale experiments and Martinez [25]	Recycling equipment
Steel product manufacturing, average metal working/RER U	0.040	g	Based on lab scale experiments and Martinez [25]	Recycling equipment
Chemicals organic, at plant/GLO U (Tin ethanoate)	0.628	g	Based on Martinez [25]	Catalyst used in polymerization process
Transport, municipal waste collection, lorry 21t/CH U	0.026	ton km	Perugini et al. [24]	Collection of residual PLA and transportation to the recycling plant
<i>Emissions</i>				
Packaging waste, plastic (unreacted PLA)	0.01	kg	Based on lab scale experiments	
Water, process and cooling, unspecified natural origin	1.51	kg	Based on Martinez [25]	Water removed on polymerization process
Waste, inorganic	1.35	g	Based on lab scale experiments	
Heat, waste	7638	kJ	Based on lab scale experiments and Martinez [25]	
Chemicals organic, at plant/GLO U (Tin ethanoate)	0.628	g	Based on Martinez [25]	Catalyst removed of polymerization process

Reference flow of 1 kg of residual PLA

Fig. 4 Polymerization step in PLA chemical recycling

Fig. 5 PLA composting phases

Table 3 Composting inventory

Product	Amount	Unit	Reference	Comment
Compost, at plant/CH U	0.33	kg	Souza et al. [33]	
<i>Energy use</i>				
Electricity mix, Brazil, 2013/BR U	39.7	kJ	Based on literature data	
<i>Input</i>				
Occupation, dump site	0.117	m ²	[34]	Area for windrows
Steel product manufacturing, average metal working/RER U	21.4	mg	Based on literature data	Recycling equipment
Transport, municipal waste collection, lorry 21t/CH U	0.026	ton km	Perugini et al. [24]	Collection of residual PLA and transportation to the recycling plant
<i>Emissions</i>				
Carbon dioxide, biogenic (CO ₂ production)	1.2	kg	Souza et al. [33]	

Reference flow of 1 kg of residual PLA

Fig. 6. Product system for PLA end-of-life using a restitution product system approach

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹⁵	Suwanmanee, Unchalee, Varabuntoonvit, Viganda, Chaiwutthinan, Phasawat, Tajan, Monchai, Mungcharoen Thumrongrut, and Thanawadee Leejarkpai, "Life cycle assessment of single use thermoform boxes made from polystyrene (PS), polylactic acid, (PLA), and PLA/starch: cradle to consumer gate", The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment, Vol. 18, No. 2, 2013, pp. 401-417
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	corn
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	
Functional unit	10,000 units of 8.0 × 10.0 × 2.5 cm of PS, PLA, and PLA/starch boxes which weigh 447.60, 597.60, and 549.56 kg, respectively
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	n/a
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	direct and indirect LUC based on the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (2006). This paper considered LUC emissions with the assumption from land converted to cropland. Average value of 328.00 t of CO ₂ equivalent per hectare of land converted to corn (Piemonte and Gironi 2011). The emission calculation for cropland change from corn to cassava is zero (Joint Graduate School of Energy and Environment 2010)
Geographic location, if defined	Thailand
Data quality	Secondary data for agricultural production, for transformation steps : primary and secondary data are used
Impact assessment method	The Environmental Design of Industrial Product 2003 method
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	global warming potential, acidification, photochemical ozone,

¹⁵ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Yelin Deng, Yajun Tian, Assessing the Environmental Impact of Flax Fibre Reinforced Polymer Composite from a Consequential Life Cycle Assessment Perspective; Sustainability, 2015, Vol. 7, pp. 11462-11483
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Flax
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Flax fibre, flax mat
Functional unit	Flax mat reinforced polypropylene composite vs. glass mat PP. Equivalent mass 7,8kg vs 9kg
Product family (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Plant fibre based composite for automotive application to replace glass mat-PP.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Co-products are treated via economic allocation (see also Weidema, B. Avoiding co-product allocation in life-cycle assessment. J. Ind. Ecol. 2000, 4, 11–33).
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	The study follows the methodology from Milà i Canals et al. (2012) ² which says that for products experiencing a decline in cultivation areas, no LUC needs to be considered. Since flax cultivation areas have been shrinking over the past few years, the LUC factor is omitted.
Geographic location, if defined	China and France for the production phase, Europe for the use phase and for EoL.
Data quality	The calculation for marginal values are based on literature and secondary data
Impact assessment method	See impact categories below. Assessment implemented in Simapro® software version 7.2.4.
Damage categories (endpoint)	/
Impact categories (midpoint)	The evaluated impact categories are based on ReCiPe method (ReCiPe Midpoint (H)). Climate change, Ozone depletion, Human toxicity, photochemical oxidant

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

² Milà i Canals, L.; Rigarlford, G.; Sim, S. Land use impact assessment of margarine. *Int. J. LCA* **2013**, *18*, 1265–1277.

	formation, particulate matter, Ionising radiation, Soil acidification, Freshwater eutrophication, marine eutrophication, Terrestrial ecotoxicity, marine ecotoxicity, freshwater ecotoxicity, agricultural land occupation, urban land occupation, water depletion, metal depletion, fossil depletion
Other information or comments	A marginal demand for flax mat in composite reinforcement induces a global marginal supply mix of flax fibres from China and France that propagates to Indian jute fibre and Canadian linseed cultivation by system expansion. These were not included in the model for practical reasons. Also, the CLCA (and notably the 'consequential supply mix scenario which is the baseline scenario) rests upon market assumptions described in p. 11468

2) Short report

This consequential LCA focuses on the marginal environmental impact changes if additional bio-based sources are used in the European industry thanks to a shift from glass fibres to flax fibres for composite reinforcement for European automotive application.

It considers the production, use and end-of life phases. In terms of geographical scope and focuses on two big producers of flax worldwide: China and France.

The authors first develop a baseline flax scenario (flax produced in China: 70% / in France: 30%) and compare it to a glass fibre scenario. The authors then develop three alternative scenarios to the baseline flax consequential LCA scenario:

- All French scenario (100% produced in France, use and EoL in Europe)
- All Chinese scenario (100% produced in China, use and EoL in Europe)
- 'Attributional' supply scenario (60% produced in France, 40% produced in China, use and EoL in Europe).

The results of the CLCAs are the following:

Compared to the glass mat-PP, the flax mat-PP has 0.8–2 times higher environmental impact values in most environmental impact categories over the production and EoL phases (and only presents better results in the following impact categories: photochemical oxidant formation, ionising radiation and water depletion).

As to the other flax scenarios, the all French flax fibre and all Chinese flax fibre supplies can be regarded as the lower and upper boundaries for all potential marginal flax supply trajectories; the attributional supply mix lays in between.

The all French flax fibre supply results in lower impact results than the glass mat-PP in all categories, except for the freshwater ecotoxicity and agricultural land occupation categories.

On the contrary, the all Chinese supply scenario presents environmental burdens well above the levels of the glass mat-PP.

The attributional supply mix scenario (60% French, 40% Chinese) can be regarded as a break-even line for the relative shares between the Chinese flax fibre and French flax fibre in terms of comparing environmental impacts.

The big differences between the Chinese and French scenarios can be explained mainly by:

- (1) the much lower flax fibre yield efficiencies in China compared to France.
- (2) China's electricity mix depending heavily on coal (negative impacts in terms of CO₂ emissions, but also in terms of terrestrial acidification and particulate matter formation).

Table 4. Consequential mix of the global flax fibre supply (retrieved from FAOSTAT [15]).

Supply Mix	Position	Application Criteria	Share (Chinese/French)
Consequential supply mix	Baseline	Four assumptions are met	70%/30%
Attributional supply mix		Overall market becomes stabilized.	40%/60%
All French fibre supply mix	Alternative	External policies promoting uses of French fibre in automotive	0%/100%
All Chinese fibre supply mix		Substantial subsidy is provided to Chinese flax cultivators	100%/0%

Table 6. Impact changes induced by flax mat-PP replacing glass mat-PP.

	Unit	Production	Use	End-of-life (EoL)	Total
Climate change	kg CO ₂ eq	23.8	-22.5	-1.6	-0.4
Ozone depletion	mg CFC-11 eq	0.7	-3.1	-0.3	-2.7
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	4.7	-0.9	-1.0	2.8
Photochemical oxidant formation	g NMVOC	95.2	-109.4	-4.5	-18.7
Particulate matter formation	g PM ₁₀ eq	214.2	-22.6	-2.2	189.5
Ionising radiation	g U ₂₃₅ eq	-177.7	-508.7	-1053.2	-1739.6
Terrestrial acidification	g SO ₂ eq	299.3	-65.6	-6.8	226.8
Freshwater eutrophication	g P eq	22.4	-0.6	-1.4	20.3
Marine eutrophication	g N eq	121.0	-2.7	-0.4	117.9
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	g 1,4-DB eq	3.4	-3.2	-0.2	0.1
Freshwater ecotoxicity	g 1,4-DB eq	366.6	-20.3	-20.2	326.2
Marine ecotoxicity	g 1,4-DB eq	121.1	-33.5	-20.6	67.1
Agricultural land occupation	m ² a	72.3	0.0	0.0	72.2
Urban land occupation	m ² a	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.2
Water depletion	litre	-3428.4	-27.4	-11.1	-3466.9
Metal depletion	g Fe eq	786.0	-102.8	-64.2	619.0
Fossil depletion	kg oil eq	5.1	-7.7	-1.0	-3.6

Figure 6. Environmental impact comparison for flax mat-PP with different scenarios of marginal flax fibre supply over production and EoL phases.

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Poopak, Sotoodehnia, and Amiri Roodan, “Environmental Benefit of Using Bagasse in Paper Production - A Case Study of LCA in Iran,” Global Warming - Impacts and Future Perspectives, 2012.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis (Although title explicitly referred to LCA, the study is more an input-output analysis) <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Bagasse (by product): fibrous material that remains after the juice of sugar cane has been extracted.
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Bagasse fibre (65-68%) used for pulp and paper production, by-products: pith (25-30%), sugar (2%), minerals (1-2%).
Functional unit	Production of one metric tonne of paper
Product family (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) (see feedstock) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Paper products
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	N/A. separate assessment for each input and factor.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Referred to only as a starting point: paper produced using by-product natural fibres (such as bagasse) is good from a land-use change perspective as it minimizes the impact of deforestation.
Geographic location, if defined	Pars Paper Factory, Iran
Data quality	Primary data is used to evaluate process input and secondary data are used for the impact assessment
Impact assessment method	CML 2000 Baseline, assessment carried out using Simapro 7.0 database.
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Abiotic Depletion ; Acidification ; Eutrophication ; Global Warming Potential ;
Other information or comments	Comment from ECOS: interesting case study, could be more meticulous in certain aspects (e.g. no explanation as to why focussing on this factory in particular, no

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

2) Short report

Paper can be produced out of virgin material, such as wood, or out of non-virgin material such as kanaf or bagasse. This study is an input-output analysis examining the environmental impacts of the paper production from bagasse in an Iranian factory, compared to those of paper production from wood. The Pars Paper Factory is a government owned factory whose input material – bagasse – is provided by sugarcane factories located nearby, using water for this process is provided from not far away the Dez River and uses hydroelectricity and mazut as energy.

The system boundary is limited to paper production, encompassing three stages: preparation of the non-virgin materials, pulp mill and paper mill process.

The most important finding is that bagasse use provides a negative GWP and thus a better option with respect to virgin wooden materials. Bagasse shows little environmental impact in all the categories, but photochemical ozone oxidation. Environmental performances for paper production could be further improved by replacing mazut as a fuel and using a sustainable substitute of chlorine as a bleaching agent.

Figure 16. Impacts of paper production process from all inputs

Key: Farmed tree 1: Bagasse Farmed tree 2: Kraft

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Arrigoni, Alessandro, Renato Pelosato, Paco Melià, Gianluca Ruggieri, Sergio Sabbadini, and Giovanni Dotelli, “Life cycle assessment of natural building materials: the role of carbonation, mixture components and transport in the environmental impacts of hempcrete blocks,” <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> Vol. 149, 2017, pp. 1051–1061.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Hemp
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Hemp fibres. Co-products are: water, binding agent (hydrated lime, natural hydraulic lime or both) and mortar
Functional unit	one square meter of non-load-bearing wall made of hempcrete blocks
Product family (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Used, as finishing plasters in non-bearing walls and floor/roof insulators.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Mass allocation (mass outputs considered were: 75% shives, 20% fibres and 5% dust) for all cases except case H (see summary)
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Not included (proposal in the conclusion to include them in future research to have a more accurate GHG calculation).
Geographic location, if defined	North of Italy
Data quality	Primary data for production process data and transportation ; secondary for the mixture of components (hemp shives and binders)
Impact assessment method	CEN, 2012. EN 15804:2012 Sustainability of Construction Works and Environmental Product Declarations - Core Rules for the Product Category of Construction Products. CML-IA Baseline characterisation factors

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Damage categories (endpoint)	/
Impact categories (midpoint)	Abiotic depletion (ADP), fossil fuels depletion (ADP fossil), global warming over a time interval of 100 y (GWP), ozone depletion (ODP), acidification (AP), eutrophication (EP), photochemical ozone creation (POCP)
Other information or comments	Construction sector very regulated and codified. Analysis performed according to EN 15804:2012, sustainability in construction works – Environmental product declarations, Cor rules for the product category of construction products

2) Short report

Hempcrete is a natural building material that has known an increased popularity in Europe recently. Hempcrete-based construction materials are used as finishing plasters and floor/roof insulators. This study assessed the environmental performances of a non-load-bearing wall made of hempcrete blocks and makes variation in its model (e.g. production distance, binder type) to spot how the overall environmental performance could be improved. EoL is not included in this LCA due to the lack of reliable data.

Results:

The production phase of the raw materials is reported as the main source of environmental impacts. The transportation of raw materials, and the composition of the binder mixture can however considerably affect the results (see table).

The main asset of this natural building material is its overall emission balance: thanks to biogenic CO₂ uptake during hemp growth and to CO₂ uptake by carbonation, hempcrete blocks have a negative carbon footprint. An experimental assessment (via X-ray Powder Diffraction analysis) of the carbonation process taking place within the binder during the use phase of the wall shows that the carbonation rate may however be smaller than assumed in previous works: after 240 d, only the outermost layers of the blocks show significant levels of carbonation, while the innermost layers experienced only a negligible increase in carbonates.

Table 2

Greenhouse gas emissions and CO₂ uptake of 1 m² of wall made of hempcrete blocks calculated using the Greenhouse Gas Protocol method (see section 3.1.2 for the description of unit processes). As for the CO₂ uptake, the value reported for the use phase refers to 240 d since the block production, while the value indicated between parentheses refers to the completion of the carbonation process.

Impact category	Unit	1. Hemp shives production	2. Binder production	4. Block production	3+5. Transport	6. Wall construction	7. Use phase	1-7. Total
Fossil	kg CO ₂ eq	1.75	35.40	1.02	6.52	3.32	–	48.02
Biogenic	kg CO ₂ eq	0.01	0.18	0.03	0.01	0.10	–	0.34
Land use	kg CO ₂ eq	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	–	0.00
Uptake	kg CO ₂ eq	58.0	0.04	0.04	0.01	1.51	0.53 (14.45)	59.60

Table 4

Results per FU relative to the seven impact categories recommended by EN 15804; for completeness, CO₂ uptake, including both biogenic uptake and the amount from full binder carbonation, is listed separately.

Impact category	Unit	A	B	C	D1	D2	E	F	G	H
ADP	mg Sb eq	1.75	1.61	15,101.48	1.75	36,321.24	1.74	1.78	1.73	1.73
ADP fossil	MJ	358.73	359.44	348.08	401.90	389.78	332.52	396.19	337.03	343.82
GWP	kg CO ₂ eq	48.04	47.88	45.88	50.87	49.08	46.33	58.41	42.03	47.70
CO ₂ uptake	kg CO ₂ eq	74.04	73.29	80.08	74.04	82.36	74.03	68.61	77.19	74.04
ODP	mg CFC-11 eq	3.93	4.09	3.97	4.46	4.70	3.61	4.42	3.65	3.80
POCP	g C ₂ H ₄ eq	6.84	7.48	6.63	7.20	7.53	6.62	8.18	6.06	6.73
AP	g SO ₂ eq	81.33	74.28	79.82	90.79	143.02	75.35	91.80	75.26	78.74
EP	g PO ₄ ³⁻ eq	15.82	13.12	14.43	17.66	13.94	14.65	17.36	14.94	15.13

Key

- Impact indicators: abiotic depletion (ADP), fossil fuels depletion (ADP fossil), global warming over a time interval of 100 y (GWP), ozone depletion (ODP), acidification (AP), eutrophication (EP), photochemical ozone creation (POCP)

- Cases: Case A: base binder; Case B: binder pure dolomitic lime; Case C: binder mix of hydrated lime, hydraulic lime and pozzolan; Case D1: hemp produced in France (transport distance:750 km), production emissions equal to those of Italian producer; Case D2: same but production emissions considered were those reported by Boutin et al² for an average French producer (lower); Case E: Transport of the binder: only 40 (baseline 100km), Case F: heavier mixture with a binder-to-hemp mass ratio 2:1; Case G: lighter mixture with a binder-to-hemp mass ratio 1:1, economic allocation, with factors based on average prices for shives, fibres and dust considered in a previous work³: 0.25, 0.60 and 0.00 V/kg, respectively.

² Boutin et al, 2006. Study on the Environmental Characteristics of Hemp through the Analysis of its Life Cycle (in French). Ministry of Agriculture, Agrifood, and Forestry, Paris, France

³ Zampori, L., Dotelli, G., Vernelli, V., 2013. Life cycle assessment of hemp cultivation and use of hemp-based thermal insulator materials in buildings. Environ. Sci. Technol. 47, 7413e7420.

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Murphy, Richard J, and Andrew Norton, “Life Cycle Assessments of Natural Fibre Insulation Materials” Published by National Non-Food Crops Centre, February 2008. http://nova-institut.de/news-images/20080306-05/lca_fibre.pdf
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	2 Natural Fibre Insulation (NFI) materials assessed in this study: Isonat®, made from hemp and cotton and Thermafleecce®, made from sheep wool.
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Isonat: Final blend is 35% hemp fibre, 35% recovered waste cotton fibre, 15% bi-component polyester fibre and 15% flame retardants; Thermafleecce: greasy wool (waste product of wool production): 70% of wool worth less than £1 per kg, rest is almost only lanolin, treatment with disodium octaborate tetrahydrate to protect it from fire and insects and 20% moisture content.
Functional unit	1m2 of insulation material
Product family (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fibres (from plants as well as animal, depending on insulation material) <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Isonat®, Thermafleecce® insulation materials
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry (+ farming) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential (both, first, attributional analysis, then marginal LCA).
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Mass allocation basis except when specified (following recommendations of ISO 14041).
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Not included. The paper demonstrates, however, how hemp is not a land intensive crop and the surface needed for meeting internal demand, would not create displacement effects for other commodities.
Geographic location, if defined	United Kingdom, East Anglia for hemp harvesting. France for the wool recovery and finished product transformation.
Data quality	Primary data regarding the NFI products studied were obtained through consultation with manufacturers.

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

	Secondary data were obtained from databases. The BUWAL 250 database was used for transport and disposal processes and Ecoinvent data was used for all other processes and materials. A separate independent dataset was used for a potential PLA based binder.
Impact assessment method	CML Impact assessment method for LCA
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Abiotic depletion potential (kg antimony eq), global warming potential, 100year time-frame (kg CO ₂ eq), ozone layer depletion potential (kg CFC-11 eq), human toxicity potential (kg 1.4-dichlorobenzene eq), freshwater ecotoxicity potential (kg 1.4-dichlorobenzene eq), terrestrial ecotoxicity potential (kg 1.4-dichlorobenzene eq), photochemical oxidant creation potential (kg ethylene eq), acidification potential (kg SO ₂ eq), eutrophication potential (kg PO ₄ eq).
Other information or comments	This study compares the environmental performances of several insulation materials

2) Short report

This study looks at natural fibre insulation (NFI) and compares the environmental performances of the following insulation materials (2 NFIs, 2 conventional insulation products). These products were chosen based on their availability on the UK market.

	Natural Fibre Insulation (NFI) Materials		Conventional Insulation Materials	
Material	Sheep wool	Hemp and Cotton	Mineral wool	Glass fibre
Product name	Thermafleece	Isonat	Rockwool Rollbatt	Crown Loft Roll 44
Production Address	Mirfield, Bradford	Cours la Ville, nr. Lyon, France	PenCoed, Bridgend, Wales	Cwmbran, Torfaen, Wales

Results:

In general terms, Figure 13 (below) shows that the impact of Isonat tends to be greater than that of Thermafleece in most impact categories. This is a result of the greater density of Isonat, its longer transportation chain (feedstock growing in the UK, produced or isonat material in France, then shipped back to the UK for its installation) and its fire-retardant treatment process. Interestingly, Thermafleece offers a net negative GWP₁₀₀ profile at the installation stage of the life cycle, meaning that up to the point of its installation and use, its material composition sequesters more CO₂ eq than has been released by the energy and materials consumed in its processing and transportation.

The main factors limiting the environmental performance of the current NFIs are inefficiencies in manufacture (consumption of fossil energy sources) and use of additives i.e. the flame retardants and polyester-based binders.

The study makes a whole set of recommendation to enhance the environmental performance, see p. 75.

Generalised results

The results on a *cradle to installation* basis for the two NFI products (together with those for the glass and mineral wool materials studied basis are presented in Figure 13 using the CML impact assessment method.

Figure 13 Environmental impact for NFI products and conventional insulation materials (CML baseline)

Table 7 Table of CML baseline impacts by described units for the Thermaflocc product

Impact category	Abiotic depletion	Global warming (GWP100)	Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	Human toxicity	Fresh water aquatic ecotox.	Terrestrial ecotoxicity	photochemical oxidation	acidification	eutrophication
Unit	kg Sb eq	kg CO ₂ eq	kg CFC-11 eq	kg 1,4-DB eq	kg 1,4-DB eq	kg 1,4-DB eq	kg C ₂ H ₂ eq	kg SO ₂ eq	kg PO ₄ ---
Total	0.00451	-0.323	1.48E-07	0.453	0.1	0.00584	0.000296	0.00835	0.00116
Clean, Raw Wool	0.0017	-1.53	0	0.106	0.0332	0.00107	0	0.00141	0.000145
Packaging film	0	0.0681	0	0.0106	0.00294	0.000398	0	0.000666	0
Bi-component Polyester	0.00065	0.455	0	0.182	0.0312	0.00283	0.000124	0.00325	0.000595
Heat gas	0.00182	0.205	0	0.0221	0.000173	0.00019	0.000011	0.000229	0
Electricity, medium voltage	0	0.333	0	0.0897	0.0298	0.00111	0	0.00122	0
Transport total	0.000906	0.145	1.22E-07	0.0356	0.00231	0.000113	0	0.0017	0.000277
Recycling PP	-0.00056	0.00123	0	0.00695	0.000426	0.000133	0	-0.00012	0

Table 8 Percentage contributions to impact category by Isonat process

Impact category	abiotic depletion	global warming (GWP100)	ozone layer depletion (ODP)	human toxicity	fresh water aquatic ecotox.	terrestrial ecotoxicity	photochemical oxidation	acidification	eutrophication
Unit	kg Sb eq	kg CO2 eq	kg CFC-11 eq	kg 1,4-DB eq	kg 1,4-DB eq	kg 1,4-DB eq	kg C2H2 eq	kg SO2 eq	kg PO4-- eq
Total	0.00669	0.345	2.56E-07	0.418	0.0545	0.00471	0.000272	0.00814	0.00132
<i>Hemp fibre production</i>	0	-0.486	0	0.0708	0.01	0.000421	0	0.000437	0
<i>Cotton fibres recycled</i>	0	-0.511	0	0.000432	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Bi-component Polyester</i>	0.00065	0.455	0	0.182	0.0312	0.00283	0.000124	0.00325	0.000595
<i>Flame retardant</i>	0	0.0426	0	0.0332	0.00431	0.000391	0	0.000155	0
<i>Kraft paper, unbleached</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Packaging film</i>	0	0.0648	0	0.01072	0.003076	0.000364	0	0.000695	0
<i>Electricity, medium voltage</i>	0	0.0139	0	0.00755	0.00176	4.10E-05	3.12E-06	8.82E-05	6.51E-06
<i>Heat gas</i>	0.00448	0.506	0	0.0546	0.000428	0.000469	2.70E-05	0.000565	6.37E-05
<i>Transport total</i>	0.00164	0.263	2.21E-07	0.0599	0.00411	0.000157	7.40E-05	0.00297	0.000534
<i>Recycling ECCS steel</i>	0	-0.014	0	-0.00112	-0.00053	0	0	0	0
<i>Recycling PP</i>	0	0	0	0.000204	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Landfill PE</i>	0	0.0123	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Martijn L.M. Broeren, Stijn N.C. Dellaert, Benjamin Cok, Martin K. Patel, Ernst Worrell, Li Shen; “Life cycle assessment of sisal fibre e Exploring how local practices can influence environmental performance” Journal of Cleaner Production 149 (2017) 818-827
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Sisal
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Sisal fibre and substantial amounts of organic residues: ratio 24t of residues for 1t of fibre. Authors propose to produce biogas with residues (not included as option in study)
Functional unit	One metric tonne of sisal fibre, ready for export at sea-port
Product family (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Textile (twine, ropes, carpets and bags)
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	In line with the ILCD, economic allocation is applied, yielding allocation factors of 78% for Tanzania and 83% for Brazil for sisal fibre based on 2011 prices
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	GHG emissions related to direct or indirect land use change (LUC) are not taken into account in this study because the methodology and databases to assess iLUC are still in development (BSI, 2011). However, LUC emissions are expected to be minor in this case. Agricultural land occupation included. Land use for sisal production has decreased in the past decades.
Geographic location, if defined	Tanzania (Tanga region) and Brazil (Bahia)
Data quality	Mostly primary data collected in Tanzania and Brazil were used and where primary data were not available, data from scientific literature, reports from relevant organisations and statistical databases were used after verification and cross-checking

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

	Secondary data: complementing interviews, data from Ecoinvent v2.2, and economic data from IEA statistics.
Impact assessment method	This study uses the LCA methodology standardised in ISO 14040/14044. GHG emissions are analysed according to IPCC's Fifth Assessment Report; the accounting of biogenic carbon is in line with PAS 2050, ILCD handbook, PEF (EC, 2013) and ISO 14067 :2013 ; agricultural land occupation and freshwater depletion are quantified at inventory level using ReCiPe Midpoint.
Damage categories (endpoint)	insufficient information available to quantify the damage potential
Impact categories (midpoint)	ReCiPe Midpoint method.
Other information or comments	Potential differences in emissions coming from the different residue management practices

2) Short report

This study focuses on the environmental performance of sisal fibre production by quantifying GHG emissions and energy use of producing sisal fibre in Tanzania and Brazil using LCA, based on region-specific inventory data.

Results:

The results show that sisal fibre production has much lower GHG emissions (75-95%) and non-renewable energy use (85-95%) compared to glass fibre on a kg-basis, which is in line with published LCAs on natural fibres.

Comparison of environmental footprint of sisal fibres produced Tanzania vs. Brazil:

As only 4% of sisal leaves is fibre, each tonne of sisal fibre produced generate 24t of organic residues. The disposal of these residues depends on whether the fibre extraction process step is centralised. In Tanzania, sisal fibre is primarily produced at a large scale at estates, using a centralised, stationary wet fibre extraction process. The large amounts of residues generated during decortication are washed away into open disposal ponds. This practice is a source of methane emissions.

Whereas in Brazil, sisal fibre is produced at smaller scale farms, using a decentralised, mobile dry decortication process. The organic residues are generally left on fields or used as animal feed. These local differences may lead to different environmental impacts. According to the authors, methane emissions due to residue disposal sites can be avoided by using this by-product to produce biogas.

Fig. 1. Overview of sisal fibre production systems in Tanzania and Brazil

Table 4
Cradle-to-factory gate environmental indicators for sisal fibre, other natural fibres and glass fibre (from peer-reviewed literature; see footnotes).

Fibre type	Agricultural land occupation, ha y/t	Freshwater depletion, m ³ /t	NREU, GJ/t	REU, GJ/t	GHG emissions, excluding sequestered carbon, kg CO ₂ eq./t	
					IPCC (2013) method	IPCC (2007) method
Sisal fibre, Tanzania	0.8	111	5.4	18.6	660	590
Sisal fibre, Brazil	1.0	1	2.5	18.1	170	170
Jute, India ^{a,b}	0.2	53	3.0	18.1	555	560
Kenaf, India ^b	0.2	506	3.1	18.1	560	570
Cotton, China ^b	0.8	6997	30.7	19.7	3290	3470
Cotton, United States ^b	1.1	1517	36.0	18.9	2960	3060
Hemp, Spain ^c	n.a.	n.a.	13.2	n.a.	n.a.	1600
Hemp, Italy ^{d,e}	0.3	n.a.	8.0	18.0	n.a.	200
Flax, France ^f	0.1	n.a.	11.7	n.a.	n.a.	250
Flax, Spain ^c	n.a.	n.a.	12.4	n.a.	n.a.	437
China reed, Switzerland ^g	n.a.	n.a.	3.6	n.a.	660 ^h	
Glass fibre, Europe ⁱ	0.0	70	44.4	1.4	2630	2630

^a Rainfed system.

^b Althaus et al. (2007).

^c González-García et al. (2010).

^d Zampori et al. (2013).

^e Values reflect economic allocation. NREU and REU values are derived from a graph.

^f Le Duigou et al. (2011).

^g Results reported by Joshi et al. (2004), based on original work by Corbiere-Nicollier et al. (2001).

^h This value is based on CO₂ emissions only.

ⁱ Kellenberger et al. (2007).

Fig. 2. Cradle-to-port NREU, REU and GHG emissions of 1 t sisal fibre production in Tanzania and Brazil by production stage.

Fig. 3. Cradle-to-port GHG emissions of 1 t sisal fibre in Tanzania under different residue disposal assumptions.

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Fig. 4. Cradle-to-port GHG emissions of 1 t sisal fibre at Estate 1 in Tanzania for three biogas production cases.

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Saraiva, Anna Bernstad, Elen B.a.v. Pacheco, Gabriel M. Gomes, Leila L.y. Visconte, C.a. Bernardo, Carla L. Simões, and Antonio G. Soares, “Comparative lifecycle assessment of mango packaging made from a polyethylene/Natural fiber-Composite and from cardboard material,” <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> Vol. 139, 2016, pp. 1168–1180.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Sponge (Lignocellulosic sponge-gourd residues)
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	High density polyethylene (HDPE) reinforced with 10% or 30% natural sponge fibre residues
Functional unit	Transportation of ten mangos per packaging
Product family (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fibres (reinforcement of packaging) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Packaging for mango fruits
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Mass allocation
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Not included
Geographic location, if defined	Brazil production; scenario 1 (inner-consumption) Brazil for use phase and end of life; scenario 2 (export) Europe for use phase and end-of-life,
Data quality	Primary data for: Milling of Luffa scrap, Extrusion of composite material, Injection of composite material/HDPE, Thermoforming of HIPS tray. Energy content of the three materials and ash content are modelled in EASETECH.

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

	Diesel use in plastic recycling and Electricity use in plastic recycling are taken from literature (secondary data).
Impact assessment method	JRC, ILCD 2011
Damage categories (endpoint)	ILCD, 2011 Endpoints
Impact categories (midpoint)	Climate Change (GWP) ; Ozone depletion ; Human toxicity (cancer effects); Human toxicity,(non-cancer effects); Particulate matter; Photochemical ozone formation; Acidification; Terrestrial eutrophication; Freshwater eutrophication; Marine eutrophication; Freshwater ecotoxicity;
Other information or comments	

2) Short report

This life-cycle assessment focuses on a packaging dedicated to the transportation of Brazilian mango fruits from the producer to the end-consumer. The packaging assessed consists of a reusable frame, made from high density polyethylene (HDPE) reinforced with 0%, 10% or 30% natural sponge fibre residues, and a high impact polystyrene recyclable (HIPS) tray (referred to as ‘composite packaging’ or ‘Mangobox’). The environmental performance of this packaging is compared with that of a similar single use packaging produced without natural fibres, and a commercial cardboard packaging (referred to as ‘cardboard packaging’).

Two scenarios were developed depending on the location of the end consumers 1) Brazil, and 2) Europe.

Primary data for the transformation of fibres and the packaging production were obtained experimentally. When no reuses were considered, most of the environmental impacts investigated were clearly lower for the cardboard packaging than for the composite box. This is due to the higher electricity input and higher fuel consumption in transports of the heavier composite packaging.

In the Brazilian scenario, after 4 or 9 uses the composite packaging greenhouse gas emissions² became inferior to those of the single-use cardboard box for a Mangobox reinforced respectively with 10% or 30% or natural fibres. In the European scenario, break-even was attained after 29 or 35 reuses, depending on the fibres' content for a Mangobox reinforced respectively with 10% or 30% or natural fibres.

This difference is mainly due to: 1. The environmental impact caused by the transport of a heavier packaging and 2. European waste management practices enabling energy recovery with incineration of cardboard packaging better than in Brazil.

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Fig. 1. System boundaries used in the mango packaging study.

² This assessment is only performed in relation to GHG emissions.

Table 3

Transportation distances used in modelling the production of the composite box in Scenario 1 (Internal consumption) and Scenario 2 (Export).

Product	Transport process	km	Scenario		Transport route
			1	2	
Sponge-gourd	Production → Transformation	422	X	X	Minas Gerais → Rio de Janeiro
HDPE and HIPS	Production → Transformation	1632	X	X	Triunfo → Rio de Janeiro
Frame + tray	Transformation → Mango producer	1865	X	X	Rio de Janeiro → Juazeiro
Frame + tray + mangos	Mango production → Retail/Harbor (BR)	506	X		Juazeiro → Rio de Janeiro
Frame + tray + mangos	Harbor (BR) → Harbor (Europe)	8598		X	Rio de Janeiro → Rotterdam
Frame + tray + mangos	Harbor (Europe) → Retail (Europe)	1000		X	Assumed
Frame	Retail (Europe) → Harbor (Europe)	1000		X	Assumed
Frame	Harbor (Europe) → Harbor (BR)	8598		X	Rotterdam → Rio de Janeiro
Tray	Retail → Incineration/Landfill	100	X	X	Assumed
Tray	Retail → Recycler	100	X	X	Assumed
Frame	Harbor (BR) → Mango producer	506		X	Rio de Janeiro → Juazeiro
Pulp	Production → Transformation	1574	X		Porto Seguro → Pacajus
Cardboard box	Transformation → Mango producer	777	X		Pacajus → Juazeiro
Cardboard box + mangos	Mango production → Retail/Harbor (BR)	506	X		Juazeiro → Rio de Janeiro
Cardboard box + mangos	Harbor (BR) → Harbor (Europe)	8598		X	Rio de Janeiro → Rotterdam
Cardboard box + mangos	Harbor (Europe) → Retail (Europe)	1000		X	Assumed
Cardboard box	Retail → Incineration/Landfill	100	X	X	Assumed
Cardboard box	Retail → Recycler	100	X	X	Assumed

Fig. 4. Environmental impacts per functional unit of the Mangobox with various contents of sponge-gourd scrap and of the cardboard alternative for Scenario 1. **Key:** GWP - Global warming potential; A - acidification; E - eutrophication; POF - photochemical ozone formation; ODP - ozone depletion potential; PM - particulate matter; Emw - eutrophication marine water; Efw - eutrophication freshwater; HTc - human toxicity carcinogenic; HTnc - human toxicity non-carcinogenic; ET - eutrophication terrestrial; ET - ecotoxicity.

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Günther, Jasmin, Niels Thevs, Hans-Jörg Gusovius, Ina Sigmund, Torsten Brückner, Volker Beckmann, and Nurbay Abdusalik, “Carbon and phosphorus footprint of the cotton production in Xinjiang, China, in comparison to an alternative fibre (Apocynum) from Central Asia,” Journal of Cleaner Production Vol. 148, 2017, pp. 490–497.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis (Phosphorous footprint) <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Carbon Footprint
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Cotton vs. Apocynum
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Natural fibre extraction
Functional unit	Kg/natural fiber
Product family (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Textile
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation (transport to farm only) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (<i>to be detailed in the report section</i>) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): methane emissions from residue disposal
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Not specified
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Not included because study is made on plantation that have been existing for more than 50 years
Geographic location, if defined	Xinjiang, China
Data quality	Primary data for cotton, secondary data for Apocynum
Impact assessment method	Carbon footprint calculated according to: The Guide to PAS 2050:2011. How to Carbon Footprint Your Products, Identify Hotspots and Reduce Emissions in Your Supply Chain. BSI, London. Phosphorous footprint: defined as ‘total input and output including storage and losses of phosphorus that are directly or indirectly caused during the life stages of a product’. Determined according to Brunner, P.H., Rechberger, H., 2004.

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

	Practical Handbook of Material Flow Analysis. CRC/Lewis, Boca Raton, FL.
Damage categories (endpoint)	Climate change, deterioration of soil
Impact categories (midpoint)	Ghg emissions, energy consumption, phosphorous consumption
Other information or comments	<p>ECOS' comments: Main limitations of study:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data asymmetry between the two feedstocks compared (primary data for cotton versus (very old) secondary data for <i>apocynum</i>) - Findings of the study mostly interesting for the comparison of environmental footprints of cottons (e.g; China vs. Australia).

2) Short report

Cotton accounts for one third of all natural and synthetic fibres of the total textile production. Xinjiang (China), has become one of the most important cotton producers with highest yields worldwide. This study determines the carbon ('climate-' and 'energy-') and phosphorus footprints of this cotton production and compares it to a theoretical production of an alternative fibre from 'Apocynum', a bast fibre plant from the Xinjian region.

Data:

Data on cotton production was collected through farmers interviews collected during six years in Xinjiang. The data for Apocynum is secondary data from literature (e.g. description of experiments in the Soviet Union).

Results:

With climate, energy and phosphorous footprints of respectively 4.43 kg CO₂e/kg fibre; 30.90 MJ/ kg fibre, and 101 g P/kg fibre, cotton fibres produced in Xinjiang have a higher impact on the environment than both: cotton produced elsewhere (e.g. Australia) and fibres from apocynum.

The main reason of this important footprint is the massive use of mineral fertilizers (accounting for about 65% or the carbon footprint of cotton production) whose production is fuelled by coal in China. The production of organic cotton without use of chemical fertiliser and pesticides, would result in considerably lower carbon and phosphorus footprints per area unit.

Requiring much less (and mostly less often) fertilizers, apocynum based fibres have significantly lower environmental impact; with a climate footprint of 1.93 kg CO₂e/kg fibre, an energy footprint of 21.85 MJ/kg fibre, and a phosphorus footprint of 1.6 g P/kg fibre. In the case of Apocynum, 65.1% of the climate footprint and 64.1% of the energy footprint are attributed to chemical treatment of the fibres in the extraction process.

Table 6
Data for phosphorus footprint calculation.

	Cotton	Source	Apocynum	Source
Fertiliser input				
Fertiliser kg P/ha	101.93	Activity data	38.25	Berljand (1950)
Losses from mining to fertiliser				
Mining %	18	Schröder et al. (2010)	18	Schröder et al. (2010)
Rock amelioration %	16	Schröder et al. (2010)	16	Schröder et al. (2010)
Fertiliser production %	5	Schröder et al. (2010)	5	Schröder et al. (2010)

Table 8

CO_{2e} emissions (*climate footprint*) and energy consumption (equivalent to *energy footprint*) of materials, farm operations, and fibre extraction of cotton and *Apocynum* cultivation.

Material/farm operation/steps of fibre extraction	Cotton				Apocynum			
	Climate footprint		Energy footprint		Climate footprint		Energy footprint	
	kg CO _{2e} /kg fibre	%	MJ/kg fibre	%	kg CO _{2e} /kg fibre	%	MJ/kg fibre	%
Fertiliser production	2.83	63.9	21.14	68.4	0.26	13.3	3.24	15.5
Pesticide production	0.01	0.1	0.31	1.0				
Herbicide production	0.00	0.1	0.13	0.4				
Mulch production	0.09	2.1	2.93	9.5				
Tube production	0.01	0.3	0.58	1.9				
Seeds	0.03	0.7	0.52	1.7	0.00	0.0	0.00	0.0
Tillage	0.03	0.7	0.15	0.5				
Ploughing					0.00	0.1	0.12	0.5
Harrowing					0.00	0.0	0.13	0.5
Cut furrows	0.04	0.8	0.24	0.8	0.00	0.1	0.07	0.2
Planting	0.01	0.2	0.01	0.0	0.00	0.0	0.00	0.0
Fertiliser application	0.02	0.4	0.03	0.1	0.00	0.1	0.00	0.0
Pesticide, herbicide application	0.00	0.0	0.02	0.1				
Weeding					0.00	0.2	0.23	0.9
Irrigation	0.30	6.8	3.98	12.9	0.01	0.5	0.40	1.5
Harvest	0.00	0.0	0.00	0.0	0.15	7.9	2.00	7.5
Transport (on farm)	0.01	0.1	0.07	0.2	0.01	0.6	0.13	0.5
Ginning of cotton	0.07	1.6	0.76	2.5				
Retting					0.06	3.3	0.87	3.3
Decortication					0.05	2.6	0.54	2.6
Hackling					0.07	3.5	0.72	3.5
Chemical treatment					1.26	65.1	13.38	64.1
Soil emissions	0.98	22.2	–	–	0.05	2.8	–	–
Total	4.43	100	30.89	100	1.93	100	21.85	100

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”)	Agyekum, Eric Ofori, K.p.j. (Karen) Fortuin, and Eugenie Van Der Harst, “Environmental and social life cycle assessment of bamboo bicycle frames made in Ghana,” <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> Vol. 143, 2017, pp. 1069–1080.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Bamboo
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Kenaf fibres, aluminium, Durban solution
Functional unit	Production of an average city bicycle frame
Product family (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Production of bike frame
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning (NOT INCLUDED IN S-LCA) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution (NOT INCLUDED IN S-LCA) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Use stage (NOT INCLUDED IN S-LCA) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> End-of-life (NOT INCLUDED IN S-LCA) <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Not specified.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Not consider due to lack of available data: bamboo harvested from the wild in Ghana.
Geographic location, if defined	Ghana for harvesting, processing and manufacturing of bike frame; the Netherlands for use and EoL phase.
Data quality	Secondary data for LCA assessment; primary data (interviews) for S-LCA
Impact assessment method	ISO 14040-14044; UNEP/SETAC, 2009 “Guidelines for social life-cycle assessment of products”; UNEP/SETAC, 2013 “The Methodological Sheets for Sub-categories in Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA)”
Damage categories (endpoint)	The impact indicators assess the resulting impacts on the interests of stakeholders and are therefore all damage oriented.
Impact categories (midpoint)	LCA ISO 14040-14044 ; CML Baseline 2001. (Abiotic Depletion, Acidification, Eutrophication, Global Warming, Ozone Depletion, Human Toxicity, Freshwater Aquatic Ecotoxicity, Marine Aquatic Ecotoxicity, Terrestrial Ecotoxicity, and Photochemical Oxidation) S-LCA child labour, freedom of association, working hours, health and safety, respect of local people's rights, and local employment. Point Performance

	indicator (1 to 5).
Other information or comments	Site-specific data are needed for S-LCA because the cultural and economic differences between countries influence social impacts. The limited availability of site-specific data restricts the number of impact subcategories that can be used for S-LCA.

2) Short report

This study combines a LCA (carried out in accordance with ISO 14040 and ISO 14044) with a S-LCA. The LCA assesses the environmental impacts of bamboo bicycle frames produced in Ghana, and compare the results with China -made (Tianjin) conventional aluminium and steel bicycle frames. The bicycle frames are used in bicycles which are assembled and sold in Amsterdam, the Netherlands. For the S-LCA the following subcategories were selected and assigned (classification) to the two stakeholder groups: child labour, freedom of association, working hours, health and safety, respect of local people's rights, and local employment. While the LCA includes the complete life cycle of the bamboo frame, the S-LCA is limited to the steps taking place in Ghana: bamboo extraction, its processing, and production of bamboo bicycle frame.

Results:

The overall environmental impact of the bamboo bicycle frame is generally about 50% less than aluminium frames and about 30% less than steel bicycle frames produced in China. This environmental performance of the bamboo bicycle could be further improved in impact categories where it currently presents higher impacts than conventional frames, by preserving bamboo with Borax and water solution instead of Dursban and water solution (improvement of freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity and terrestrial ecotoxicity).

Fig. 2. Comparison of the environmental impact of bamboo, aluminium and steel bicycle frames to ten environmental impact categories. The result of the frame with the highest impact in a category is set at 100%.

The production of the bamboo bicycle frame in Ghana has no negative impacts on most of the social impact subcategories. However, most companies did not contribute to improvements in the economic value of the bamboo resources and the provision of safety gear for harvesting operations and supervision was inadequate.

Fig. 4. Performance of companies and impacts on stakeholders in the bamboo extraction process. The graph is based on data from three bamboo bicycle frame companies in Ghana.

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”)	Carmen Galan-Marin, Carlos Rivera-Gomez and Antonio Garcia-Martinez, (2016) “Use of Natural-Fiber Bio-Composites in Construction versus Traditional Solutions: Operational and Embodied Energy Assessment,” <i>Materials</i> .9. 465. 10.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment (only energy consumption and GHG emissions) <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Animal fibre: wool, used cut and raw, without washing or processing; Algae
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Natural fibre bio-composite stabilised soil block
Functional unit	The total surface of walls in each case
Product family (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Building material (e.g. for masonry walls)
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Not specified
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Not included
Geographic location, if defined	Spain
Data quality	Secondary data: The environmental data of wool and algae have been extracted from the recent studies conducted by Barber and Pellow ¹ and Resurreccion et al ² , respectively. The environmental data of the rest of the building materials were obtained from the well-recognized ECOINVENT database.
Impact assessment method	CML 2001 method
Damage categories (endpoint)	Climate change
Impact categories (midpoint)	Cumulative energy demand (MJ/t wool top), Global warming potential MJ/t wool

¹ Barber, A.; Pellow, G. Life Cycle Assessment: New Zealand Merino Industry, Merino Wool Total Energy Use and Carbon Dioxide Emissions; The Agribusiness Group: Canterbury, New Zealand, 2006

² Resurreccion, E.P.; Colosi, L.M.; White, M.A.; Clarens, A.F. Comparison of algae cultivation methods for bioenergy production using a combined life cycle assessment and life cycle costing approach. *Bioresource Technol.* 2012, 126, 298–306.

top)

Other information or comments

2) Short report

This paper compares conventional building materials for load-bearing walls and with a composite one stabilized with natural fibers. The load-bearing walls it compares are used in a widespread type of twentieth century buildings in Europe and are still built nowadays in developing countries.

The structural and thermal insulation characteristics of different construction solutions are considered for this LCA. The LCAs encompass the whole lifespan of the considered construction materials.

Three construction materials are assessed according to their environmental performance: fired clay brick masonry walls (BW), concrete block masonry walls (CW), and stabilized soil block masonry walls (SW) stabilized with natural fibers and alginates. The energy consumption and GHG emissions incurred by these materials are evaluated according to two locations with different climates.

Results (see table below):

The manufacturing phase of the materials is the phase which has the most prominent environmental impact of all phases in the life cycle of a construction material.

Buildings made out of SW have a lower environmental impact than those out of BW and CW. From a GHG emissions and energy consumption perspectives, around three SW homes could be erected for every two homes built with BW

Table 4. Inventory list of the materials used for every type of building system and climate.

Stage	Component	Unit	BW		CW		SW	
			LOCATION I	LOCATION II	LOCATION I	LOCATION II	LOCATION I	LOCATION II
Manufacture PH ₁	Gravel	kg	199.316,16	199.316,16	199.316,16	199.316,16	199.316,16	199.316,16
	Limestone	kg	776,96	776,96	776,96	776,96	776,96	776,96
	Concrete	m ³	158,36	158,36	185,97	185,97	158,36	158,36
	Bricks	kg	196.924,82	196.924,82	83.044,34	83.044,34	83.044,34	83.044,34
	Plaster Board	kg	10.071,90	10.071,90	10.071,90	10.071,90	10.071,90	10.071,90
	Mortar	kg	86.316,30	86.316,30	20.461,47	20.461,47	10.446,01	10.446,01
	Clay plaster	kg	19.666,60	19.666,60	19.666,60	19.666,60	19.666,60	19.666,60
	Glass	kg	3.583,13	3.583,13	3.583,13	3.583,13	3.583,13	3.583,13
	Aluminium	kg	2.329,44	2.329,44	2.329,44	2.329,44	2.329,44	2.329,44
	Reinforcing steel	kg	6.550,74	6.550,74	6.550,74	6.550,74	6.550,74	6.550,74
	Steel	kg	314,62	314,62	314,62	314,62	314,62	314,62
	Paint	kg	8.263,95	8.263,95	8.263,95	8.263,95	8.263,95	8.263,95
	Bitumen	kg	258,39	258,39	258,39	258,39	258,39	258,39
	Polyethylene	kg	45,81	45,81	45,81	45,81	45,81	45,81
	Polyurethane	kg	155,93	27,46	187,11	467,78	155,93	311,85
	Polyvinylchloride	kg	27,46	27,46	27,46	27,46	27,46	27,46
	Rubber	kg	79,06	79,06	79,06	79,06	79,06	79,06
	Water	kg	34.664,05	34.664,05	26.845,78	26.845,78	101.112,30	101.112,30
	Wood	m ³	4,11	4,11	4,11	4,11	4,11	4,11
	Sand	kg	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	226.324,80	226.324,80
Algae	kg	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	2.715,90	2.715,90	
Sheep Wool	kg	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	565,81	565,81	

Stage	Component	Unit	BW		CW		SW	
			LOCATION I	LOCATION II	LOCATION I	LOCATION II	LOCATION I	LOCATION II
Construction and Demolition PH ₂	Electricity (Const-Dem)	kWh	34.058,76	34.501,07	29.467,66	30.131,13	31.651,75	32.762,28
	Diesel (Const-Dem)	MJ	286.093,61	289.808,99	247.528,31	253.101,48	29.737,79	275.203,15
	Transport (Const-Dem)	tkm	111.348,48	111.370,00	97.721,92	97.754,20	94.982,97	97.186,61
Operational PH ₅	Electricity (Operational)	kWh	767.477,57	814.227,25	767.477,57	814.227,25	767.477,57	814.227,25
	Natural Gas (Operational)	MJ	3.867.080,73	7.658.781,91	3.867.080,73	7.658.781,91	3.867.080,73	7.658.781,91
Final Disposal PH ₄	Brick final disposal	kg	196.924,82	196.924,82	83.044,34	83.044,34	83.044,34	83.044,34
	Concrete final disposal	kg	395.893,90	395.893,90	464.924,50	464.924,50	395.893,90	395.893,90
	Glass final disposal	kg	3.583,13	3.583,13	3.583,13	3.583,13	3.583,13	3.583,13
	Polyurethane final disposal	kg	155,93	343,04	187,11	467,78	155,93	311,85
	Polyvinylchloride final disposal	kg	27,46	27,46	27,46	27,46	27,46	27,46
	Steel final disposal	kg	6.865,36	6.865,36	6.865,36	6.865,36	6.865,36	6.865,36
	Wood final disposal	kg	2.874,80	2.874,80	2.874,80	2.874,80	2.874,80	2.874,80
	Aluminum final disposal	kg	2.329,44	2.329,44	2.329,44	2.329,44	2.329,44	2.329,44
	Bitumen final disposal	kg	258,39	258,39	258,39	258,39	258,39	258,39
	Inert material final disposal	kg	324.671,08	324.671,08	258.816,25	258.816,25	478.407,30	478.407,30

Key: Operational energy data are considered according to the benchmarks included a Spanish ministry report for houses located in Spain, considering two climates, location 1, corresponding to the warm Mediterranean climate and location 2, corresponding to the inner continental areas of the peninsula³.

³ SPAHOUSEC PROJECT, Análisis del Consumo Energético del Sector Residencial en España, Secretaría General Departamento de Planificación y Estudios: Madrid, Spain, 2011; pp. 1–76. Available online: http://www.idae.es/uploads/documentos/documentos_informe_spahousec_acc_f68291a3.pdf (accessed on 19 April 2016).

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Diego Magalhães do Nascimento, Amanda Ferreira Dias, Celso Pires de Araújo Junior, Morsyleide de Freitas Rosa, João Paulo Saraiva Morais, Maria Cléa Brito de Figueirêdo; ‘A comprehensive approach for obtaining cellulose nanocrystal from coconut fiber. Part II: Environmental assessment of technological pathways’; Industrial Crops and Products Volume 93, 25 December 2016, pp. 58-65
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Unripe coconut husks (as a by-product of the coconut water industry)
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Cellulose nanocrystal; lignin; (methane)
Functional unit	The production of 1g of cellulose nanocrystal
Product family (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Alternative to carbon nanotubes as reinforcement agents in nano-composites
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Mass and economic allocation for the unit processes gridding and pulping
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Not included
Geographic location, if defined	Brazil
Data quality	Primary data regarding the consumption of water, electricity and reagents Secondary data regarding the parameters from the bleaching effluents; inventory data on the production of chemical reagents and energy; fractionation of unripe coconut husks and the production of ammonium sulphate (as the production ammonium persulfate was not found in the database used)

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Impact assessment method	The hierarchical version of ReCiPe method at the midpoint level.
Damage categories (endpoint)	Not specified
Impact categories (midpoint)	Climate change, acidification, water body eutrophication, marine eutrophication, human toxicity and water depletion (for more on this, see Rosa, M.F., Medeiros, E.S., Malmonge, J.A., Gregorski, K.S., Wood, D.F., Mattoso, L.H.C., Glenn, G., Orts, W.J., Imam, S.H., 'Cellulose nanowhiskers from coconut husk fibers: Effect of preparation conditions on their thermal and morphological behavior'. Carbohydr. Polym. Vol. 81, 2010, pp. 83–92, http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2010.01.059).
Other information or comments	For detailed descriptions of the extraction methods, see Part I of the study. ECOS' comment: interesting study although would have been more interesting for the project to have study comparing extraction of natural fibres (e.g CNU) to production of synthetic ones.

2) Short report

Unripe coconut fibres are a by-product of the coconut water industry. These fibres can be extracted from unripe coconut husks, a renewable and abundant source of lignocellulose in the tropical regions. However, **recent studies have reported high environmental impacts associated with the method of cellulose nanocrystal extraction from coconuts, mostly related to increased water and energy consumption, use of chlorine-based chemical reagents, and low yield.**

The study compares the environmental impacts of 4 methods for hydrolyse and extract cellulose nanocrystal from coconut fibres (also enabling lignin recovery): (1) diluted sulfuric acid (CNH1); (2) concentrated sulfuric acid (CNH2); (3) ammonium persulfate (CNO); and (4) high powered ultrasound (CNU). The authors also assess whether the increase of the overall environmental performance, go alongside the recovery of as many valuable components as possible, such as lignin and hemicellulose. This is done via the testing of an alternative scenario: burning of lignin and use of the generated energy to extract cellulose nanocrystals (already happening in paper and cellulose mills to generate power).

Hence, the methods are assessed according to: (1) the performance in extracting cellulose nanocrystal from coconut husks; (2) the performance in recovering other materials vs. these materials being a power source for the system.

Results:

The LCA results indicate that cellulose nanocrystals obtained using the high-power ultrasound method have (quasi systematically) a better environmental performance than chemical-based methods tested. Power consumption, acetic acid production and water consumption are the factors that make the biggest difference.

The use of lignin as a power source makes a bigger environmental impact than its recovery.

Table 1
 Data used for mass and economic allocation.

Outputs	Unit	Cellulose nanocrystal extraction methods ^a			
		CNH1	CNH2	CNO	CNU
Cellulose nanocrystal	g	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Lignin	g	1.3	2.4	2.2	0.9
Mass allocation					
Cellulose nanocrystal	%	44	29	31	53
Lignin	%	56	71	69	47
Economic allocation					
Cellulose nanocrystal(11 \$/g) ^b	%	86	77	78	90
Lignin (1.4 \$/g) ^c	%	14	23	22	10

^a CNH1: extraction with diluted acid; CNH2: extraction with concentrated acid; CNO: extraction with ammonium persulfate; CNU: extraction with high power ultrasound.

Table 3
Life cycle inventory of the assessed cellulose nanocrystal extraction methods.

Inputs	Unit	Cellulose nanocrystal extraction methods ^a			
		CNH1	CNH2	CNO	CNU
Fiber	g	13.70	25.38	23.40	9.22
Acetic acid	g	127.90	236.68	218.34	86.23
HCl	g	1.37	2.54	2.34	0.92
H ₂ SO ₄	g	9.23	56.87	-	-
HNO ₃	g	-	-	-	-
NaOH	g	7.72	13.78	-	5.02
H ₂ O ₂	g	11.31	20.99	-	7.65
KOH	g	2.04	3.79	-	1.38
NaClO ₂	g	-	-	-	-
(NH ₄) ₂ S ₂ O ₄	g	-	-	108.65	-
Water	l	6.43	8.80	1.89	1.67
Energy	MJ	4.38	5.15	4.54	2.48
Emissions					
BOD	g	3.28	3.88	1.95	1.74
COD	g	3.63	5.67	2.82	2.63
Total nitrogen	g	1.156 × 10 ⁻²	2.2 × 10 ⁻²	5.13	7.89 × 10 ⁻³
Total phosphorus	g	1.366 × 10 ⁻³	2.518 × 10 ⁻³	8.026 × 10 ⁻⁴	9.255 × 10 ⁻⁴
Phenol	g	5.508 × 10 ⁻⁴	9.74 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.841 × 10 ⁻⁵	3.570 × 10 ⁻⁴
Furfural	g	0.25	0.31	0.30	0.21
HMF	g	3.415 × 10 ⁻³	4.177 × 10 ⁻³	4.12 × 10 ⁻³	2.781 × 10 ⁻³
Products					
CN	g	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Lignin	g	1.29	2.40	2.21	0.87

^a CNH1: extraction with diluted acid; CNH2: extraction with concentrated acid; CNO: extraction with ammonium persulfate; CNU: extraction with high power ultrasound.

Fig. 3. Comparative impacts of each studied method, considering mass (M) and economic (E) allocation.

Fig. 3 key: CC Climate Change in kg CO₂-eq/g; TA: Terrestrial Acidification in kg SO₂-eq/g; FE: Water Body Eutrophication in kg P-eq/g; ME: Marine Eutrophication in kg N-eq/g; HT: Human Toxicity in kg 1,4-DB eq/g; WD: Water Depletion in m³/g

Alternative scenario applied to CNU (burning lignin during the process in order to generate energy): reduces electricity consumption however increases environmental impacts in four out of 6 categories of the six analysed categories. This happened because the impacts from milling and pulping processes were attributed to cellulose nanocrystals only (hence decreasing yield overall).

Fig. 5. Results of the environmental impacts for high power ultrasounds and the alternative scenario of lignin burning.

T2.1 Literature review – Thermal Insulation Material

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Pargana, Nuno, Manuel Duarte Pinheiro, José Dinis Silvestre, and Jorge de Brito, "Comparative Environmental Life Cycle Assessment Of Thermal Insulation Materials Of Buildings", Energy And Buildings, Vol. 82, 2014, pp. 466-481.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment (comparative) <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	LWA: clay. XPS: dimethyl ether, polystyrene crystals, difluoroethane. EPS: expandable polystyrene. PUR: polyol, isocyanate. ICB: raw cork (falca)
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Insulation board from different thermal insulation materials (conventional and bio-based). Extruded polystyrene (XPS), expanded polystyrene (EPS), polyurethane (PUR), expanded cork agglomerate (ICB), expanded clay lightweight aggregates (LWA).
Functional unit	Mass (kg) of insulation board that provides a thermal resistance R-value of 1 (m ² K/W) and an area A of 1 m ²
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Materials
Possible applications	Thermal insulation in construction. Raw material in the production of lightweight concrete blocks (LWA)
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Mass, volume and economic allocation
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC and dLUC are not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	Portugal
Data quality	Primary data: site specific data from companies. Ecoinvent database.
Impact assessment method	CML 2001 (Netherlands, Institute of Environmental Sciences of Leiden University)
Damage categories (endpoint)	

Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming, ozone depletion, acidification of soil and water, eutrophication, photochemical ozone creation and depletion of abiotic resources
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Quality of LCI data:

Table 1: Quality of information used in LCI data.

Company that produces: (average value-AV)	Quality of the information used in the LCI of the building products studied				
	Confidence (AV=2.2)	Integrity ^c (AV=3.1); market share (%)	Temporal correlation (AV=1.2)	Geographic correlation (AV=1)	Technological correlation (AV=1)
LWA (1.2)	1: Verified ^a data (internal reports and visit to the production line) and based on measurements ^b	2: One company and a two-year period; 33% of national production and sales (i.e. a small number of companies, but for appropriate periods)	1: 2010 and 2011 (i.e. maximum difference of 3 years from the year being studied)	1 (i.e. data from the region being studied)	1 (i.e. data from the company being studied)
XPS boards (1.4)	2: Unverified (but including a visit to the production line) but based on measurements	2: One company and a two-year period; 50% of national production and 30% of sales	1: 2010 and 2011	1	1
EPS boards (1.6)	2: Partially verified data (internal documents and visit to the production line) and based on hypothesis ^d	2: One company and a three-year period	2: 2008, 2009 and 2010 (i.e. less than 6 years difference)	1	1
PUR boards (2.4)	5: Neither verified nor qualified data estimations (and not including a visit to the production line)	4: Representative data but from only one company and from short periods (data measured from the process); 100% of national production for the construction sector	1: 2012	1	1
ICB boards (1.6)	2: Unverified (but including a visit to the production line) but based on measurements	2: One company and a two-year period; most important company in the national market	2: 2008 and 2010	1	1

Notes to Table 3:

^aData can be verified by comparison with original documents, by repeating the calculations, by comparison with other sources, by material or energy balances, etc.

^bExperimental measurement techniques must be described in the report.

^cTo achieve an Integrity value of 1, data representing a sufficient number of companies over a period that enables the elimination of fluctuations should be used.

^dThe considered hypothesis must also be specified in the report.

T2.1 Literature review – Kenaf-Fiber reinforced polyurethane

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Batouli, Seyed Mostafa, Yimin Zhu, Mangesh Nar, and Nandika Anne D’Souza, "Environmental Performance Of Kenaf-Fiber Reinforced Polyurethane: A Life Cycle Assessment Approach", Journal Of Cleaner Production, Vol. 66, 2014, pp. 164-173.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Kenaf fiber
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Structural insulated panels: 1. Pure rigid polyurethane foam (PRPUF), 2. PU reinforced with 5% kenaf core, 3. PU reinforced with 10% kenaf core, 4. PU reinforced with 15% kenaf core
Functional unit	The mass (kg) of insulating board, which involves a thermal resistance of 1 m ² /kW for the same area of 1 m ²
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Materials
Possible applications	Structural insulated panels (SIPs) are an energy-efficient building technology. They can be used for walls, partitions, roofing and floorings. SIP walls perform better because of their long uniform insulation and fewer joints.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	No allocation procedure specified
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	No iLUC or dLUC mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	
Data quality	Ecoinvent, industry data, and U.S. life cycle inventory (USLCI) libraries
Impact assessment method	Building for Environmental and Economic Sustainability (BEES)

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming, acidification, human health cancerogenics, human health non cancerogenics, human health air pollutants, eutrophication, ecotoxicity, smog, natural resource depletion, indoor air quality, habitat alteration, water intake, ozone depletion.
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Kenaf-fiber reinforced polyurethane samples:

Figure 1: Flexural samples pure PU, 5, 10 and 15% kenaf core loading

Life cycle inventory:

Table 1: Materials and energy used to create the samples

	Materials (g)			RPM	Mixing time Sec	Power W	Energy J	Density Kg m ⁻³	Cell diameter Micron	Volume fraction of kenaf core (∅) %
	Polyol	MDI	Kenaf core							
Pure rigid PU	100	130	0	2559	120	31.844	31.836	415	390	0
5% Kenaf core in rigid PU	95	123.5	11.5	2559	180	47.766	47.754	286	650	5.11
10% Kenaf core in rigid PU	90	117	23	2559	360	95.532	95.508	448	162	16.02
15% Kenaf core in rigid PU	85	110.5	34.5	2559	480	127.376	127.344	744.5	340	39.94

Functional unit:

Table 2: Definition of the functional unit according to thermal resistance

Sample	10 Degrees centigrade						50 Degrees centigrade					
	Thickness (Cm)	Mass (Kg)	Energy (KJ)	Materials (kg)			Thickness (Cm)	Mass (Kg)	Energy (KJ)	Materials (kg)		
				Polyol	MDI	Kenaf core				Polyol	MDI	Kenaf core
Pure rigid PU	3.57	14.82	2.05	6.45	8.38	0.00	3.91	16.22	2.24	7.05	9.17	0.00
5% Kenaf core in rigid PU	3.31	9.46	1.96	3.91	5.08	0.47	3.65	10.44	2.17	4.31	5.61	0.52
10% Kenaf core in rigid PU	3.82	17.13	7.12	6.70	8.72	1.71	4.15	18.61	7.73	7.28	9.47	1.86
15% Kenaf core in rigid PU	5.21	38.79	21.48	14.34	18.64	5.82	5.54	41.24	22.83	15.24	19.81	6.19

System definition:

Figure 1: Typical life cycle for kenaf-based SIP

Figure 2: Manufacturing process block diagram for one functional unit SIP

Manufacturing process major steps:

1. Resin metering and mixing
2. Impregnation
3. PU foaming
4. Tankfarm
5. Double belt
6. Cutting unit

T2.1 Literature review – Protease in poultry feed

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Oxenboll, K.M., K. Pontoppida, and F. Fru-Nji, "Use Of A Protease In Poultry Feed Offers Promising Environmental Benefits", International Journal Of Poultry Science, Vol. 10, No. 11, 2011, pp. 842-848.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Corn, soybean meal, aminoacids (from wheat)
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Poultry feed
Functional unit	Ton of broiler chicks. LCA analysis is based on data from the grower period (22-42 d), 200 ppm protease
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Use of proteins and protease to improve broilers diet
Possible applications	When animals utilize nitrogen better, there is a possibility to decrease the diet protein content and in turn also reduce the content of nitrogen in manure (reduce emissions). Use enzymes in feed to improve utilization of nutrients. Proteases are added to feed with the purpose of increasing dietary protein hydrolysis and thus enabling improved nitrogen utilization.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Use stage (manure production) <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Allocation procedure not mentioned
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC and dLUC not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	Denmark
Data quality	Ecoinvent database 2009, primary data from Novozymes A/S (Denmark)
Impact assessment method	CML baseline 2000
Damage categories (endpoint)	

Impact categories (midpoint)	Acidification, eutrophication, global warming, N-containing emissions (N, NH3, NOx, N2O)
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Life cycle inventory:

Table 1: Broiler diets (d 22-42) with normal and low protein level and 200 ppm protease (15,000 PROT/kg) (adopted from Freitas et al.,2011)

	Normal Protein Level (NP)			Low Protein Level (LP)		
	d 22-35	d 36-42	Avr d 22-42	d 22-35	d 36-42	Avr d 22-42
Ingredients (g/kg)						
Corn	609.2	628.7	618.95	655.0	671.0	663.00
Soybean meal	270.0	229.3	249.65	232.6	194.7	213.65
Meat and bone meal	66.0	67.0	66.50	67.0	68.0	67.50
Soybean fat	41.2	52.1	46.65	33.8	45.2	39.50
Limestone	1.5	1.5	1.50	1.5	1.5	1.50
Common salt ^a	2.8	2.9	2.85	3.0	3.1	3.05
Na bicarbonate	0.8	0.6	0.70	0.4	0.3	0.35
DL-methionine	2.4	2.0	2.20	1.7	1.3	1.50
L-lysine HCl	2.3	2.0	2.15	1.5	1.4	1.45
L-threonine	0.3	0.4	0.35	0.0	0.0	0.00
Px. Vit and Min ^{bd}	2.5	2.5		2.5	2.5	
Choline chloride ^d	0.8	0.8		0.8	0.8	
Kaolin ^d	0-0.2	0-0.3		0-0.4	0-0.5	
Protease ^e	0/0.2	0/0.2	0/0.20	0/0.2	0/0.2	0/0.20
ME (kcal/kg)	3,144.0	3,247.0	3,195.00	3,144.0	3,247.0	3,195.00
Analyzed CP (g/kg)	197.0	179.0	188.00	189.0	172.0	180.50

^aNaCl.

^bVitamin, mineral and additive contribution per kg of feed: vitamin A: 9,000 IU; vitamin D3: 2,500 IU; vitamin E: 20 IU; vitamin K3: 2.5 mg; vitamin B1: 1.5 mg; vitamin B2: 6 mg; vitamin B6: 3 mg; pantothenic acid: 1.2 mg; biotin: 0.06 mg; folic acid: 0.8 mg; niacin: 25 mg; vitamin B12: 12 µg; I: 2 mg; Se: 0.25 mg; Cu: 20 mg; Mn: 160 mg; Zn: 100 mg; Fe: 100 mg (all sources as sulphate, except for sodium selenite and calcium iodate); monensim sodium: 100 ppm (1-21 d); salinomycin: 66 ppm (22-40 d).

^dThe protease replaced kaolin.

^eNot included in the LCA calculation

T2.1 Literature review – Insect based protein feed

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	PROteINSECT: Insects as sustainable sources of protein. http://www.proteinsect.eu/
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Insects: house fly, black soldier fly. Range of organic wastes as substrate for larvae growth
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Animal feeds based on insects for fish, poultry and pig, which are rich in protein (isoleucine, valine, lysine, methionine, tryptophan) as well as fat and minerals. Residual substrate. High value oils biodiesel. Chitosan antimicrobials
Functional unit	House fly, fresh manure: 1 kg of waste reduction. House fly, dewatered manure: 1 kg of waste reduction. Black soldier fly, manual harvest: 1 kg of insect product. Black soldier fly, automated harvest: 1 kg of insect product
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Insect protein for animal feed, organic waste reduction
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Impact categories: per kg of manure reduction/per kg insect product. Product yield: per kg of input substrate. Energy and labour: per kg insect product.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC and dLUC are not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	Europe, China and Sub-Saharan Africa
Data quality	Primary data: surveys from pilot plants in different locations
Impact assessment method	Life Cycle Assessment (ISO 14040)
Damage categories (endpoint)	

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Impact categories (midpoint)	Climate change, ozone depletion, terrestrial acidification, freshwater eutrophication, marine eutrophication, human toxicity, photochemical oxidant formation, particulate matter formation, particulate matter formation, terrestrial ecotoxicity, freshwater ecotoxicity, marine ecotoxicity, ionizing radiation, agricultural land occupation, urban land occupation, natural land transformation, water depletion, mineral resource depletion, fossil resource depletion
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

PROteINSECT, project’s objective:

Global growth in population (forecast of 9 billion people by 2050) and increased welfare levels lead to fast increasing demand for high quality foods. Increased dependency on proteins imports for animal feed use puts the economic viability of the EU feedstock & livestock sector at risk - soybean meal (of which 70% of EU consumption is imported) prices increased over 100% over the 5 past years - fishmeal (of which 65% of EU consumption is imported) increased 4-fold.

On the other hand, insects are part of the staple diet of around 2,5 billion people in large areas of the world and an important part of the natural diet of widely consumed animals (e.g. trout, poultry). On average, insects can convert 2 kg of feed into 1 kg of insect mass, whereas cattle require 8 kg of feed to produce 1 kg of body weight gain. Therefore, insects can bear a great application potential, but success will largely depend on proven sustainability by means of LCSA in this case.

Block diagram:

Figure 1: Block diagram

Process flow diagrams:

Figure 2: Pretreated pig manure, manual harvest, dried insect product [HFdm] (Alicante, Spain), House fly.

Figure 3: Brewery waste, manual harvest, dried insect product [BSFmh] (Alicante, Spain). Black Soldier fly.

Figure 4: Brewery waste, semi-automated harvest, dried insect product [BSFah] (Alicante, Spain). Black Soldier Fly.

T2.1 Literature review – Plywood

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	B. Wilson, James, Eric T. Sakimoto, "Gate-to-gate life-cycle inventory of softwood plywood production" Wood and Fiber Science, Society of Wood Science and Technology, 37 Corrim Special Issue, 2005, pp. 58 – 73
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Life cycle inventory
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Softwood
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Plywood
Functional unit	One cubic meter of plywood
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Materials
Possible applications	Structural sheathing for roof, wall and flooring applications in home construction
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Allocation of environmental burdens based on the mass of product and co-products
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC and dLUC are not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	USA
Data quality	Data quality was high based upon comparisons between mills and regions, and on mass and heat balances. Inconsistent data were addressed by contacting mill personnel to resolve the issue.
Impact assessment method	
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Process Block diagram:

Figure 1: Unit process approach to the modeling of the plywood manufacturing process.

System boundaries:

Figure 2: System boundaries for both the cumulative and mill site for modeling the plywood manufacturing process

Life Cycle Inventory:

Table 1: Wood mass balance for production of a unit of plywood. All weights are reported on an oven-dry basis.

	PNW plywood		SE plywood	
	kg/m ³	lb/MSF	kg/m ³	lb/MSF
Inputs				
Logs without bark ¹	917	1,788	1,066	2,080
Purchased dry veneer	3.1	6	4.20	8.07
Purchased green veneer	7.2	14	5.30	10.40
Total	927	1,809	1,075	2,098
Outputs				
Plywood (wood only) ²	470	916	541	1,055
Wood chips	218	425	331	645
Peeler core	49	95	57	112
Green clippings	16	31	89	173
Veneer downfall	1.7	3.4	0	0
Panel trim	55	107	31	61
Sawdust	4.9	9.6	2.2	4.2
Wood waste to boiler	0.13	0.25	16	30
Sold wood waste	11	21	11	21
Sold dry veneer	32	63	0	0
Unaccounted wood ³	70	137	-1.4	-2.64
Total	927	1,809	1,075	2,098

¹ The weights are based on survey log volumes and the average species density of wood.

² Based on the weight of plywood minus the survey reported amount of resin.

³ Used to balance the input and output wood flow for mills.

Table 2: Gate-to-gate LCI inputs to produce a unit of plywood in the PNW.

Inputs	PNW plywood			
	SI unit	SI unit per m ³	Unit	Unit per MSF
Materials²				
Logs without bark	m ³	2.10E + 00	ft ³	6.56E + 01
	kg	9.17E + 02	lb	1.79E + 03
Phenol-formaldehyde resin	kg	8.15E + 00	lb	1.59E + 01
Extender and fillers ³	kg	4.56E + 00	lb	8.90E + 00
Catalyst ³	kg	5.69E - 01	lb	1.11E + 00
Soda ash ³	kg	1.69E - 01	lb	3.30E - 01
Bark	kg	5.07E + 01	lb	9.90E + 01
Purchased				
Dry veneer	kg	3.28E + 00	lb	6.40E + 00
Green veneer	kg	7.28E + 00	lb	1.42E + 01
Electrical use				
Electricity	MJ	5.65E + 02	kWh	1.39E + 02
Fuel use				
Wood fuel (produced) ⁴	kg	9.84E + 01	lb	1.92E + 02
Wood fuel (purchased)	kg	2.56E - 01	lb	5.00E - 01
Wood waste	kg	2.56E - 01	lb	5.00E - 01
Liquid petroleum gas	L	1.54E + 00	gal	3.59E - 01
Natural gas	m ³	5.22E + 00	ft ³	1.63E + 02
Diesel	L	1.69E + 00	gal	3.95E - 01
Water use				
Municipal water source	L	3.54E + 02	gal	8.28E + 01
Well-water source	L	1.26E + 02	gal	2.94E + 01
Recycled water source	L	1.28E + 00	gal	3.00E - 01

¹ Survey data for mill site collected in 2000.

² Materials and wood fuels are given on an oven-dry or solids weight basis.

³ These materials were not included in the LCI analysis based on the 2% exclusion rule.

⁴ Includes hogged bark and wood wastes produced within the system boundary; oven-dry weights.

Table 3: Mill survey data on air emissions from wood fuel fired boilers compared to FAL¹ boiler data.

Air emission	PNW		SE	
	Survey data kg/m ³	FAL data kg/m ³	Survey data kg/m ³	Fal data kg/m ³
Acetaldehyde	1.09E – 03	2.03E – 04	2.31E – 04	2.97E – 04
Acrolien	7.69E – 07	N/R ²	2.08E – 05	N/R
CO	2.45E + 00	9.23E – 01	2.50E + 00	1.35E + 00
CO ₂ (biomass) ³	1.93E + 02	1.43E + 02	3.29E + 02	2.08E + 02
Formaldehyde	2.36E – 03	4.46E – 04	7.28E – 04	6.51E – 04
Methanol	N/R	N/R	2.65E – 03	N/R
NOx	4.15E – 01	1.05E – 01	5.48E – 01	1.58E – 01
Particulates	2.76E – 01	1.15E – 02	2.11E – 01	1.69E – 02
Particulates (PM10)	2.23E – 01	N/R	8.82E – 02	N/R
Phenol	1.49E – 04	2.71E – 03	3.47E – 06	3.96E – 03
SO ₂	8.20E – 02	5.28E – 03	1.18E – 02	7.48E – 03
VOC	1.63E – 01	N/R	3.74E – 02	N/R

¹ Reference: SimaPro 5.0.009, PRé Consultants 2001; Franklin Associates (FAL) 2001.

² N/R = not reported.

³ The “survey” CO₂ was calculated from EPA Wood Waste Combustion in Boilers, AP-42, Section 1.6, EPA 1999.

Table 4: Mill survey data on air emissions from drying veneer during the production of plywood.

Air emission ¹	PNW veneer dryers		SE veneer dryers	
	kg/m ³	lb/MSF	kg/m ³	lb/MSF
Acetaldehyde	5.69E – 03	1.11E – 02	1.73E – 04	3.38E – 04
Acrolein	3.61E – 07	7.05E – 07	3.47E – 06	6.76E – 06
CO	7.69E – 02	1.50E – 01	6.25E – 02	1.22E – 01
CO ₂ (biomass) ²	5.02E + 00	9.80E + 00	0.00E + 00	0.00E + 00
CO ₂ (fossil)	1.38E + 00	2.71E + 00	1.05E + 01	2.04E + 01
Formaldehyde	1.15E – 02	2.24E – 02	1.39E – 04	2.71E – 04
Methanol	1.76E – 02	3.44E – 02	3.70E – 04	7.21E – 04
NOx	2.56E – 02	4.99E – 02	2.08E – 02	4.06E – 02
Particulates	1.62E – 01	3.16E – 01	3.77E – 02	7.35E – 02
Particulates (PM10)	1.44E – 01	2.81E – 01	1.07E – 02	2.09E – 02
Phenol	1.41E – 03	2.76E – 03	1.61E – 04	3.15E – 04
SO ₂	5.64E – 04	1.10E – 03	4.21E – 05	8.21E – 05
VOC	3.22E – 01	6.28E – 01	3.90E – 02	7.61E – 02

¹ Total air emissions as reported from surveys based on weighted production data.

² Biomass fuel consisting of bark and wood wastes; value calculated from EPA Plywood Manufacturing—Emission Factor Documentation, AP-42, Chapter 10, Table 10.5-2, 2001.

Table 5: Total air emissions for hot-pressing softwood plywood during production (EPA 2001).

Air emission ¹	PNW hot presses		SE hot presses	
	kg/m ³	lb/MSF	kg/m ³	lb/MSF
Acetaldehyde	2.15E – 03	4.19E – 03	2.15E – 03	4.20E – 03
Formaldehyde	9.74E – 04	1.90E – 03	9.74E – 04	1.90E – 03
Methanol	7.13E – 02	1.39E – 01	7.18E – 02	1.40E – 01
Particulates	6.15E – 02	1.20E – 01	9.12E – 02	1.78E – 01
Phenol	7.13E – 04	1.39E – 03	7.18E – 04	1.40E – 03
VOC	1.28E – 01	2.49E – 01	1.28E – 01	2.50E – 01

¹ Calculated from EPA Plywood Manufacturing, Emission Factor Documentation, AP-42, Chapter 10, Table 10.5-6, 2001.

Table 6: Fuel and electricity energy¹ use at the mill site; both unallocated and allocated to plywood on a mass basis.

	Unallocated energy use at mill				Allocated energy use at mill			
	PNW on-site energy		SE on-site energy		PNW on-site energy		SE on-site energy	
	MJ/m ³	Btu/MSF	MJ/m ³	Btu/MSF	MJ/m ³	Btu/MSF	MJ/m ³	Btu/MSF
Renewable fuel use								
Wood fuel (biomass)	2.25E + 03	1.89E + 06	3.22E + 03	2.07E + 06	1.40E + 03	1.18E + 03	1.99E + 03	1.67E + 06
Non-renewable fuel use								
Liquid petroleum gas	4.09E + 01	3.43E + 04	4.78E + 01	4.01E + 04	2.02E + 01	1.70E + 04	3.51E + 01	2.95E + 04
Natural gas	2.00E + 02	1.68E + 05	2.97E + 02	2.49E + 05	1.50E + 02	1.26E + 05	2.77E + 02	2.32E + 05
Diesel	6.54E + 01	5.49E + 04	4.47E + 01	3.75E + 04	3.40E + 01	2.85E + 04	2.29E + 01	1.92E + 04
Electricity use								
Electricity	5.65E + 02	4.74E + 05	4.96E + 02	4.16E + 05	3.81E + 02	3.20E + 05	3.86E + 02	3.24E + 05
Total	3.12E + 03	2.62E + 06	4.11E + 03	3.45E + 06	1.99E + 03	1.67E + 06	2.71E + 03	2.27E + 06

¹ Energy values were determined for the fuels using their higher heating values (HHV) in units of MJ/kg as follows: liquid petroleum gas 54.0, natural gas 54.4, diesel 44.0, and wood oven-dry 20.9. Electricity was calculated at 3.6 MJ/kWh.

Table 7: Fuel and electricity energy¹ cumulative use considering both site and off-site energies allocated to plywood on a mass basis.

	Allocated cumulative energy use			
	PNW energy		SE on-site energy	
	MJ/m ³	Btu/MSF	MJ/m ³	Btu/MSF
Renewable fuel use				
Wood fuel (biomass)	1.55E + 03	1.30E + 06	2.29E + 03	1.92E + 06
Non-renewable fuel use				
Coal	1.30E + 02	1.09E + 05	7.39E + 02	6.20E + 05
Crude oil	2.69E + 02	2.26E + 05	4.58E + 02	3.84E + 05
Natural gas	8.76E + 02	7.35E + 05	1.49E + 03	1.25E + 04
Uranium	9.83E + 00	8.25E + 03	5.46E + 01	4.58E + 04
Electricity				
Energy from hydro power	3.07E + 02	2.58E + 05	7.92E + 00	6.65E + 03
Energy from other sources	4.56E + 00	3.82E + 03	1.53E + 01	1.28E + 04
Total	3.14E + 03	2.64E + 06	5.06E + 03	4.24E + 06

¹ Energy values were determined for the fuels using their higher heating values (HHV) in units of MJ/kg as follows: coal 26.2, crude oil 45.5, natural gas 54.4, and wood oven-dry 20.9. Uranium was calculated at 381,000 MJ/kg and electricity at 3.6 MJ/kWh.

Table 8: Life-cycle inventory results for production of plywood in the PNW region, gives both allocated site and cumulative emissions to air, water, and land

Substance	Allocated cumulative		Allocated site	
	kg/m ³	lb/MSF	kg/m ³	lb/MSF
Emissions to air				
Acetaldehyde	6.10E - 03	1.19E - 02	6.10E - 03	1.19E - 02
Acrolein	4.49E - 07	8.75E - 07	2.71E - 07	5.28E - 07
CO	1.07E + 00	2.08E + 00	9.94E - 01	1.94E + 00
CO ₂ (biomass)	1.46E + 02	2.85E + 02	1.46E + 02	2.85E + 02
CO ₂ (fossil)	3.99E + 01	7.78E + 01	6.15E + 00	1.20E + 01
Formaldehyde	1.92E - 02	3.74E - 02	1.06E - 02	2.06E + 02
Methane	1.09E - 01	2.13E - 01	3.65E - 05	7.13E - 05
Methanol	6.97E - 02	1.36E - 01	6.97E - 02	1.36E - 01
NO _x	3.33E - 01	6.50E - 01	1.94E - 01	3.79E - 01
Particulates	1.95E - 01	3.81E - 01	1.92E - 01	3.75E - 01
Particulates (PM10)	1.16E - 01	2.27E - 01	1.14E - 01	2.22E - 01
Particulates (unspecified)	1.29E - 02	2.52E - 02	—	—
Phenol	1.55E - 02	3.02E - 02	4.33E - 03	8.44E - 03
SO _x	5.43E - 01	1.06E + 00	9.23E - 03	1.80E - 02
VOC	3.43E - 01	6.69E - 01	3.43E - 01	6.69E - 01
Emissions to water				
BOD	7.38E - 04	1.44E - 03	2.92E - 06	5.69E - 06
Cl-	3.20E - 02	6.24E - 02	—	—
COD	8.56E - 03	1.67E - 02	2.50E - 04	4.88E - 04
Dissolved solids	7.07E - 01	1.38E + 00	4.90E - 04	9.56E - 04
Oil	1.26E - 02	2.45E - 02	—	—
Suspended solids	1.68E - 02	3.27E - 02	5.23E - 04	1.02E - 03
Emissions to land				
Solid waste	9.46E + 00	1.88E + 01	6.10E + 00	1.19E + 01

T2.1 Literature review – Polylactide-based wood plastic composites toughened with polyhydroxyalkanoates

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Qiang, Tao, Demei Yu, Anjiang Zhang, Honghong Gao, Zhao Li, Zengchao Liu, Weixing Chen, and Zhen Han, "Life Cycle Assessment On Polylactide-Based Wood Plastic Composites Toughened With Polyhydroxyalkanoates", <i>Journal Of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 66, 2014, pp. 139-145.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Pine and corn
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Wood plastic composite (WPC) containing PLA and PHA for toughening
Functional unit	1000 kg of transport pallet manufactured with the PLA-based WPC.
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Materials
Possible applications	Material for building, construction, and automotives
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Allocation procedure is not mentioned
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC and dLUC are not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	High-tech Zone, Xi'an, Shaanxi
Data quality	Literature data
Impact assessment method	Attribute hierarchy model (AHM)
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming potential, acidification potential, photochemical oxidation

Other information or comments

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

System boundaries:

Figure 1: System boundary of life cycle assessment for the PLA-based WPC.

Life cycle inventory of emissions:

Table 1: Life cycle inventory of pollutant emissions from 1000 kg of the PLA-based WPC.

Process	Waste gases/kg									Water requirement/kg	Solid waste/kg	Inventory data source
	CO ₂	CO	CH ₄	N ₂ O	NO _x	VOC	PM	SO _x	NH ₃			
① + ② + ③	426.157	0.989	1.1007	0.0251	6.0998	3.072	1.368	4.720	0.00981	4.14	64.8	Ref (Bergman and Bowe, 2008; Magelli and Bi, 2007; natural gas was used as fuel).
④	68.039	0.274	0.00262	0.00042	1.073	0.0664	0.04215	0.06039	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	Ref (Magelli and Bi, 2007; Xiong et al., 2008)
⑤	-156.527	5.778	13.848	0.365	7.727	0.00024	0.0149	2.465	0.00492	69021 ^a	42	Ref (Vink et al., 2007)
⑥	47.887	0.193	0.00184	0.0003	0.755	0.0467	0.02967	0.0425	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	Same as ④
⑦	490	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	Ref (Yu and Chen, 2008)
⑧	47.887	0.193	0.00184	0.0003	0.755	0.0467	0.02967	0.0425	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	Same as ④
⑨	3568.394	4.639	6.746	0.187	29.652	n.a.	2.982	13.849	0.96	53.585	0.129	Ref (Corbière-Nicollier et al., 2001; China reed pallet; Joshi et al., 2004)

Note: Values of steps ① to ⑨ in Table 3 are inputs and outputs from the acquisition and transportation of 1000 kg of the raw materials. n.a.: not available. a: 0.0119831 kg of phosphate.

System description:

Pine wood (Dahurian larch), Greater Khingan, Heilongjiang, was harvested and dried near the forests. The dried planks were milled into WF, which was transported from Greater Khingan to Xi'an, Shaanxi. PLA and PHAs were purchased from BrightChina Industrial Co., Ltd. Shenzhen and Ecoman Biotechnology Co., Ltd. Shenzhen, Guangdong, respectively, and transported to Xi'an. The PLA-based WPC were manufactured through extrusion blending followed by injection molding. The content of WF (filler) and PLA (matrix) for the untoughened PLA-based WPC (Sample A) is 20 wt% and 80 wt %, respectively. The PLA-based WPC toughened with PHAs (Sample B), in which the content of WF, PLA and PHAs is 20 wt%, 55 wt% and 25 wt%, respectively.

T2.1 Literature review – Agglomerated cork as thermal insulation

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Sierra-Pérez, Jorge, Jesús Boschmonart-Rives, Ana C. Dias, and Xavier Gabarrell, "Environmental Implications Of The Use Of Agglomerated Cork As Thermal Insulation In Buildings", Journal Of Cleaner Production, Vol. 126, 2016, pp. 97-107.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Forestry cork wastes
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Cork insulation board
Functional unit	The mass (kg) of insulation board with an area of 1m ² that provides a thermal resistance R-value of 1 m ² K/W
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Materials
Possible applications	Insulation material
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Mass allocation basis in the raw material extraction stage.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC and dLUC are not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	Cataluña, Spain
Data quality	Literature, Ecoinvent 3.1 database, consultations and visits to the factory.
Impact assessment method	Hierarchical approach of CML 2002
Damage categories (endpoint)	

Impact categories (midpoint)	Abiotic depletion potential for non-fossil resources, abiotic depletion potential for fossil resources, acidification potential, eutrophication potential, global warming potential, ozone layer depletion potential, photochemical oxidation potential, embodied energy, cumulative energy demand.
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Life cycle diagram and system boundaries:

Figure 1: Diagram of the cork insulation board life cycle based on EN 15408. The study includes A1, A2 and A3 stages.

Life cycle inventory:

Table 1: Inventory data to produce the FU of cork insulation boards ($R= 1 \text{ m}^2 \text{ K/W}$).

Inputs	Unit	Quantity	Ecoinvent process
A1 – Raw materials extraction			
<i>Materials</i>			
Water	m ³	3.62E-03	tap water production, conventional treatment, Europe without Switzerland
Fungicide (Thiophanate-methyl 45%)	kg	3.03E-03	[thio]carbamate-compound production, RER
<i>Transport</i>			
Workers to stripping	km	1.71E+00	transport, passenger car, large size, diesel, EURO 3, RER
Workers to scratching	km	5.01E-01	transport, passenger car, large size, diesel, EURO 3, RER
Cork to meeting point	km	5.32E+01	transport, tractor and trailer, agricultural, CH
Distribution of auxiliary materials	km	1.00E+02	transport, freight, light commercial vehicle, Europe without Switzerland
Workers to shrub clearance and road maintenance	km	8.63E-01	transport, passenger car, large size, diesel, EURO 3, RER
Forestry tractor	km	1.00E+00	transport, tractor and trailer, agricultural, CH
A2 – Transport to the manufacturer			
From the forest	km	2.40E+02	transport, freight, lorry 16–32 metric ton, EURO3, RER
A3 – Manufacturing			
A3.1 – Granulate manufacture			
Diesel for internal displacements	MJ	7.63E+00	diesel, burned in building machine, GLO
Electricity	kWh	4.40E+00	market for electricity, medium voltage, ES
A3.2 – Board manufacture			
Electricity	kWh	1.45E+00	market for electricity, medium voltage, ES
Diesel boiler	MJ	4.24E+01	heat production, light fuel oil, at boiler 10 kW, non-modulating, Europe without Switzerland
Polyurethane (PU)	kg	1.68E-01	polyurethane production, flexible foam, RER
Transport (PU)	km	2.00E+01	transport, freight, light commercial vehicle, Europe without Switzerland
HPDE	kg	4.55E-02	polyethylene production, high density, granulate, RER

System description:

The system considered in this study begins with the extraction of raw cork, considering only operations related to this process. In assessing the extraction, the workers and cork transports within the forest are included, because most operations in this process are entirely manual. Moreover, there are some complementary activities during the period between each stripping that are necessary to facilitate future cork extractions: the scratching stage, the fungicide operation and the shrub clearance and road maintenance. As the raw cork material currently being extracted is the result of the last few decades, it is assumed that similar technology will be used to generate current and future cork.

The next stage is the transport of the cork from the forest to the factory. In this case, 80% of the raw materials are local and the remaining 20% comes from Extremadura, a southwestern region of Spain. All transport to the factory is by road.

The final stage is manufacturing and includes two main substages: cork granulates manufacturing and board manufacturing. The initial materials extracted from the forest are the forestry cork wastes, which do not require that preparation processes be included in the production process. First, the raw cork is received and transferred to the cork trituration process. This operation consists of breaking up the pieces of raw cork into small particles using two types of trituration machines.

Then, granulates are classified using densimetric tables that separate the different granulates by density classes. This makes it possible to sort out the heavier particles, which are reprocessed. Moreover, fine particles with dimensions below 0.25 mm are removed as dust throughout the process and may be used as an energy source. This dust represents approximately 50% of the initial raw cork. Granulates of different sizes are stored in silos and are supplied to a dispenser where the agglomeration process involves the blending of the cork with polyurethane. The mixture is placed on a conveyor and is pressed by applying a high temperature; it can then be cut into boards of the desired dimensions. A diesel boiler produces the required heat energy. The wastes generated are introduced again in the agglomeration process and will be used in manufacturing subsequent boards. After the cutting process, the boards are given time for cooling and stabilization. Finally, the boards are packed using polyethylene film and stored until their distribution.

T2.1 Literature review – Amino Acids

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Marinussen and Kool. “Environmental impacts of synthetic amino acid production”, report from Blonk Milieu Advies BV, 2010 Netherlands
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Wheat
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Amino acids (L-lysine, DL-methionine, L-threonine)
Functional unit	1000 kg synthetic produced amino acid (Lysine.HCl, Threonine 98% pure crystalline threonine containing 2% water and 100% D, L-methionine)
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
Possible applications	Animal feed (use of a protease to improve the nutritional value of feed for broilers)
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Allocation rules as recommended in the Dutch horticulture protocol for carbon footprinting (Blonk, 2009)
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC and dLUC are not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	Europe (Germany, Denmark and France)
Data quality	Consultancy, literature and internet (The data represent a best estimate of an average commercial scale of operation in Europe. The level of technology can be considered state of the art). For background data: Ecoinvent database (Ecoinvent 2010)

Blonk, H., A. Kool, B. Luske, T. Ponsioen & J. Scholten. “Berekening van broeikasgasemissies door productie van tuinbouwproducten”. *Blonk Milieudvies*. 2009.

Impact assessment method	ReCiPe 2008 (Goedkoop, 2009)
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Climate change, fossil consumption, acidification, eutrophication, photochemical smog formation, land use
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Process flow diagram:

Figure 1: Flow diagram of the production of Lysine and Threonine

L-lysine and L-threonine are produced by a bio-synthetic process where micro-organisms produce the amino acids using glucose as a carbon source (L-lysine and L-threonine are produced with a C-yield of resp. 40% and 35%) and corn steep liquor (CSL) as a source for vitamins and amino acids. Ammonium sulphate is mainly used as source for nitrogen. Raw materials for glucose are corn, wheat, cane molasses or beet molasses. CSL is a co-product of processing corn into starch, corn oil, gluten and sweeteners.

Regarding the considered life cycle stages, the system studies the cradle to gate production of the amino acids. In the life cycle assessment capital goods and office services were excluded. Components used in minor quantities, for the production of L-lysine and L-threonine, such as vitamins, amino acids, salts, antibiotics, and nitric acid for cleaning are excluded from the inventory because the expected share to the impact is very small relative to the effort to inventory the impacts. The disposal of waste water with diluted organic material is also excluded from the inventory because the impact is expected to be very small.

Inventory tables:

Table 1: Raw materials used for production of 1000 kg L-Lysine

Raw material	unit	Used/ton Lysine ¹
Glucose syrup (as DE98, 70% dry matter)	kg	3500
Corn Steep Liquor (CSL 48%)	kg	300
Ammonia	Kg	155
Ammonium Sulphate	Kg	95
Sulphuric Acid (96%)	kg	320
Phosphoric Acid, 85 % w/w	kg	25
Vitamins, amino acids	kg	4
Salts (like Mg, citric acid, Mn, Fe)	kg	5
Antifoam	liter	10
Process water (fermentation/cleaning)	M3	4.6
Caustic (as 46%) for cleaning	kg	4.5
Nitric acid, 67% for cleaning	kg	1.5

¹ as Lysine.HCL

Table 2: Utilities used for production of 1000 kg L-Lysine

Energy source	unit	Used/ton Lysine ¹
Steam fermentation	ton	1.6
Steam evaporation	ton	0.7
Steam evaporation and drying	ton	3.5
Electricity fermentation (incl. cooling/aeration)	kWh	3750
Electricity evaporation and drying	kWh	185
Water for cooling fermentation	M3	7
Water for cooling evaporation	M3	61
Effluent (waste water; low BOD)	M3	4
Total steam consumption	ton	5.8
Total electricity consumption	kWh	3935
Total water consumption	M3	72

¹ as Lysine.HCL

Table 3: Raw materials used for production of 1000 kg L-Threonine

Raw material	unit	Used/ton Threonine
Glucose (100% glucose)	kg	3000
Corn Steep Liquor (CSL 48%)	kg	1000
Ammonia	Kg	700
Sulphuric Acid (96%)	kg	1500
Vitamins, amino acids, salts, antibiotics	kg	5
H3PO4	kg	4
46% Caustic (NaOH) for CIP	kg	200
Down stream processing:		
water	M3	120
Cleaning chemicals	kg	250
resins	liter	300

Table 4: Utilities used for production of 1000 kg L-Threonine

Energy source	unit	Used/ton Threonine
Steam (fermentation, evaporation and drying)	ton	20
Electricity	kWh	12000
Water	M3	9
Downstream utilities (electricity)	kWh	50

Table 5: Raw materials used for production of 1000 kg Methionine

Raw material	unit	Used/ton Methionine
Acrylic acid	kg	376
Methanol	kg	228
Hydrogen Sulfide (H ₂ S)	kg	215
Hydrogen Cyanide	kg	181
Ammonium Carbonaat	kg	1611
Energy source:		
Natural gas	GJ	16

T2.1 Literature review – β -Galactosidase

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Feijoo, S., S. González-García, J.M. Lema, and M.T. Moreira, "Life Cycle Assessment Of B-Galactosidase Enzyme Production", Journal Of Cleaner Production, Vol. 165, 2017, pp. 204-212.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Cheese whey
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	β -Galactosidase
Functional unit	1 kg of β -Galactosidase enzyme
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Offering alternatives to lactose intolerant consumers, favor intestinal bacterial microflora (galactooligosaccharides produced through lactose hydrolysis), produce high sweetness syrups, more efficient fermentation (reduce time to obtain products such as cottage cheese and yogurt)
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC and dLUC are not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	
Data quality	Simulation of a full-scale plant based on microbial kinetics experiments. Bibliographic sources. Ecoinvent database.
Impact assessment method	LCA methodology was performed by applying the ReCiPe midpoint method.
Damage categories (endpoint)	

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Impact categories (midpoint)

Climate change, ozone depletion, terrestrial acidification, freshwater eutrophication, marine eutrophication, human toxicity, photochemical oxidant formation, terrestrial ecotoxicity, freshwater ecotoxicity, marine ecotoxicity, water depletion, fossil depletion.

Other information or comments
2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Industrial facility flow diagram and system boundaries:

Figure 1: System boundaries of the production of the β -Galactosidase enzyme.

The description of the facility under analysis includes the following sections: i) a storage area where primary and secondary raw materials are discharged and warehoused in tanks or silos; ii) a fermentation section that contains the heat sterilizer for the feed, the seed fermenter for the production of the inoculum and the production fermenter, and iii) a number of downstream stages to recover the β -Galactosidase enzyme, such as microfilters, homogenizers, centrifuges and a dead-end polishing filter, and a purification section, in which ultrafilters, an ion-exchange column, a diafilter and a freeze dryer produce a refined powdered product before packaging. The enzymes production system (foreground system) has been split into two main subsystems as displayed in Figure 1.

- Subsystem 1 (SS1) includes activities related to the formulation of the culture medium and fermentation (storage, preparation of culture medium and fermentation sections)
- Subsystem 2 (SS2) involves downstream activities (separation and purification sections).

Cleaning-in-place (CIP) units have been considered as ancillary activities within SS2. These operations are required to clean process equipment without dismantling it. They are required after the use of a piece of material to prepare it for the next batch. Regarding further activities involved in the liquid and solid wastes management, they have been included within the system boundaries as ancillary stages. Liquid waste is sent to a wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) and solid waste to sanitary landfill, both located in surroundings. Finally, background system includes background processes related to the production of the different inputs to the foreground system such as electricity, chemicals, natural gas and tap water.

T2.1 Literature review – Bioactive compounds

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Pérez-López, Paula, Sara González-García, R. Gabriela Ulloa, Jorge Sineiro, Gumersindo Feijoo, and M ^a Teresa Moreira, "Life Cycle Assessment Of The Production Of Bioactive Compounds From Tetraselmis Suecica At Pilot Scale", <i>Journal Of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 64, 2014, pp. 323-331.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Microalgae <i>Tetraselmis suecica</i>
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Bioactive compounds: lipids (45%% PUFAs), a-tocopherol, chlorophyll, β-carotenoid. Co-products: fertilizers, electricity
Functional unit	1 kg of <i>T. suecica</i>
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Bioactive compounds
Possible applications	Polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs): potential applications in pharmaceutical, nutraceutical and cosmetics industries. They are metabolically active and considered essential since the human body cannot synthesize them itself. Pigments: food and feed additives, dyes for culinary applications in the food and fabric sector, precursors in green chemistry.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	The results of the assessment are presented per kg of product, taking into account, therefore, a mass allocation approach
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC and dLUC are not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	
Data quality	Primary data from pilot plant, field data, interviews with workers, research reports and literature
Impact assessment method	CML 2 baseline 2001 V2.04 method for the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA)

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Abiotic depletion potential, acidification potential, eutrophication potential, global warming potential over a 100-year timeframe, ozone layer depletion potential, photochemical oxidants formation potential, cumulative non-renewable fossil and nuclear energy demand.
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Process value chain and system boundaries:

Figure 1: Process chain and system boundaries overview. The box in dark gray is out of the system boundaries.

The main process of study (foreground system) is the production of *T. suecica* at pilot scale, performed in an indoor photobioreactor (PBR), consisting on a vertical bubble column. Following a biorefinery perspective of the production system, the anaerobic digestion of the algal residual paste obtained after the extraction step was also included. Accordingly, the life cycle was divided in five main stages:

- sterilization: the photobioreactor was chemically sterilized with sodium hypochlorite. Later, a flow of air was supplied to neutralize residual chlorine. Then, the reactor was washed twice with sterile distilled water.
- inoculation and culturing: The inoculum was grown indoors under artificial light in an 8L photobioreactor. The reactor was inoculated with biomass in a semi-continuous culture.

iii) harvesting: cultures were kept in a semi-continuous regime for 60 days. After that, algal biomass was collected by centrifugation; frozen biomass of *T. suecica* for biochemical analysis while freeze dried biomass was processed for trace elements and antioxidant analysis.

iv) extraction: three different solvents were considered in three different extraction steps. After each extractive process, the algal paste was centrifuged for 5 min with an average harvesting efficiency of 90%. Solvents were recovered using a rotary evaporator and recycled to the system. First, the lipid fraction (including 45% PUFAs) was extracted, from the lyophilized algal paste using hexane. Then the centrifuged algal paste was washed with ethanol. Later, a fraction including the compounds: a-tocopherol, chlorophyll and b-carotenoid, was extracted using a solution of methanol and KOH. Finally, polyphenols were extracted from the remaining centrifuged algal paste with a methanol based aqueous solution.

v) anaerobic digestion: algal residual paste was obtained after the extraction process. The anaerobic digestion of this stream was simulated as base scenario. The heat requirement in the anaerobic digestion was provided by the biogas produced in the reactor.

Life cycle inventory:

Table 1: Global inventory for the production of bioactive compounds by *T. suecica* at pilot scale (functional unit: 1 kg algal biomass).

Inputs from technosphere			
Materials		Energy	
Filtered seawater	1269 L	Electricity from grid	68.7 kWh
Distilled water	129 L		
Tap water	129 L		
Inoculum	0.80 g		
CO ₂ (aeration)	4.48 kg		
NaNO ₃ ^a	431.5 g		
NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·2H ₂ O ^a	39.6 g		
Na ₂ C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₈ ·2H ₂ O ^a	24.9 g		
CuSO ₄ ^a	0.04 g	<i>Transport</i>	
NaMoO ₄ ^a	0.52 g	Truck 3.5–7.5 t (nutrients)	0.05 t km
ZnCl ₂ ^a	0.35 g	Truck 3.5–7.5 t (solvents)	0.29 t km
MnCl ₂ ^a	0.32 g	Truck 3.5–7.5 t (washing agents)	0.04 t km
C ₁₂ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ OS·HCl ^a	0.09 g	Truck 3.5–7.5 t (equipment)	0.08 t km
C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃ S ^a	0.03 g	Truck 3.5–7.5 t (wastes)	0.02 t km
C ₆₃ H ₈₈ CoN ₁₄ O ₁₄ P ^a	0.01 g	Truck 3.5–7.5 t (seawater)	50.8 t km
CoCl ₃ ^a	0.04 g	Oceanic tanker (seawater)	50.8 t km
C ₆ H ₅ FeO ₇ ^a	12.4 g		
Hexane ^b	22.21 g		
HDPE ^c	3.44 g		
Lamps ^c	6.10 g		
Methacrylate ^c	0.19 kg		
Stainless steel ^c	0.39 kg		
Stainless steel ^d	0.22 kg		
Lamps ^d	0.82 g		
Polyvinyl chloride (PVC) ^d	1.00 g		
Polyamide ^d	5.50 g		
Sodium hypochlorite ^e	0.32 L		
Sodium hydrosulfite ^e	6.45 g		
Outputs to technosphere			
Main products		Waste to sanitary landfill	
α-tocopherol	69.7 mg	Polyamide	5.50 g
Polyphenols	3.76 g	Methacrylate	0.19 kg
β-carotenoid	3.21 g	Polyvinyl chloride	1.00 g
Chlorophyll	8.76 g	<i>Waste to inert landfill</i>	
Lipids (45% PUFAs)	164 g (73.9 g)	Steel	0.61 kg
<i>Co-product</i>		<i>Waste to municipal incineration</i>	
Algal residual paste	820 g	HDPE	3.44 g
		<i>Waste to specific treatment</i>	
		Lamps (electronic wastes)	6.92 g
Outputs to environment			
<i>Water emissions</i>			
Wastewater	1527 L		
NaNO ₃	58.2 g	C ₆₃ H ₈₈ CoN ₁₄ O ₁₄ P	1.03 mg
NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	5.34 g	CoCl ₃	5.66 mg
Na ₂ C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₈ ·2H ₂ O	45.57 g	C ₆ H ₅ FeO ₇	1.7 g
CuSO ₄	74.0 mg	Hexane	1.64 mL
NaMoO ₄	0.07 g	Methanol	0.22 L
ZnCl ₂	0.05 g	KOH	3.34 g
MnCl ₂	0.04 g	Ethanol	0.20 L
C ₁₂ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ OS·HCl ^a	0.01 g	Sodium hypochlorite	0.32 L
C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃ S	3.43 mg	Sodium hydrosulfite	6.45 g

^a Nutrients.

^b Solvent.

^c Inoculation and culturing step related materials.

^d General materials.

^e Cleaning agents.

Table 2: Transport activities related with the microalgae pilot plant.

Materials	Transport mode	Capacity (t)	Average distance (km)
Nutrients	Diesel lorry	3.5–7.5	100
Solvents	Diesel lorry	3.5–7.5	1140
Equipment materials	Diesel lorry	3.5–7.5	100
Washing agents	Diesel lorry	3.5–7.5	100
Seawater	Diesel lorry	3.5–7.5	40
Seawater	Transoceanic tanker	3.5–7.5	40
Wastes to treatment	Diesel lorry	3.5–7.5	50

Table 3: Energy and mass flows associated with the production of biogas from algal residual paste.

Inputs	
<i>Settling</i>	
Electricity (pumping)	361 kJ
<i>Centrifugation</i>	
Electricity (injecting algae in the digester)	99 kJ
<i>Anaerobic digestion</i>	
Electricity (mixing the digesters)	255 kJ
Heat (from produced biogas)	1606 kJ
<i>Upgrading</i>	
Electricity	771 kJ
Water	44 L
Outputs	
Biogas	4444 kJ (0.131 m ³)
Water with CO ₂	44 L
<i>Avoided products</i>	
Ammonium nitrate	57.8 g N
Triple superphosphate	17.9 g P ₂ O ₅
Potassium sulphate	7.7 g K ₂ O

T2.1 Literature review – Astaxanthin

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Pérez-López, P., S. González-García, C. Jeffryes, S.N. Agathos, E. McHugh, D. Walsh, P. Murray, S. Moane, G. Feijoo, and M.T. Moreira, "Life Cycle Assessment Of The Production Of The Red Antioxidant Carotenoid Astaxanthin By Microalgae: From Lab To Pilot Scale", <i>Journal Of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 64, 2014, pp. 332-344.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Microalgae (<i>Haematococcus pluvialis</i>), fish oil (byproduct of fisheries).
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Astaxanthin (high-value red carotenoid pigment). Fertilizer (by-product)
Functional unit	1 g of astaxanthin (lab-scale production), 800 g of astaxanthin (pilot-scale process)
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Carotenoids
Possible applications	Additive in food and feed industries, nutraceuticals to cosmetics market, medical sector (anti-inflammatory and anti-cancer)
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (<i>to be detailed in the report section</i>) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	All the environmental burdens were allocated to the amount of astaxanthin produced.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC and dLUC are not mentioned.
Geographic location, if defined	Belgium, Ireland
Data quality	Lab and pilot-scale on site measurements. Ecoinvent database. Bibliographic sources.
Impact assessment method	The characterisation factors reported by the Center of Environmental Science of Leiden University (CML 2001 method) were used. The software SimaPro 7.3 was

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

	usec for the computational implementation of the inventories.
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Abiotic depletion, acidification, eutrophication, global warming, ozone layer depletion, human toxicity, freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity, marine aquatic ecotoxicity, terrestrial ecotoxicity, photochemical oxidants formation.
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

System boundaries and flow diagram:

The system to produce astaxanthin from *H. pluvialis* is divided into five stages, which are described below: i) Cleaning of the reactor, ii) Preparation of the culture medium, iii) Cultivation of the microalga, iv) Harvesting and v) Extraction of the astaxanthin.

Figure 1: System boundaries and process chain of the lab-scale case study: production of astaxanthin from *Haematococcus pluvialis* in a 15 L tubular airlift photobioreactor.

Figure 2: System boundaries and process chain of the pilot-scale case study: production of astaxanthin from *Haematococcus pluvialis* in a two-stage process with 1000 L internally illuminated airlift photobioreactors in series.

Inventory tables:

Table 1: Global inventory for the lab-scale production of astaxanthin from *Haematococcus pluvialis* in a 15 L tubular airlift photobioreactor (functional unit: 1 g astaxanthin).

Inputs from technosphere			
Materials		Materials	
Cleaning of the reactor		Extraction	
Deionised water	28.27 L	Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO)	2.63 L
Tap water	47.11 L	Stainless steel	0.31 g
Sodium hypochlorite (NaClO)	18.84 g	Cast metal	0.94 g
Stainless steel	4.70 g	Galvanised steel	8.16 g
Preparation of the culture medium		Anodised aluminium	0.22 g
Deionised water	14.13 L	Polycarbonate	211.05 g
NaNO ₃	10.571 g	Energy	
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	0.352 g	Cleaning of the reactor	
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	1.057 g	Autoclaving	1.11 kWh
NaCl	0.352 g	Preparation of the culture medium	
K ₂ HPO ₄ ·3H ₂ O	1.057 g	Autoclaving	0.78 kWh
KH ₂ PO ₄	2.466 g	Addition of inoculum in laminar flow hood	0.19 kWh
C ₁₂ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ OS·HCl	0.0169 g	Cultivation	
C ₆₃ H ₈₈ CoN ₁₄ O ₁₄ P	0.0001 g	Incubation (excluding lights)	40.70 kWh
C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ Na ₂ O ₈ ·2H ₂ O	0.0634 g	Lighting in incubation stage	9.50 kWh
FeCl ₃	0.0049 g	Lighting in the photobioreactor	68.38 kWh
MnCl ₂	0.0035 g	Air blowing	3.73 kWh
ZnCl ₂	0.0004 g	Harvesting	
CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	0.0002 g	Centrifugation	10.99 kWh
Na ₂ MoO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	0.0003 g	Freezer	5.65 kWh
Stainless steel	26.14 g	Freeze-drying	2.26 kWh
Polystyrene (PS)	3.37 kg	Extraction	
High density polyethylene (HDPE)	124.37 g	Heating of the solvent	0.39 kWh
Polyethylene terephthalate (PET)	0.96 g	Vortex mixing	0.05 kWh
Cultivation		Centrifugation	1.28 kWh
Compressed air (enriched 0.5% CO ₂)	67.91 kg	Transport	
Fluorescent lamps (15 W)	3.04 g	Truck, 3.5–7.5 t, Euro 4 (Chemicals)	2.344 tkm
Polyurethane foam	34.26 g	Truck, 3.5–7.5 t, Euro 4 (Materials)	3.134 tkm
Galvanised steel	79.94 g	Truck, 3.5–7.5 t, Euro 4 (Waste)	0.261 tkm
Gro-lux fluorescent tubes (36 W)	16.15 g		
Polyvinyl chloride (PVC)	40.47 g		
Harvesting			
Distilled water	4.71 L		
Polypropylene (PP)	819.72 g		
Galvanised steel	32.96 g		
Anodised aluminium	0.85 g		
Polycarbonate	422.11 g		
Polyurethane foam	3.00 g		
Stainless steel	20.70 g		
Inputs from environment			
Materials		Outputs to environment	
Biomass	0.424 g	Air emissions	
Outputs to technosphere		Air (excluding CO ₂)	
Product		CO ₂	
<i>Haematococcus</i> astaxanthin	1 g	Water emissions	
Avoided product ^a		Water effluent	
Nitrogen-rich fertiliser	0.573 g	NaClO	
Phosphorous-rich fertiliser	0.375 g	NaNO ₃	
Waste treatment		CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	
Steel, to inert landfill	173.847 g	MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	
Polystyrene, to sanitary landfill	3.373 kg	NaCl	
Polyethylene, to sanitary landfill	124.371 g	K ₂ HPO ₄ ·3H ₂ O	
Polyethylene terephthalate	0.964 g	KH ₂ PO ₄	
Fluorescent lamps, to specific treatment for electronics wastes	19.185 g	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ OS·HCl	
		C ₆₃ H ₈₈ CoN ₁₄ O ₁₄ P	
		C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ Na ₂ O ₈ ·2H ₂ O	
		FeCl ₃	
		MnCl ₂	
		ZnCl ₂	
		CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	
		Na ₂ MoO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	
		DMSO	
		6316.6316 L	

^a N and P fertiliser dosage is equivalent to 27.266 g of residual biomass.

Table 2: Global inventory for the production of astaxanthin from Haematococcus pluvialis in a two stage process with 1000 L stirred-tank photobioreactors in series (functional unit: 800 g carotenoid).

Inputs from technosphere			
Materials		Materials	
Cleaning of the reactor		Extraction	
OPTION 1		Drying agent (pelletised diatomaceous earth) 35.46 kg	
Tap water	4.009 m ³	Co-solvent (fish/vegetable oil)	4.67 kg
NaClO	4.009 kg	Stainless steel	0.55 kg
OPTION 2		Energy	
Stainless steel	0.200 kg	Cleaning of the reactor (OPTION 2)	
Preparation of the culture medium		Reactor sterilisation with ozonised water 0.12 kWh	
NaNO ₃	4.4651 kg	Preparation of the culture medium	
K ₂ HPO ₄	0.9121 kg	Reverse osmosis filtration 7.71 kWh	
KH ₂ PO ₄	0.4041 kg	UV filtration 0.35 kWh	
CaCl ₂	0.2914 kg	Cultivation	
MgSO ₄	1.3473 kg	Lighting in the photobioreactor 1539.43 kWh	
NaCl	0.1194 kg	Air blowing 96.21 kWh	
C ₆ H ₈ O ₇	0.0287 kg	Agitation 96.21 kWh	
C ₆ H _{5-4y} Fe _x N _y O ₇	0.0287 kg	Harvesting	
Na ₂ CO ₃	0.4778 kg	Centrifugation 1.50 kWh	
C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₈	0.0263 kg	Spray drying 82.70 kWh	
H ₃ BO ₃	0.0137 kg	Extraction	
ZnSO ₄	0.0011 kg	Supercritical CO ₂ extraction 158.25 kWh	
CuSO ₄	0.0004 kg	Transport	
Co(NO ₃) ₂	0.0002 kg	OPTION 1	
FeCl ₃	0.0028 kg	Truck, 3.5–7.5 t, Euro 4 (Chemicals) 41.87 tkm	
ZnCl ₂	0.0001 kg	Truck, 3.5–7.5 t, Euro 4 (Materials) 8.03 tkm	
CoCl ₂	0.0001 kg	Truck, 3.5–7.5 t, Euro 4 (Waste) 2.44 tkm	
MnCl ₂	0.0098 kg	Ship (Chemicals) 73.27 tkm	
Na ₂ MoO ₄	0.0012 kg	Ship (Materials) 18.73 tkm	
Stainless steel	0.3446 kg	OPTION 2	
Polyvinyl chloride (PVC)	0.0213 kg	Truck, 3.5–7.5 t, Euro 4 (Chemicals) 38.60 tkm	
UV lamps	0.0175 kg	Truck, 3.5–7.5 t, Euro 4 (Materials) 8.15 tkm	
Polyamide	0.1169 kg	Truck, 3.5–7.5 t, Euro 4 (Waste) 2.45 tkm	
Cultivation		Ship (Chemicals) 67.55 tkm	
Stainless steel	8.36 kg	Ship (Materials) 19.01 tkm	
Reactor lamps	0.13 kg		
Harvesting			
Stainless steel	3.84 kg		
Inputs from environment			
Materials		Materials	
Biomass	0.017 kg	Air (excluding CO ₂)	434.72 t
River/rain water	2.786 m ³	CO ₂	0.26 t
Outputs to technosphere		Outputs to environment	
Product		Water emissions	
Haematococcus astaxanthin	800 g	NaNO ₃	0.0891 kg
Avoided product ^a		K ₂ HPO ₄	0.0194 kg
Nitrogen-rich fertiliser	0.431 kg	KH ₂ PO ₄	0.0086 kg
Phosphorous-rich fertiliser	0.282 kg	CaCl ₂	0.0041 kg
Waste treatment		MgSO ₄	0.0189 kg
Steel, to inert landfill (OPTION 1)	13.09 kg	NaCl	0.0017 kg
Steel, to inert landfill (OPTION 2)	13.29 kg	C ₆ H ₈ O ₇	0.0004 kg
Polyvinyl chloride, to sanitary landfill	0.02 kg	C ₆ H _{5-4y} Fe _x N _y O ₇	0.0004 kg
Fluorescent lamps, to specific treatment for electronics wastes	0.15 kg	Na ₂ CO ₃	0.0067 kg
		C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₈	0.0004 kg
		H ₃ BO ₃	0.0002 kg
		ZnSO ₄	0.00001 kg
		CuSO ₄	0.000005 kg
		Co(NO ₃) ₂	0.000003 kg
		FeCl ₃	0.000039 kg
		ZnCl ₂	0.000002 kg
		CoCl ₂	0.000001 kg
		MnCl ₂	0.000138 kg
		Na ₂ MoO ₄	0.000016 kg
		OPTION 1	
		Water effluent	6.79 m ³
		NaClO	4.009 kg
		OPTION 2	
		Water effluent	2.79 m ³
Outputs to environment			
Air emissions			
Air (excluding CO ₂)	434.72 t		
CO ₂	0.24 t		

^a N and P fertiliser dosage is equivalent to 20.505 kg of residual biomass.

T2.1 Literature review – Cellulase enzyme

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Gilpin, Geoffrey S., and Anders S. G. Andrae, "Comparative Attributional Life Cycle Assessment Of European Cellulase Enzyme Production For Use In Second-Generation Lignocellulosic Bioethanol Production", <i>The International Journal Of Life Cycle Assessment</i> , Vol. 22, No. 7, 2016, pp. 1034-1053.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Case A: cornstarch glucose. Case B: sugar cane. Case C: pre-treated softwood
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Cellulase enzyme (mixture of endo-p-glucanases, exo-p-glucanases and β -glucosidase proteins)
Functional unit	1 kg of cellulase enzyme in full broth
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Second generation lignocellulosic bioethanol production
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Allocation has been applied to all multi-functional processes. For corn wet-milling economic allocation. For sugar cane proceswsing, energetic allocation. Other allocation decisions are selected according to the most suitable causal relation (see article)
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC and dLUC are not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	Europe
Data quality	Stoichiometric ecuations, volume flow, literature, Ecoinvent database
Impact assessment method	Life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) results are determined with SimaPro 8 software using CML 1A baseline and non-baseline methods along with cumulative energy demand. Sensitivity analysis is performed with the application of

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

advanced attributional LCA.	
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming potential (100 years), eutrophication potential, acidification potential, ozone layer depletion, photochemical oxidation potential, land use
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Process overview of CE (Cellulase enzyme) production:

Kommentar [BOS1]:

Figure 1: Process overview of CE production via the submerged aerobic fermentation (SmF) method

The on-site SmF production of CE in full broth involves three steps:

1. Media preparation—A carbon source, water and other nutrients are mixed in fixed quantities, along with small amounts of slip-stream-produced sophorose, which induces *Trichoderma reesei* to produce CE.
2. Seed train— *Trichoderma reesei* fungus is stimulated to multiply in optimal conditions and fed by fraction of the media prepared in step 1, producing a *Trichoderma reesei* inoculum for step 3.
3. Aerobic cultivation—In this step, the *T.reesei* from step 2 is introduced into a fermenter under submerged aerobic conditions (SmF), where it feeds on the carbon source and nutrients prepared in step 1 and secretes CE, see Fig. 2.

Three cases of CE production that use the three more relevant carbon sources are considered: cornstarch glucose in case A, sugar cane molasses in case B and pretreated softwood in case C.

Live cycle inventories:

Table 1: Life cycle inventory for cases A, B, C to produce 1 kg cellulase enzyme

	Case A	Case B	Case C	Unit	Data source ^a
Product					
CE	1.0	1.0	1.0	kg	
Input					
Materials/fuels					
Water	19.0	22.9	35.5	kg	Ecoinvent 3
Carbon source	4.7	6.9	28.3	kg	Table 5 (no allocation)/Agri-footprint (energy)/Table 6 (no allocation)
Ammonium sulphate	0.037	0.046	0.095	kg	Ecoinvent 3
Potassium phosphate	0.053	0.066	0.135	kg	Electronic Supplementary Material (no allocation)
Magnesium sulphate	0.008	0.010	0.020	kg	Ecoinvent 3
Calcium chloride	0.011	0.013	0.027	kg	Ecoinvent 3
Polysorbate 80	0.005	0.007	0.014	kg	Own calculation (no allocation)
Corn steep liquor	0.269	0.338	0.692	kg	Agri-footprint
Sulphur dioxide	0.028	0.028	0.022	kg	Ecoinvent 3
Ammonia	0.189	0.189	0.254	kg	Ecoinvent 3 (no allocation)
Antifoam (corn oil)	0.026	0.033	0.068	kg	Agri-footprint
Energy					
Electricity	6.3	7.3	26.5	kWh	Ecoinvent 3 (exergy)
Heating	2.9	3.6	0.0	MJ	Ecoinvent 3 (exergy)
Cooling	59.8	59.8	43.3	MJ	Ecoinvent 3
Emissions					
Carbon dioxide	3.8	3.8	4.4	kg	

^a Causal relation used for foreground allocation in bold; when present and significant ($\geq 5\%$) with respect to the contribution analysis of GWP, see either Fig. 3 or Electronic Supplementary Material

Table 2: Life cycle inventory for the production of 1000 kg cornstarch glucose 85% DM

	Value	Unit	Data source ^a
Product			
Glucose	1000	kg	
Input			
Materials/fuels			
Activated carbon	15.3	kg	Agri-footprint (economic)
Hydrochloric acid	7.7	kg	Ecoinvent 3
Cornstarch	766	kg	Ecoinvent 3 (economic)
Soda ash	3.1	kg	Ecoinvent 3
Water	6130	kg	Ecoinvent 3
Electricity/heat			
Electricity	57.6	kWh	European Life Cycle Database v3.0
Heat	540	MJ	Ecoinvent 3
Waste and emissions to treatment			
Waste water	5.9	m ³	Ecoinvent 3

^a Causal relation used for foreground allocation in bold; when present and significant ($\geq 5\%$) with respect to the contribution analysis of GWP

Table 3: Life cycle inventory for the production of 1000 kg pre-treated softwood biomass

	Value	Unit	Data source ^a
Product			
Pre-treated softwood biomass	1000	kg	
Input			
Materials/fuels			
Ammonia	3.14	kg	Ecoinvent 3 (no allocation)
Lime	1.97	kg	Ecoinvent 3
Softwood chips (DM)	441	kg	Electronic Supplementary Material
Steam	177	kg	Electronic Supplementary Material
Sulfuric acid	5.15	kg	Ecoinvent 3
Water	759	kg	Ecoinvent 3
Electricity/heat			
Electricity	5.93	kWh	Ecoinvent 3
Waste and emissions to treatment			
Gypsum	6.71	kg	Ecoinvent 3
Waste water	0.42	m ³	Ecoinvent 3

^a Causal relation used for foreground allocation in bold; when present and significant ($\geq 5\%$) with respect to the contribution analysis of GWP

T2.1 Literature review – Enzyme Production MetGen

1) Summary table

See example on page 3

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Pursula, Tiina, and Minna Päällysaho, <i>Report: LCA Of Enzyme Production And Calculation Of Key Performance Indicators For Metgen</i> , Gaia Consulting Oy, 2016. http://www.metgen.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/Final-report-LCA-and-KPIs-for-enzyme-production-18.11.2016.pdf .
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Yeast extract (from whey), lactose (from whey), glucose (from starch)
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Enzyme (MetGen's OXR enzyme)
Functional unit	1 kg of product at factory gate
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Thermomechanical pulping (CO2 emission intensity of primary refining reduced), Tissue production (increase efficiency), fluted paper production (increase efficiency)
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC and dLUC are not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	
Data quality	Process information delivered by Metgen Oy, Ecoinvent 3.2 data library
Impact assessment method	CML IA* methodology
Damage categories (endpoint)	

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming, acidification, eutrophication, photochemical ozone formation
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Overview of process boundaries, general block diagram:

Figure 1: General block diagram of considered system

Assumptions performed and data sources for LCI:

Table 1: Used assumptions and emissions factors for calculations

Energy	
Electricity	Electricity was purchased from Italian energy company Edison Energia Spa. The share of renewable energy is approximately 37 %. Emission factor (CO ₂) and share of electricity sources reported in company's sustainability report was used for calculation.*
Steam	Information received from Metgen was used in calculation. According to the information, all the steam used in production was produced by natural gas. Water consumption and efficiency parameters were derived from Ecoinvent database v.3.2. (Steam, in chemical industry, RER, production, Alloc Rec U)
Emissions from production	
Air emission	Amount of air emissions (CO ₂) was received from Metgen Oy.
Waste water	Amount of generated waste water was received from Metgen Oy. Process model for waste treatment plant was derived from Ecoinvent database 3.2 (Wastewater from starch production, CH, treatment of, Alloc Rec) and the process was modified according to the information received from production site.
Transportation	
Transportation	The transportation distances and modes of raw materials were not available. It was assumed that average transportation distance is 600 km according to Eurostat statistics**. It was assumed that all of the transportation is done by trucks. Transportation of the materials below the cut-off criteria was also included in calculation.

Raw materials:	
Compressed air	Amount of used compressed air was received from Metgen. Process model for compressed air production was derived from Ecoinvent database 3.2 (Compressed air, 600 KPa gauge, RER, compressed air production, Alloc Rec U). The model was modified according the data received from the production site (electricity consumption, pressure and Edison Energia's electricity mix.).
Water	According to the received information, the major part of the process water is steam condensate. It was assumed in calculation that share of freshwater is 10 % of required amount. Information from Ecoinvent database 3.2 was used for calculation (Tap water, Europe without Switzerland , market for, Alloc Rec, U).
Yeast extract	Ecoinvent 2.2 database was used for calculation (Yeast past, from whey, at fermentation, CH, U).
CSA	Ecoinvent 3.2 database was used for calculation (Chemical, organic, (GLO) production, Alloc Rec U).
NaCl	Ecoinvent 3.2 database was used for calculation (Sodium chloride, powder, RER, production, Alloc Rec U).
Ammonia	Ecoinvent 3.2 database was used for calculation (Ammonia, liquid, RER, market for, Alloc Rec U).
Lactose	Production of whey was used as estimate. Information was received from Ecoinvent 3.2 database (Whey, GLO, market for, Alloc Rec U)

Raw materials:	
Glucose	Average European raw material consumption for starch production* was used as estimate as primary information about the raw materials used for production and environmental data related to enzymatic hydrolysis of starch was not available from the suppliers. However, results are in line with the LCA study conducted by the European starch industry association**.
Triton X	Ecoinvent database 3.2 was used for calculation (Diethylene glycol, RER, ethylene glycol production, Alloc Rec, U)
Glycerol	According to supplier's information glycerol is produced as a by-product from diesel production although primary data on used raw materials was not available. As an assumption, share of different raw materials (reported by GAIN****) used for production of biodiesel was used for modelling of environmental impacts.
Ammonium sulfate	Ecoinvent 3.2 database was used for calculation (Ammonium sulfate as N, (RER), ammonium sulfate production, Alloc Rec U).
Sodium formate	Ecoinvent 3.2 database was used for calculation (Sodium formate, GLO, market for, Alloc Rec U).
Potassium phopshate	Ecoinvent 3.2 database was used for calculation (Chemical inorganic, GLO, production, Alloc Rec U).

T2.1 Literature review – Enzymes (Novozymes)

1) Summary table

See example on page 3

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Nielsen, Per H., Karen M. Oxenbøll, and Henrik Wenzel, "Cradle-To-Gate Environmental Assessment Of Enzyme Products Produced Industrially In Denmark By Novozymes A/S", The International Journal Of Life Cycle Assessment, Vol. 12, No. 6, 2006, pp. 432-438.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Potato protein, wheat/corn
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Enzymes (Termamyl 120L: liquid, Spirizyme plus FG: liquid, Ronozyme P5000 CT: granulated and coated, Savinase 12 TXT: granulated and coated, Novamyl 10,00 BG: granulated)
Functional unit	1 kg final product at the factory's gate
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Termamyl 120 L: liquefaction of starch. Spirizyme plus FG: saccharification of starch. Ronozyme P5000 CT: release of phytate bound phosphate. Savinase 12 TXT: removal of protein stains. Novamyl 10,000 BG: diminish crystallisation of starch.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC and dLUC are not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	Denmark
Data quality	Primary data reflecting Novozymes production conditions in 2004. Data from suppliers. Literature data (verified by producers). Energy supply data derived

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

	from 1996 Ecoinvent database.
Impact assessment method	Life cycle assessment (analytical tool), modelling through SimaPro 6.0 software. Characterization of environmental impacts based on Eco-indicator 95 v2.1.
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming, acidification, nutrient enrichment, photochemical ozone formation, primary energy consumption, use of agricultural land.
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Production process and flow diagram:

Production of enzyme products at Novozyme factories involves four main processes: 1) fermentation: growth of pure culture micro-organisms in a liquid medium, 2) recovery: separation of extracellular enzymes from the biomass, 3) formulation: preservation and standardization of enzyme products and, eventually, addition of formulation chemicals and 4) biomass treatment: inactivation of micro-organisms and drying the biomass for use as soil improver in agriculture (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Main processes in industrial enzyme production at Novozymes. Heat, electricity and water are used in any process and wastewater is generated in any process

Enzymes are produced in fermentation tanks by micro-organisms supplied with carbohydrates (sugar and starch), protein, mineral salts and vitamins. The process typically takes three to ten days and electricity is used for aeration and mixing. The fermentation broth contains the micro-organisms and extracellular enzymes. The enzymes are recovered by centrifugation and filtration. The recovered enzyme liquor is transferred to formulation processes and the remaining biomass is transferred to biomass treatment. The recovery process uses filtration materials and electricity for pumping, etc. The concentration of enzyme in the enzyme liquor is standardized and some products are furthermore fixed on a solid material (granulation) and coated in the formulation process. The formulation process uses water for dilution, heat and electricity for spray driers and vacuum evaporators and granulation materials for the granulation process (kaolin, sodium sulphate, etc. depending on the specific product). The final products are packed and stored for delivery.

Inventory data sources:

Table 1: Ingredients and materials included in the study

Process	Substance	Data source
Fermentation	Corn starch	Würdinger et al. (2003)
	Sucrose	Nielsen et al. (2003)
	Glucose/maltose	Supplier / Int. Starch Inst., Denmark
	Corn steep powder	Supplier
	Soy bean meal	Nielsen et al. (2003)
	Potato protein	Supplier
	Phosphoric acid	Ecoinvent (2003)
	Glucose syrup	Supplier / Int. Starch Inst., Denmark
	Ammonia	Ecoinvent (2003)
Recovery	Kieselgur	Supplier (mined from the ground)
	Perlite	Supplier (mined from the ground)
	Sodium chloride	Ecoinvent (2003)
Formulation	Sodium sulphate	Supplier (mined from the ground)
	Cellulose powder	Supplier
	Palm oil	Ecoinvent (2003)
	Wheat starch	Würdinger et al. (2003)
	Kaolin	Ecoinvent (2003)
	Calcium carbonate	Ecoinvent (2003)
	Titanium dioxide	Ecoinvent (2003)
	Sodium chloride	Ecoinvent (2003)
	Sucrose	Nielsen et al. (2003)
	Calcium chloride	Weidema (2003)
Acetic acid	Ecoinvent (2003)	

The ingredients listed in the table constitute the majority of ingredients used to produce the considered enzymes. The remaining ingredients comprise a relatively long list of individual substances such as vitamins, cleaning agents, micronutrients, flocculation agents, product stabilizers, etc. used in small amounts. Their names and applications are not detailed for confidentiality reasons.

T2.1 Literature review – Immobilized enzymes

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Kim, Seungdo, Concepción Jiménez-González, and Bruce E. Dale, "Enzymes For Pharmaceutical Applications—A Cradle-To-Gate Life Cycle Assessment", The International Journal Of Life Cycle Assessment, Vol. 14, No. 5, 2009, pp. 392-400.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Soybean protein, yeast extract
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Immobilized enzymes: aldolase, carbamoylase, and hydantoinase
Functional unit	1 kg of immobilized enzyme
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Production of pharmaceutical products
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Mass allocations are applied to multi-output processes in the upstream processes (soybean protein and yeast extract). Mass allocation and system expansion approach to estimate the LCI of glycerin. Economic based allocation is not included.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	The land use change associated with conversion of undisturbed natural ecosystems to croplands (indirect land use change) is not included. GHG emissions associated with land use change (direct and indirect), measured by changes in soil organic carbon levels, are included in the analysis with the assumption that undisturbed ecosystems converted to croplands (corn-soybean rotation) consist of 62% of grassland and 38% of forest.
Geographic location, if defined	
Data quality	LCI information was obtained from the company GlaxoSmithKline (GSK) LCI database FLASC, commercial databases (DEAM, Ecoinvent) and the literature.

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Impact assessment method	The 100-year time horizon GWPs (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change 2001) are used to estimate GHG emissions. Acidification, eutrophication, and photochemical smog are estimated by the CML characterization factors (Guinée 2002)
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Non-renewable energy consumption, global warming, acidification, eutrophication and photochemical smog formation
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Generic block diagram for enzyme production process:

Figure 1: Generic enzyme production process

The following enzyme production processes and sub-processes for the enzymes analyzed and their boundaries are included:

- Media preparation includes the upstream processes for substrate production (including transportation) and energy consumption in substrate mixing.
- Fermentation includes energy consumption in agitation and heating during enzyme production and emissions during fermentation. Sanitization includes steam consumption in sanitization.
- Separation includes water consumption and energy consumption in separating cells from the fermentation broth.

- Cell disruption includes energy consumption and chemicals used. & Immobilization includes the enzyme support sepabead (poly(glycidyl methacrylate-co-ethylene dimethacrylate)), chemicals, and energy consumption in immobilizing enzyme in the sepabead.
- Waste management includes a wastewater treatment facility and assumes biosolids are discharged into the sea.

*The enzyme used in inoculation is not included in the system boundary due to lack of data and its small quantity.

T2.1 Literature review –Glass-hemp/thermoset composite

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	La Rosa, A.D., G. Cozzo, A. Latteri, A. Recca, A. Björklund, E. Parrinello, and G. Cicala, "Life Cycle Assessment Of A Novel Hybrid Glass-Hemp/Thermoset Composite", Journal Of Cleaner Production, Vol. 44, 2013, pp. 69-76.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Hemp fibers
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Elbow fitting made of glass-hemp/epoxy vinyl ester in comparison with an elbow made of glass fibre/epoxy vinyl ester.
Functional unit	The function of one elbow fitting used in the sea water cooling pipeline of a Sicilian chemical plant, with an estimated life of 20 years.
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Materials
Possible applications	Natural fibre-reinforced composites find a wide array of applications in the building and construction industry and the automobile industry.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	No allocation
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC and dLUC are not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	Italy, Europe
Data quality	Primary data collected mainly for the manufacturing process of the composite. Ecoinvent database for other parts of the system
Impact assessment method	ReCiPe method
Damage categories (endpoint)	Damage to Human Health, Ecosystem Quality, and Resources
Impact categories (midpoint)	Global energy requirement, global warming potential, agricultural land occupation

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

System boundaries:

Figure 1: System boundaries

Final product:

Figure 2: Elbow-fitting manufacturing

Life cycle inventory:

Table 1: Cradle to gate inventory for hemp

<i>Hemp cultivation</i> ^a	
Country of origin	UK
Growing practices:	Companion planting bio organics small coop's of family farms
Use of fertilizers	No
Use of pesticides	No
Land occupation	0.696 m ² a
Agricultural machinery	23.05 kg
<i>Hemp processing</i>	
Country of origin	Essex, UK
Type of process used	Clean, chemical free and waste free process
Energy demand: electricity for scutching	336 kWh

^a Data source González-García et al., 2010.

Table 2: Materials transport specifications

<i>Glass-fibre</i>	
Country of origin	Germany
Manufacture country	Italy (Sicily)
Use country	Italy (Sicily)
Assumed distance	1600 km + 600 km
Type of transport	Lorry >32 t (1600 km) + lorry 7.5–16 t (600 km)
<i>Epoxy Vinyl ester resin</i>	
Country of origin	Germany
Manufacture country	Italy (Sicily)
Use country	Italy (Sicily)
Assumed distance	1600 km + 600 km
Type of transport	Lorry >32 t (1600 km) + lorry 7.5–16 t (600 km)
<i>Hemp mats</i>	
Country of origin	UK
Manufacture country	Italy (Sicily)
Use country	Italy (Sicily)
Assumed distance	Lorry >32 t (1600 km) + lorry 7.5–16 t (600 km)
Type of transport	Lorry >32 t (1600 km) + lorry 7.5–16 t (600 km)

Life cycle costing:

Figure 2: a. LCC network of the GF elbow. b. LCC network of the hybrid elbow.

T2.1 Literature review – Green Hardboard

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	González-García, Sara, Gumersindo Feijoo, Carol Heathcote, Andreas Kandelbauer, and M. Teresa Moreira, "Environmental Assessment Of Green Hardboard Production Coupled With A Laccase Activated System", Journal Of Cleaner Production, Vol. 19, No. 5, 2011, p
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Composites
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Lignocellulosic fibers. Bio-based phenolic materials (lignosulfonates, which are a co-product from dissolving pulp mills or flavonoid-based tannins: chestnut, tara, mimosa or quebracho tannins) with phenol-oxidizing enzymes (laccase produced through genetically modified fungus in submerged fermentation)
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Hardboards produced with a two-component adhesive based on laccase activated tannin (instead of PF resin). Main features of green hardboard specified on short report (Table 1).
Functional unit	1 m ³ of finished green hardboard for interior applications. Density of 900 kg/m ³ and moisture content of 7%.
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Materials
Possible applications	Wood-based panels for end-use sectors: residential construction, furniture, cabinets, flooring, mouldings
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	An allocation procedure is necessary for the panels (residual wood is used for on-site generation of thermal energy). No environmental burden allocation was assumed to forest waste from previous processes.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC and dLUC are not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	Western Europe
Data quality	Foreground system (green HB manufacturing) data consists on data obtained by

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

	on-site measurements. Typical process-specific data were collected to avoid anomalous conditions. All the emission data corresponded to field data. Background system such as electricity, paraffin and aluminum sulphate production and emission factors were obtained from the Ecoinvent database. Regarding chemicals and green chips requirements and wood waste transportation routes were supplied by plant workers. Inventory data for forest operations, wood chipping, laccase production, the lignin based phenolic material production were taken from the literature.
Impact assessment method	CML 2 baseline 2000 V2.1 biogenic method
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming (GW), photochemical oxidant formation (PO), acidification (AC), eutrophication (EP), cumulative energy demand (CED)
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Bio-product properties:

Table 1: Main features of green hardboard
Main features of green HB.

Nominal width	1220–1524 m
Moisture content	2–9%
Board thickness	3.0–3.6 mm
MoR	38–60 N mm ⁻²
MoE	3200–3900 N mm ⁻²
Internal bond (IB) ^a	0.8–2.2 N mm ⁻²

^a with a 24 h water swelling (20 °C) of 29–57%.

Global inventory data:

Table 2: Global inventory data per 1 kg of lignin based phenolic material.

INPUTS from TECHNOSPHERE			
Materials		Energy	
Biomass		Electricity from grid	40.2 kWh
Green logs (50% moisture)	0.26 m ³	Steam from biomass ^a	208.4 kWh
Chemicals		<i>Transport</i>	
Hydrogen Peroxide	2.7 kg	20-28 t truck	0.77 t km
Sodium hydroxide	4.5 kg	16 t truck	0.07 t km
Sulfurous acid	0.14 kg		
Chelant	0.10 kg		
OUTPUTS			
To TECHNOSPHERE		To ENVIRONMENT	
Materials		Emissions to air	
Lignosulfonate	1 kg	CO ₂ biogenic	0.11 kg
Ethanol	2.5 kg	CO ₂ fossil	4.2 kg
Dissolving pulp	42.0 kg	<i>Emissions to water</i>	
		COD	1.8 kg
		BOD ₅	0.40 kg

System boundaries, block diagram:

Figure 1: System boundaries and process chain under study

Description of the system under study

Three subsystems conform the foreground system: Fiber preparation, board forming and board finishing.

Fiber preparation. The main raw materials are green wood chips obtained from Norway spruce (*Picea abies*) and European beech (*Fagus sylvatica*). This material is delivered by truck from Austrian wood-based industries such as sawmills, satellite chip mills, etc. Wood chips are washed to remove dirt and other debris. Clean chips and additional raw material from the plant (sanding dust, sawdust, trimmings, rejected hardboard etc.) are pre-heated to soften lignin and enable subsequent fiber separation. The following step consists of their reduction into fibers, followed by an enzymatic treatment and placement in a storage bin. The enzymatic treatment is carried out by immersing the fibers in the aqueous laccase containing solution for a 20min incubation time. Enzyme dose may be reduced by applying longer incubation time and/or recirculation. A fraction of the wood material is burnt in biomass boilers to produce thermal energy for plant activities.

Board forming. Fibers with the two-component adhesive are transported from the storage bin to the forming machine where they are placed onto a moving conveyor belt to form a mat. The mat is pre-pressed and trimmed before being loaded into the hot press. This press applies heat and pressure to cure the adhesive and bond the fibers for 4 min.

Board finishing. The boards are placed in a conditioning room and then sanded and sawed into final size. Finally, the boards are packaged and sent to the warehouse. Trimming residues are recycled back to board production or used for on-site energy production.

T2.1 Literature review – Insulin (Novo Nordisk)

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Ministry of environment and food of Denmark. Danish Environmental Protection Agency “Novo Nordisk’s Environmental Profit and Loss account”. 2014 http://mst.dk/service/publikationer/publikationsarkiv/2014/apr/assessment-of-potentials-and-limitations-in-valuation-of-externalities/ .
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Environmental profit and loss account
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Maize
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Insulin (main pharmaceutical product). Glucose (from maize, for insulin production)
Functional unit	Indirect spend: per DKK Direct spend: per physical volume (kg)
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Pharmaceutical /medical field
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Two categories: indirect and direct spend. Indirect spend: IT, office furniture, production equipment and machinery. Direct spend: processed raw materials sources, glucose for insulin production, plastic granulate for pen components production
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC analyzed for glucose only. iLUC is measured in terms of land occupation (ha yr) and applied as a rough proxy for biodiversity and ecosystem services. No distinction between land use types is made. GHG emissions relating to iLUC are reported under GHG emissions and not land use.
Geographic location, if defined	Novo Nordisk production sites: Clayton, USA. Chartres, France. Tizi Ouzou, Algeria. Montes Claros, Brazil. Denmark (multiple). Tianjin, China. Koriyama, Japan
Data quality	Collection of data includes environmental data such as energy consumption, the

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

	<p>purchasing of chemicals, methods of transportation etc. It also includes economic accounts describing the expenditure made by the company.</p> <p>If primary data is not obtained from suppliers, the gaps are filled out with modelled data. Modelled data uses sector averages to estimate environmental impacts, and can be obtained on a regional level, depending on the supplier's geographical location. Additional data sources include secondary LCA data from existing LCA databases.</p>
Impact assessment method	Customized method (See report)
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Water use, GHGs, Air pollution, iLUC
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Environmental Profit and Loss Account (E P&L):

The information mentioned below is extracted from the *Novo Nordisk's Environmental Profit and Loss account report*.

Through a partnership, NIRAS, Trucost and 2.0 LCA have combined their experience in EIO modelling, life cycle assessment and environmental evaluation to conduct an Environmental Profit and Loss study within the scope of the project and develop the above cited work. Therefore, throughout the customized method, the quantification and evaluation of impacts throughout Novo Nordisk's supply chain is possible. The approach for the E P&L developed for Novo Nordisk, throughout seven steps is presented in the figure below.

Figure 1: High level project approach. The 7 steps of the Novo Nordisk E P&L

Novo Nordisk value chain:

Novo Nordisk is a global health care company with core competencies in the development and production of pharmaceuticals (primarily insulin) and in the development and production of medical devices, primarily for delivering insulin. The Novo Nordisk value chain taken into account in the E P&L

study (with the exception of distribution from affiliates to pharmacies, hospitals and wholesalers as well as in-use or end-of-life of products) is presented in figure 2.

Figure 2: Novo Nordisk's value chain

Tier definition in Novo Nordisk is presented on Figure 3.

Figure 2: Novo Nordisk's tier definition

Novo Nordisk operations

Novo Nordisk operations include the core activities for pharmaceutical production, production of devices, filling, assembly and packaging. A large portion of the parts production is outsourced, but is still considered part of Novo Nordisk operations, since Novo Nordisk owns the molds and approves all suppliers to produce device parts. Direct impacts from Novo Nordisk operations are mainly related to energy use in the production facilities.

Tier 1: Finished products and services

Novo Nordisk sources many finished products and services to support administration, Research and development, product distribution and maintenance of production facilities. Tier 1 includes impacts from production of products and services such as production equipment, clinical and laboratory services, transportation services, IT and office supplies. E.g. environmental impacts occur at the factories manufacturing the machines/products demanded by Novo Nordisk, and/or occur due to the distribution of these products by truck, ship and/or air transport.

Tier 2: Processed materials

The impacts associated with Tier 2 come from the processing of raw materials, for example transforming oil into plastic granulates, corn into glucose, and by milling starch into syrup. Novo Nordisk sources a large quantity of processed raw materials for direct use in their own or outsourced production facilities. A finished product in Tier 1 (i.e. a machine) draws processed materials from Tier 2, which includes processes such as rolling and extruding of metals. 18 Novo Nordisk's environmental profit and loss account

Tier 3: Raw materials

Impacts in tier 3 come from the extraction of raw materials or cultivation of farm crops. Commodities such as corn are highly water intensive during this stage. In addition, fertilizer application and harvesting contribute to air pollution and GHG emissions in this phase. Impacts from raw materials such as crude oil and petroleum, which are key inputs for plastic and other chemicals used in the Novo Nordisk value chain, come from energy and water use associated with the extraction of materials. Novo Nordisk indirectly source raw materials through tier 1 and 2 suppliers.

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

See example on page 3

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Sheldon, Roger A., “Utilisation of Biomass for Sustainable Fuels and Chemicals: Molecules, Methods and Metrics”, Catalysis Today, Vol. 167, No. 1, Utilisation of Biomass for Fuels and Chemicals: The Road to Sustainability, June 10, 2011, pp. 3–13.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): No Explicit LCA but a methodology has been proposed which I think would be valuable in the assessment of chemical products
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	General
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	All chemicals
Functional unit	none
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Platform chemicals
Possible applications	Application as bio-surfactant in industry and laundry detergents, dishwashing liquid, personal care products and as pesticides
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	None
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	
Geographic location, if defined	
Data quality	Information captured in this study is valuable for environmental indicator selection as these are specific to bio-based products and green chemistry
Impact assessment method	

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Damage categories (endpoint)	None
Impact categories (midpoint)	Atom economy E-factor (kg of waste/ kg of product)
Other information or comments	None

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Example of summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”)	Nuss, Philip, and Kevin H. Gardner, “Attributional Life Cycle Assessment (ALCA) of Polyitaconic Acid Production from Northeast US Softwood Biomass”, The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment, Vol. 18, No. 3, 2013, pp. 603–612.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Wood from forestry (hemicellulose), compared to corn (glucose) and to fossil base.
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Polyitaconic acid (PIA, main product, granulated, water soluble). Co-products include sawlogs and bark, wood pulp and mycelium (protein-rich animal feed)
Functional unit	1 kg of main product
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Chemical additive with a wide range of possible applications including superabsorbents, anti-scaling agents in water treatments, co-builders in detergents, and dispersants for minerals in coatings.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Forest products: by weight. Xylane extraction: by heating value. Fermentation: by dry weight (sensi with market price).
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC is excluded. dLUC is not mentioned, but activity takes place in the US and hence dLUC seems ignored.
Geographic location, if defined	N-E of the U.S.A.
Data quality	Primary data for softwood-derived PIA tranformation (lab and pilot plant runs). Referenced data + secondary data (ecoinvent).
Impact assessment method	Customized method set (see below)
Damage categories (endpoint)	ReCiPe end-point impacts (H/A v1.05; Goedkoop et al. 2009)
Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming potential (GWP); cumulative energy demand (Goedkoop et al. 2008); acidification and eutrophication (Bare et al. 2002); water use and land occupation (Goedkoop et al. 2009). Acidification and eutrophication (Bare et al. 2002), as their LCIA method applies region-specific characterization factors more in line with the geographical scope (USA) of our assessment.
Other information or comments	

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

See example on page 3

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Slater, C. Stewart, Mariano J. Savelski, David Hitchcock, and Eduardo J. Cavanagh, “Environmental Analysis of the Life Cycle Emissions of 2-Methyl Tetrahydrofuran Solvent Manufactured from Renewable Resources”, Journal of Environmental Science and Health, Part A, Vol. 51, No. 6, May 11, 2016, pp. 487–494.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Left-over corn cob
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	2-Methyl tetrahydrofuran (MeTHF) Lignin Methyl alcohol Acetone Acetic acid
Functional unit	1kg of MeTHF
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Manufacture of fine chemicals, bioplastics and other
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	GHG emission allocated among the products and co-products by mass.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Land-use has been ignored since corn-cob is considered an agricultural by-product (waste)
Geographic location, if defined	Location not-specified
Data quality	Good, life cycle inventory for the bio-products synthesised has been presented in the supplementary section

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Impact assessment method	None stated ; only specific indicators chosen
Damage categories (endpoint)	None
Impact categories (midpoint)	Total air emissions (CO ₂ , CO, CH ₄ , NO _x , NMVOC kg/kg of MeTHF) Particulate emission Emissions to water Emissions to soil
Other information or comments	None

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Example of summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”)	Nuss, Philip, and Kevin H. Gardner, “Attributional Life Cycle Assessment (ALCA) of Polyitaconic Acid Production from Northeast US Softwood Biomass”, The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment, Vol. 18, No. 3, 2013, pp. 603–612.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Wood from forestry (hemicellulose), compared to corn (glucose) and to fossil base.
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Polyitaconic acid (PIA, main product, granulated, water soluble). Co-products include sawlogs and bark, wood pulp and mycelium (protein-rich animal feed)
Functional unit	1 kg of main product
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Chemical additive with a wide range of possible applications including superabsorbents, anti-scaling agents in water treatments, co-builders in detergents, and dispersants for minerals in coatings.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Forest products: by weight. Xylane extraction: by heating value. Fermentation: by dry weight (sensi with market price).
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC is excluded. dLUC is not mentioned, but activity takes place in the US and hence dLUC seems ignored.
Geographic location, if defined	N-E of the U.S.A.
Data quality	Primary data for softwood-derived PIA tranformation (lab and pilot plant runs). Referenced data + secondary data (ecoinvent).
Impact assessment method	Customized method set (see below)
Damage categories (endpoint)	ReCiPe end-point impacts (H/A v1.05; Goedkoop et al. 2009)
Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming potential (GWP); cumulative energy demand (Goedkoop et al. 2008); acidification and eutrophication (Bare et al. 2002); water use and land occupation (Goedkoop et al. 2009). Acidification and eutrophication (Bare et al. 2002), as their LCIA method applies region-specific characterization factors more in line with the geographical scope (USA) of our assessment.
Other information or comments	

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

See example on page 3

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Zhang, Yanan, Guiping Hu, and Robert C. Brown, “Life Cycle Assessment of Commodity Chemical Production from Forest Residue via Fast Pyrolysis”, The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment, Vol. 19, No. 7, July 1, 2014, pp. 1371–1381.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Lignocellulosic forest residue
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Bio-oil upgraded to commodity chemicals below Ethylene 22.9% Propene 38.5% Butylene 10.2% Benzene 7.6% Toulene 14.1% Xylene 5.5% Ethylbenzene 0.7% Styrene 0.4% Indene 0.1% Naphthalene 0.1%
Functional unit	1 kg of chemicals
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Bulk chemicals
Possible applications	Used in the preparation of polymers, as intermediates for other fine chemical production, bio-based fertiliser and other derivatives like surfactants, dyes and pigments and resins.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): chemical replacement
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	None

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Inclusion of land use change <i>(please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)</i>	Indirect land-use omitted, however, no explicit mention/ analysis of direct land use emission considered (mainly due to use of forest residues)
Geographic location, if defined	None
Data quality	Sufficient for an simple-attributinal LCA
Impact assessment method	TRACI 2.0
Damage categories (endpoint)	Carcinogenics (CTUh) Noncarcinogenics (CTUh) Respiratory effects (kg PM10 eq)
Impact categories (midpoint)	Ozone Depletion (kgCFC-11 eq) Smog (kg O3eq) Acidification (mol H+ eq) Eutrophication (kg N eq) Ecotoxicity (CTUe)
Other information or comments	None

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Example of summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”)	Nuss, Philip, and Kevin H. Gardner, “Attributional Life Cycle Assessment (ALCA) of Polyitaconic Acid Production from Northeast US Softwood Biomass”, The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment, Vol. 18, No. 3, 2013, pp. 603–612.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Wood from forestry (hemicellulose), compared to corn (glucose) and to fossil base.
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Polyitaconic acid (PIA, main product, granulated, water soluble). Co-products include sawlogs and bark, wood pulp and mycelium (protein-rich animal feed)
Functional unit	1 kg of main product
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Chemical additive with a wide range of possible applications including superabsorbents, anti-scaling agents in water treatments, co-builders in detergents, and dispersants for minerals in coatings.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Forest products: by weight. Xylane extraction: by heating value. Fermentation: by dry weight (sensi with market price).
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC is excluded. dLUC is not mentioned, but activity takes place in the US and hence dLUC seems ignored.
Geographic location, if defined	N-E of the U.S.A.
Data quality	Primary data for softwood-derived PIA transformation (lab and pilot plant runs). Referenced data + secondary data (ecoinvent).
Impact assessment method	Customized method set (see below)
Damage categories (endpoint)	ReCiPe end-point impacts (H/A v1.05; Goedkoop et al. 2009)
Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming potential (GWP); cumulative energy demand (Goedkoop et al. 2008); acidification and eutrophication (Bare et al. 2002); water use and land occupation (Goedkoop et al. 2009). Acidification and eutrophication (Bare et al. 2002), as their LCIA method applies region-specific characterization factors more in line with the geographical scope (USA) of our assessment.
Other information or comments	

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

See example on page 3

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Jeswani, Harish K., Temitope Falano, and Adisa Azapagic, “Life Cycle Environmental Sustainability of Lignocellulosic Ethanol Produced in Integrated Thermo-Chemical Biorefineries”, <i>Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining</i> , Vol. 9, No. 6, November 1, 2015, pp. 661–676.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	wheat straw poplar Miscanthus and forest residue
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Lignocellulosic ethanol
Functional unit	g CO ₂ eq./l of ethanol
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Commodity chemical
Possible applications	Engine fuel and fuel additive (antifreeze)
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Butanol and Propanol
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Land-use has been accounted for these feedstock and quantified. A variety of scenarios have been considered for land use (referring to t
Geographic location, if defined	Location not-specified. However, the significance of the same on overall emission calculation is acknowledged
Data quality	Good, life cycle inventory for the bio-products synthesised has been presented in the supplementary section
Impact assessment method	None stated ; only specific indicators chosen

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Damage categories (endpoint)	None
Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming potential Acidification Eutrophication Photochemical ozone formation Human toxicity Water use
Other information or comments	None

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Example of summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”)	Nuss, Philip, and Kevin H. Gardner, “Attributional Life Cycle Assessment (ALCA) of Polyitaconic Acid Production from Northeast US Softwood Biomass”, The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment, Vol. 18, No. 3, 2013, pp. 603–612.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Wood from forestry (hemicellulose), compared to corn (glucose) and to fossil base.
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Polyitaconic acid (PIA, main product, granulated, water soluble). Co-products include sawlogs and bark, wood pulp and mycelium (protein-rich animal feed)
Functional unit	1 kg of main product
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Chemical additive with a wide range of possible applications including superabsorbents, anti-scaling agents in water treatments, co-builders in detergents, and dispersants for minerals in coatings.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Forest products: by weight. Xylane extraction: by heating value. Fermentation: by dry weight (sensi with market price).
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC is excluded. dLUC is not mentioned, but activity takes place in the US and hence dLUC seems ignored.
Geographic location, if defined	N-E of the U.S.A.
Data quality	Primary data for softwood-derived PIA tranformation (lab and pilot plant runs). Referenced data + secondary data (ecoinvent).
Impact assessment method	Customized method set (see below)
Damage categories (endpoint)	ReCiPe end-point impacts (H/A v1.05; Goedkoop et al. 2009)
Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming potential (GWP); cumulative energy demand (Goedkoop et al. 2008); acidification and eutrophication (Bare et al. 2002); water use and land occupation (Goedkoop et al. 2009). Acidification and eutrophication (Bare et al. 2002), as their LCIA method applies region-specific characterization factors more in line with the geographical scope (USA) of our assessment.
Other information or comments	

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

See example on page 3

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Adom, Felix, Jennifer B. Dunn, Jeongwoo Han, and Norm Sather, “Life-Cycle Fossil Energy Consumption and Greenhouse Gas Emissions of Bioderived Chemicals and Their Conventional Counterparts”, Environmental Science & Technology, Vol. 48, No. 24, December 16, 2014, pp. 14624–14631.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Algae and Corn stover
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Glycerol to propylene glycol through catalytic hydrogenolysis Ethanol Polyethylene via dehydration to ethylene and polymerization Sugars to clean sugars via separation
Functional unit	1 kg of chemical
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Manufacture of fine chemicals, bioplastics and other
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	GHG emission allocated among the products and co-products by mass.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Land use emission have been accounted for algae, excluding corn-stover due to it being an agricultural residue
Geographic location, if defined	Location not-specified
Data quality	Good, life cycle inventory for the bio-products synthesised has been presented in the supplementary section
Impact assessment method	None stated ; only specific indicators chosen
Damage categories (endpoint)	None

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Impact categories (midpoint)	Fossil Energy Consumption (FEC) Cradle-Grave GHG emissions (kg CO ₂ eq/kg of chemical)
Other information or comments	None

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Example of summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”)	Nuss, Philip, and Kevin H. Gardner, “Attributional Life Cycle Assessment (ALCA) of Polyitaconic Acid Production from Northeast US Softwood Biomass”, The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment, Vol. 18, No. 3, 2013, pp. 603–612.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Wood from forestry (hemicellulose), compared to corn (glucose) and to fossil base.
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Polyitaconic acid (PIA, main product, granulated, water soluble). Co-products include sawlogs and bark, wood pulp and mycelium (protein-rich animal feed)
Functional unit	1 kg of main product
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Chemical additive with a wide range of possible applications including superabsorbents, anti-scaling agents in water treatments, co-builders in detergents, and dispersants for minerals in coatings.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Forest products: by weight. Xylane extraction: by heating value. Fermentation: by dry weight (sensi with market price).
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC is excluded. dLUC is not mentioned, but activity takes place in the US and hence dLUC seems ignored.
Geographic location, if defined	N-E of the U.S.A.
Data quality	Primary data for softwood-derived PIA tranformation (lab and pilot plant runs). Referenced data + secondary data (ecoinvent).
Impact assessment method	Customized method set (see below)
Damage categories (endpoint)	ReCiPe end-point impacts (H/A v1.05; Goedkoop et al. 2009)
Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming potential (GWP); cumulative energy demand (Goedkoop et al. 2008); acidification and eutrophication (Bare et al. 2002); water use and land occupation (Goedkoop et al. 2009). Acidification and eutrophication (Bare et al. 2002), as their LCIA method applies region-specific characterization factors more in line with the geographical scope (USA) of our assessment.
Other information or comments	

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

See example on page 3

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Fiorentino, G., M. Ripa, S. Mellino, S. Fahd, and S. Ulgiati, “Life Cycle Assessment of Brassica Carinata Biomass Conversion to Bioenergy and Platform Chemicals”, Journal of Cleaner Production, Vol. 66, No. Supplement C, March 1, 2014, pp. 174–187.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Brassica carinata – Rape straw and seed
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Rapeseed- Bio-diesel Straw – Ethyl Levulinate, Formic acid and Biochar
Functional unit	1ha of cultivated land
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Platform and bulk chemical
Possible applications	Application as Food additive : flavouring agent ; Formic acid : flavouring agent, preservative and as insecticides in agriculture ; Corrosion inhibition and anti-scaling agent ; Ion exchange agents
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Mass-based and economic allocation assumed
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Land-use has been accounted for these feedstock and quantified. No further elaboration presented as its all internally calculated by SimaPro
Geographic location, if defined	Plantation in Southern Italy ; Biorefinery in Le Calorie Srl (Caserta, Italy)
Data quality	Good, life cycle inventory for the bio-products synthesised has been presented in the supplementary section
Impact assessment method	CML 2001 and Cumulative Energy demand

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Damage categories (endpoint)	None
Impact categories (midpoint)	Abiotic Depletion potential (ADP, in kg Sb eq) Acidification potential (EP, in kg SO ₂ eq) Eutrophication potential (EP, in kg PO ₄ eq) Global warming potential (GWP, in kg CO ₂ eq) HUman Toxicity potnetial (HTP, in kg C ₂ H ₄)
Other information or comments	None

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Example of summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”)	Nuss, Philip, and Kevin H. Gardner, “Attributional Life Cycle Assessment (ALCA) of Polyitaconic Acid Production from Northeast US Softwood Biomass”, The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment, Vol. 18, No. 3, 2013, pp. 603–612.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Wood from forestry (hemicellulose), compared to corn (glucose) and to fossil base.
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Polyitaconic acid (PIA, main product, granulated, water soluble). Co-products include sawlogs and bark, wood pulp and mycelium (protein-rich animal feed)
Functional unit	1 kg of main product
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Chemical additive with a wide range of possible applications including superabsorbents, anti-scaling agents in water treatments, co-builders in detergents, and dispersants for minerals in coatings.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Forest products: by weight. Xylane extraction: by heating value. Fermentation: by dry weight (sensi with market price).
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC is excluded. dLUC is not mentioned, but activity takes place in the US and hence dLUC seems ignored.
Geographic location, if defined	N-E of the U.S.A.
Data quality	Primary data for softwood-derived PIA tranformation (lab and pilot plant runs). Referenced data + secondary data (ecoinvent).
Impact assessment method	Customized method set (see below)
Damage categories (endpoint)	ReCiPe end-point impacts (H/A v1.05; Goedkoop et al. 2009)
Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming potential (GWP); cumulative energy demand (Goedkoop et al. 2008); acidification and eutrophication (Bare et al. 2002); water use and land occupation (Goedkoop et al. 2009). Acidification and eutrophication (Bare et al. 2002), as their LCIA method applies region-specific characterization factors more in line with the geographical scope (USA) of our assessment.
Other information or comments	

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

See example on page 3

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Lokesh, K., C. West, J. Kuylenstierna, J. Fan, V. Budarin, P. Priece, J. A. Lopez-Sanchez, and J. Clark, “Environmental Impact Assessment of Wheat Straw Based Alkyl Polyglucosides Produced Using Novel Chemical Approaches”, <i>Green Chemistry</i> , Vol. 19, No. 18, September 19, 2017, pp. 4380–4395.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Wheat straw
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Alkyl Polyglucoside Levoglucosan and levoglucosenone Biochar
Functional unit	1kg of chemical
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Platform chemicals
Possible applications	Application as bio-surfactant in industry and laundry detergents, dishwashing liquid, personal care products and as pesticides
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Mass-based and economic allocation assumed
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Land-use has been accounted for these feedstock and quantified.
Geographic location, if defined	Plantation and processing assumed in the UK at a distance of 150 km each
Data quality	Life cycle inventory for the bio-products synthesised has been presented in the supplementary section
Impact assessment method	Opted for selected life cycle inventory indicators (mainly using metrics from Green chemistry)

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Damage categories (endpoint)	None
Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming potential (GWP, in kg CO2 eq) Water consumption (m3/kg chemical) Fossil-derived energy consumption (MJ/ kg of chemical) Waste generation (kg/kg of chemical)
Other information or comments	None

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Example of summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”)	Nuss, Philip, and Kevin H. Gardner, “Attributional Life Cycle Assessment (ALCA) of Polyitaconic Acid Production from Northeast US Softwood Biomass”, The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment, Vol. 18, No. 3, 2013, pp. 603–612.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Wood from forestry (hemicellulose), compared to corn (glucose) and to fossil base.
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Polyitaconic acid (PIA, main product, granulated, water soluble). Co-products include sawlogs and bark, wood pulp and mycelium (protein-rich animal feed)
Functional unit	1 kg of main product
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Chemical additive with a wide range of possible applications including superabsorbents, anti-scaling agents in water treatments, co-builders in detergents, and dispersants for minerals in coatings.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Forest products: by weight. Xylane extraction: by heating value. Fermentation: by dry weight (sensi with market price).
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC is excluded. dLUC is not mentioned, but activity takes place in the US and hence dLUC seems ignored.
Geographic location, if defined	N-E of the U.S.A.
Data quality	Primary data for softwood-derived PIA tranformation (lab and pilot plant runs). Referenced data + secondary data (ecoinvent).
Impact assessment method	Customized method set (see below)
Damage categories (endpoint)	ReCiPe end-point impacts (H/A v1.05; Goedkoop et al. 2009)
Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming potential (GWP); cumulative energy demand (Goedkoop et al. 2008); acidification and eutrophication (Bare et al. 2002); water use and land occupation (Goedkoop et al. 2009). Acidification and eutrophication (Bare et al. 2002), as their LCIA method applies region-specific characterization factors more in line with the geographical scope (USA) of our assessment.
Other information or comments	

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

See example on page 3

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	H. Khoo, H., W. L. Ee, and Valerio Isoni, “Bio-Chemicals from Lignocellulose Feedstock: Sustainability, LCA and the Green Conundrum”, Green Chemistry, Vol. 18, No. 7, 2016, pp. 1912–1922.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Sugarcane bagasse Corn stover Rice straw Wheat straw
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Bio-methanol Bio-formic acid Bio-acetone
Functional unit	1kg of bio-chemical
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Bulk Chemicals
Possible applications	Application as solvent, fuel additive and antifreeze
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	No co-products were discussed
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Land-use has been accounted for these feedstock and quantified. It was determined to be 19 times and 57 times for formic acid and methanol sourced from stover and bagasse respectively
Geographic location, if defined	Location not-specified. However, the significance of the same on overall emission calculation is acknowledged
Data quality	Good, life cycle inventory for the bio-products synthesised has been presented in the supplementary section
Impact assessment method	None stated ; only specific indicators chosen

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Damage categories (endpoint)	None
Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming potential Acidification Eutrophication Photochemical ozone formation Human toxicity Water use
Other information or comments	None

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Example of summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”)	Nuss, Philip, and Kevin H. Gardner, “Attributional Life Cycle Assessment (ALCA) of Polyitaconic Acid Production from Northeast US Softwood Biomass”, The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment, Vol. 18, No. 3, 2013, pp. 603–612.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Wood from forestry (hemicellulose), compared to corn (glucose) and to fossil base.
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Polyitaconic acid (PIA, main product, granulated, water soluble). Co-products include sawlogs and bark, wood pulp and mycelium (protein-rich animal feed)
Functional unit	1 kg of main product
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Chemical additive with a wide range of possible applications including superabsorbents, anti-scaling agents in water treatments, co-builders in detergents, and dispersants for minerals in coatings.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Forest products: by weight. Xylane extraction: by heating value. Fermentation: by dry weight (sensi with market price).
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC is excluded. dLUC is not mentioned, but activity takes place in the US and hence dLUC seems ignored.
Geographic location, if defined	N-E of the U.S.A.
Data quality	Primary data for softwood-derived PIA tranformation (lab and pilot plant runs). Referenced data + secondary data (ecoinvent).
Impact assessment method	Customized method set (see below)
Damage categories (endpoint)	ReCiPe end-point impacts (H/A v1.05; Goedkoop et al. 2009)
Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming potential (GWP); cumulative energy demand (Goedkoop et al. 2008); acidification and eutrophication (Bare et al. 2002); water use and land occupation (Goedkoop et al. 2009). Acidification and eutrophication (Bare et al. 2002), as their LCIA method applies region-specific characterization factors more in line with the geographical scope (USA) of our assessment.
Other information or comments	

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

See example on page 3

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Dros, A. B., O. Larue, A. Reimond, F. De Campo, and M. Pera-Titus, “Hexamethylenediamine (HMDA) from Fossil- vs. Bio-Based Routes: An Economic and Life Cycle Assessment Comparative Study”, Green Chemistry, Vol. 17, No. 10, October 2, 2015, pp. 4760–4772
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Grain Maize Potatoes
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Hexamethylenediamine (HMDA)
Functional unit	1kg of HMDA
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Platform chemical
Possible applications	Used predominantly in the production of polymers especially Nylon 66
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that (Further elaboration not found)
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Co-products (Humins) are assumed to be incinerated
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Land-use ignored due to poor quality inventory and lack of background information
Geographic location, if defined	France, Germany
Data quality	Good, life cycle inventory for the bio-products synthesised has been presented in the supplementary section
Impact assessment method	-
Damage categories (endpoint)	-

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Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming potential Acidification Terrestrial eutrophication Marine Eutrophication Photochemical ozone formation Primary Non renewable fossil-derived energy
Other information or comments	None

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme.

Example of summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”)	Nuss, Philip, and Kevin H. Gardner, “Attributional Life Cycle Assessment (ALCA) of Polyitaconic Acid Production from Northeast US Softwood Biomass”, The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment, Vol. 18, No. 3, 2013, pp. 603–612.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Wood from forestry (hemicellulose), compared to corn (glucose) and to fossil base.
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Polyitaconic acid (PIA, main product, granulated, water soluble). Co-products include sawlogs and bark, wood pulp and mycelium (protein-rich animal feed)
Functional unit	1 kg of main product
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Chemical additive with a wide range of possible applications including superabsorbents, anti-scaling agents in water treatments, co-builders in detergents, and dispersants for minerals in coatings.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Forest products: by weight. Xylane extraction: by heating value. Fermentation: by dry weight (sensi with market price).
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	iLUC is excluded. dLUC is not mentioned, but activity takes place in the US and hence dLUC seems ignored.
Geographic location, if defined	N-E of the U.S.A.
Data quality	Primary data for softwood-derived PIA tranformation (lab and pilot plant runs). Referenced data + secondary data (ecoinvent).
Impact assessment method	Customized method set (see below)
Damage categories (endpoint)	ReCiPe end-point impacts (H/A v1.05; Goedkoop et al. 2009)
Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming potential (GWP); cumulative energy demand (Goedkoop et al. 2008); acidification and eutrophication (Bare et al. 2002); water use and land occupation (Goedkoop et al. 2009). Acidification and eutrophication (Bare et al. 2002), as their LCIA method applies region-specific characterization factors more in line with the geographical scope (USA) of our assessment.
Other information or comments	

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Adom, Felix K., and Jennifer B. Dunn, “Life Cycle Analysis of Corn-Stover-Derived Polymer-Grade L-Lactic Acid and Ethyl Lactate: Greenhouse Gas Emissions and Fossil Energy Consumption”, <i>Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining</i> , Vol. 11, 2017, pp. 258–268.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Corn stover
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Polymer-grade lactic acid (PGLA), ethyl lactate
Functional unit	1 kg of PGLA or 1 kg of ethyl lactate
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	<p>Ethyl lactate can be used as a functional replacement for high-volume, energy intensive, and emissions-intensive petroleum-derived chemicals such as N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone and ethyl acetate.</p> <p>Polymer-grade lactic acid (PGLA) is a high-potential bioproduct and while it is currently made from first-generation feedstocks, its environmental performance could be enhanced through use of cellulosic feedstocks.</p>
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	There is no multifunctionality
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Reported results exclude GHG emissions from potential land-use change associated with feedstock production.
Geographic location, if defined	-
Data quality	Material and energy flows were estimated by developing process simulations with Aspen Plus. The authors built these data into Argonne National Laboratory’s

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

	Greenhouse gases, Regulated Emissions, and Energy use in Transportation (GREET™) model and linked them to existing feedstock production material and energy flow data in GREET in the bioproducts module. Existing upstream GREET data for energy sources (e.g. natural gas, electricity) and process inputs (e.g. corn stover, cellulosic sugars, yeast extract) were used in this analysis
Impact assessment method	GREET model
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and fossil energy consumption (FEC)
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Figure 1. Schematic of PGLA and ethyl lactate production

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Moussa, Hassan I., Ali Elkamel, and Steven B. Young, “Assessing Energy Performance of Bio-Based Succinic Acid Production Using LCA”, <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 139, 2016, pp. 761–769.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): and techno-economic analysis
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Non-food crop
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Succinic acid (SAC) Coproduct: ammonium sulfate
Functional unit	The functional unit is 1 kg industrial grade (99.5% wt) bio-Succinic with specifications and physical properties described in Table 1.
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	To produce bio-plastic
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): retentate and waste disposal of the process
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	A system expansion approach is applied.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	Louisiana, USA
Data quality	Combination of primary, secondary and tertiary data. Up-stream data were obtained from pre-existing datasets in the LCA software and literature. The foreground data used were assessed based on five semi-quantitative data quality indicators for LCIs proposed by Weidema and Wesnaes (1996). The data timeline is less than 3 years and data are geographically representative of the area and facility under study.
Impact assessment method	SimaPro and a LCA software toll developed by Pre Consultants

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Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming potential, non-renewable fossil energy demand , waste heat
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme

Fig. 1. Simplified system boundary for the production of bio-SAC showing system expansion co-product treatment for AMS (Myriant Corporation, 2011).

Fig. 2. The production of bio-SAC process flow diagram (PFD) (both reaction and separation) (Myriant Corporation, 2013).

Table 1
Myriant bio-SAC specification and physical properties (Myriant Corporation, 2013).

Property	Density	Assay	Moisture	Ash	Colour	Lead content
Myriant Bio-SAC	1.57 g/cm ³	99.5 wt %	<0.5 wt%	<0.025 wt%	White crystalline Solid	<2 ppm

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Madival, Santosh, Rafael Auras, Sher Paul Singh, and Ramani Narayan, “Assessment of the Environmental Profile of PLA, PET and PS Clamshell Containers Using LCA Methodology”, Journal of Cleaner Production, Vol. 17, No. 13, 2009, pp. 1183–1194. http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2009.03.015 .
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Corn
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Poly(lactic acid) (PLA)
Functional unit	The functional unit was chosen as 1000 containers of capacity 0.4536 kg (1 lb) each for the packaging of strawberries.
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Poly(lactic acid) (PLA), one of the bio-based polymers derived from corn-based starch, has recently been drawing the attention of the food packaging industry. PLA has progressively created a market for the packaging of fresh cut produce like salads, replacing the conventional petroleum-based polymers like poly-(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) and poly(styrene) (PS).
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Data for PLAs was taken from the literature, and hence no allocation rule was defined for its process.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Not mentioned.
Geographic location, if defined	The geographical scope of the study reflects data from Europe, North America and the Middle East
Data quality	SimaPro software from PRe consultants (The Netherlands) was used as the primary source for the life cycle inventory (LCI). The software contains LCI data for over 2500

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	processes typically used in the packaging industry. The time span of the data ranges from 1999 to 2006.
<i>Impact assessment method</i>	The goal and scope definition of the problem and the inventory analysis were framed and conducted according to ISO 14040 recommendations. The LCA and interpretation were conducted according to ISO 14044 respectively, and ISO 14049 was used for developing function, distinguishing function of comparative systems, establishing inputs and outputs of unit processes and system boundaries. ASTM 7075 was consulted to comply with U.S. standards
<i>Damage categories (endpoint)</i>	
<i>Impact categories (midpoint)</i>	Global warming, aquatic acidification, aquatic eutrophication, aquatic ecotoxicity, ozone depletion, non-renewable energy and respiratory organics, land occupation and respiratory inorganics were the selected midpoint impact categories in this study.
<i>Other information or comments</i>	This paper reports a cradle-to-cradle Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of poly(lactic acid) (PLA) in comparison with poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) and poly(styrene) (PS) thermoformed clamshell containers, used for packaging of strawberries with emphasis on different end-of-life scenarios. It considers all the inputs such as fertilizers, pesticides, herbicides and seed corn required for the growing and harvesting of corn used for manufacturing PLA. For PET and PS, the extraction of crude oil and the entire cracking processes from crude oil through styrene and ethylene glycol and terephthalic acid are considered.

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Fig. 1. Life cycle inventory flow chart for PLA, PET and PS thermoformed containers from cradle to gate, cradle-to-grave, and cradle-to-cradle.(T – transport, T/R – transport with refrigeration).

Fig. 2. Distances from the PLA, PET and PS resin producers NE, SC, and IL respectively to the resin converters in CA and the Strawberry distributor in CA (solid lines). Distances from the Strawberry exporter (CA) to four-warehouse located in WA, CO, NH and FL (dashed lines).

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Kit, Yoong, Leong Pau, and Loke Show, “Economic and Environmental Analysis of PHAs Production Process”, Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy, Vol. 19, No. 7, 2017, pp. 1941–1953.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	glycerol
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs)
Functional unit	1 kg PHA produced
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	-
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	No multifunctionality was considered.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Not mentioned.
Geographic location, if defined	-
Data quality	Chemicals database contained in the WAR algorithm.
Impact assessment method	Based on the potential environmental impact (PEI) balance concept introduced by Hilaly and Sikdar (Hilaly and Sikdar 1995), Young and Cabezas (Young and Cabezas 1999) have introduced WAR algorithm that focuses on waste minimization across the process boundary.
Damage categories (endpoint)	

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Impact categories (midpoint)	The authors covers four local toxicological impact categories which are human toxicity potential by ingestion (HTPI), terrestrial toxicity potential (TTP), human toxicity potential by either inhalation or dermal exposure (HTPE), and aquatic toxicity potential (ATP), and four global atmospheric impacts which are global warming potential (GWP), ozone depletion potential (ODP), photochemical oxidation or smog formation potential (POP), and acidification or acid-rain potential (AP).
Other information or comments	The major process contributing to the environmental impacts in the PHA production is PHA fermentation. Henceforth, the fermenter is the piece of equipment among all the process units that needed most attentions to minimize environmental impacts of the process.

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Fig. 2 Process flowsheet of PHAs production using recovery by surfactant-hypochlorite digestion

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Parajuli, Ranjan, Marie Trydeman Knudsen, Morten Birkved, Sylvestre Njakou Djomo, Andrea Corona, and Tommy Dalgaard, “Environmental Impacts of Producing Bioethanol and Biobased Lactic Acid from Standalone and Integrated Biorefineries Using a Consequential and an Attributional Life Cycle Assessment Approach”, <i>Science of the Total Environment</i> , Vol. 598, 2017, pp. 497–512. http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.04.087 .
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Three biorefinery systems were evaluated and compared: a standalone system producing bioethanol from winter wheat-straw (system A), a standalone system producing biobased lactic acid from alfalfa (system B), and an integrated biorefinery system (system C) combining the two standalone systems and producing both bioethanol and lactic acid.
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Bioethanol and lactic acid
Functional unit	The systems were compared against a common reference flow: “1 MJEtOH + 1 kgLA”, which was set on the basis of products delivered by the system C.
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	-
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Within ALCA, economic allocation method was used to distribute impacts among the main products and the coproducts, whereas within the CLCA system expansion was adopted to avoid allocation.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Indirect LUC was considered as the upstream consequences of occupying a productive land in Denmark during the biomass production. Within CLCA, consequently induced GHG emissions was calculated covering both, (i) upstream consequences of occupying a productive land in Denmark to produce alfalfa and (ii) avoided iLUC assumed to be occurring due to the substitution of the alternative agricultural products, assumed to

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	be displaced by the biobased products. For the first element, iLUC factor of 1.73 t CO ₂ eq ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹ was considered (Schmidt and Muños, 2014). For the second element, the avoided iLUC was calculated based on the equivalent amount of feed products displaced due to the production of feed protein and fodder silage from system B (Fig. 2) and system C (Fig. 3).
Geographic location, if defined	The assumed geographical boundary was Denmark.
Data quality	Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) of the product systems covered both; the background and foreground processes (Figs. 1–3). The background process covered the environmental impacts of producing materials and energy entering to the foreground level. Emission factors for the production of assumed material inputs were based on Ecoinvent v3 (Weidema et al., 2013). The foreground process is the biorefinery system, covering the production and supply of the selected biomasses and their conversion into the selected biobased products.
Impact assessment method	The first three impact categories were assessed using the “EPD” method (Envirodec, 2013), while the ALO was evaluated using the ReCiPe method (Goedkoop et al., 2009). The selected environmental impact categories were among the ISO preliminary list (ISO, 2006).
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	The selected environmental impact categories were: Global Warming Potential (GWP100), Eutrophication Potential (EP), Non-Renewable Energy (NRE) use and Agricultural Land Occupation (ALO).
Other information or comments	The goal of the current study is to evaluate and compare two standalone biorefinery systems with an integrated biorefinery plant, which combine the two standalone systems on the basis of the possible synergy between them. The study also examined whether CLCA and ALCA approach considered for the environmental evaluation of biorefinery systems would arrive with same conclusions. The current study highlights that the benefits of the system integration for bioethanol and biobased lactic acid productions were in terms of higher net savings of GHG emissions, NRE use and EP compared to the standalone systems. However, the obtained ALO was higher in the integrated system than the standalone system.

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Fig. 1. Resource flow and systemboundary of systemA. Electricity produced represents net values of the system(i.e., plant's own consumptions are subtracted). The dotted lines indicate the avoided products considered in the CLCA approach.

Fig. 2. Resource flow and systemboundary of systemB. Electricity produced represents net values of the system (i.e., plant's own consumptions are subtracted). The dotted lines indicate the avoided products considered in the CLCA approach.

Fig. 3. Resource flow and system boundary of system C. Electricity produced represents net values of the system (i.e., plants' own consumptions are subtracted). The dotted lines indicate the avoided products considered in the CLCA approach.

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Forte, Annachiara, Amalia Zucaro, Riccardo Basosi, and Angelo Fierro, “LCA of 1,4-Butanediol Produced via Direct Fermentation of Sugars from Wheat Straw Feedstock within a Territorial Biorefinery”, <i>Materials</i> , Vol. 9, No. 7, 2016, pp. 1–22.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	wheat straw
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	1,4-butanediol (BDO)
Functional unit	1 kg of bio-based BDO.
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	The 1,4-Butanediol (BDO) is an organic compound commonly used as a solvent in the industrial cleaners and in the annual manufacture of over 2.5 million tons of valuable polymers. It represents a key chemical building block used to make several products, such as polybutylene terephthalate (PBT), spandex (lycra, elastane), and polyurethanes (e.g., car bumpers).
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	allocation on economic basis
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Not mentioned.
Geographic location, if defined	Campania Region, Southern Italy
Data quality	The primary data about the bio-based BDO production via direct fermentation of sugars were gathered within the framework of the “EnerbioChem” project (fermentation and purification stages). Differently, a review of pertinent technical and

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	<p>scientific literature was carried out to: (i) check the local availability of wheat straw feedstock; (ii) identify the common agronomic practices for wheat cultivation in the context of Campania Region; and (iii) retrieve material and energetic input for the industrial recovery of fermentable sugars from lignocellulosic feedstock (pre-treatment and enzymatic hydrolysis) and the energetic valorization of unconverted solids inside the designed biorefinery system (electricity and heat production through combustion in a cogeneration plant).</p> <p>As far as the fossil-based BDO was concerned, inventory data were retrieved from the Ecoinvent database v. 2.0: record “butane-1,4-diol, at plant”. As regards the bio-based BDO, the inventory analysis (detailed in Sections 2.2.1 and 2.2.2) quantified flows input (using mass and energy balances) and output (products and pollutant emissions released to air, water and soil) for all the processing steps included in the system boundary (Figure 1).</p>
Impact assessment method	Collected data were analyzed according to ISO standards, by means of SimaPro 8.0.3 software coupled with the ReCiPe (v.1.10, 2013) midpoint hierarchic impact assessment method.
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	The following impact categories were explored in this work: Climate Change (CC, kg CO ₂ eq), Ozone Depletion (OD, kg CFC-11 eq), Terrestrial Acidification (TA, kg SO ₂ eq), Freshwater Eutrophication (FE, kg P eq), Marine Eutrophication (ME, kg N eq), Photochemical Oxidant Formation (POF, kg NMVOC), Particulate Matter Formation (PMF, kg PM ₁₀ eq), Water Depletion (WD, m ³) and Fossil Depletion (FD, kg oil eq).
Other information or comments	The biogenic C incorporated within the bio-based BDO molecule was considered as carbon-neutral. Otherwise, no CO ₂ uptake was included in the present analysis, since the long term storage of biogenic C inside bio-based compounds is highly affected by the final use and durability of the target biopolymers.

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Figure 1. Analyzed production stages of bio-based BDO production chain. The dotted frame shows the “cradle-to-factory gate” system boundary investigated in the study.

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Cok, Benjamin, Ioannis Tsiropoulos, Alexander L. Roes, and Martin K. Patel, “Succinic Acid Production Derived from Carbohydrates: An Energy and Greenhouse Gas Assessment of a Platform Chemical toward a Bio-Based Economy”, <i>Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining</i> , Vol. 8, No. 1, 2014, pp. 16–29.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Two feedstocks are evaluated: dextrose from corn for Europe, the USA, and China and sucrose from sugarcane for Brazil (Center-South region)
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Succinic acid
Functional unit	one kg of high-grade bio-based succinic acid (≥ 99.5 wt-% pure).
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	An important application of bio-based succinic acid could be the production of commodity chemical 1,4-butanediol (1,4-BDO), which is a starting material for tetrahydrofuran (THF) and γ -butyrolactone (GBL). Moreover, the specialty chemical n-methylpyrrolidinone (NMP) can be produced from GBL and bio-based succinic acid could potentially substitute petrochemical adipic acid in the production of polyester polyols to polyurethanes. Moreover, it could also be used as feedstock for the production of polybutylene succinate.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Where allocation is required in this study, the prioritized allocation procedure defined by ISO 14044 is followed i.e. at first avoiding allocation either by subdivision or system expansion and secondly partitioning based on physical relationships (mass allocation).
Inclusion of land use change	Not mentioned.

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

<i>(please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)</i>	
Geographic location, if defined	The geographical coverage is the European Union (EU).
Data quality	This study is performed with the most recent process and design data for bio-based succinic acid production from Reverdia's operating demonstration plant. Data on the petrochemical process is taken from Ecoinvent15 (based on MAN), industry sources (petrochemical succinic acid), and the UNFCCC national inventory submission database (Germany, the UK, France, and Italy), combined with data from ICIS (adipic acid). The feedstock data is based on a study of European dextrose production from corn starch. The inventory for sucrose from sugarcane is based on data from Ecoinvent and the study of Seabra et al.
Impact assessment method	Impact method 'Cumulative Energy Demand' (v1.08) and 'IPCC 2007 GWP 100a' (v1.02), respectively.
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	non-renewable energy use (NREU) and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions
Other information or comments	cradle-to-factory gate in Europe. The biogenic carbon embodied in succinic acid is deducted from the calculated gross GHG emissions.

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Figure 1. Flow diagram of three bio-based succinic acid production processes, i.e. the direct crystallization (DC), electrodialysis (ED), and ammonium sulfate (AS) process.

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Gezae Daful, Asfaw, and Johann F. G??rgens, “Techno-Economic Analysis and Environmental Impact Assessment of Lignocellulosic Lactic Acid Production”, Chemical Engineering Science, Vol. 162, 2017, pp. 53–65. http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2016.12.054 .
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Lignocellulosic biomass (sugarcane bagasse)
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Lactic acid
Functional unit	one tonne of LA produced.
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	LA can be used as feedstock to generate multiple commodity and intermediate chemicals, such as acrylic acid, 1,2-propanediol, pyruvic acid, acetaldehyde, and 2,3-pentanedione. LA can also be polymerized into a biodegradable plastic suitable for packagings, i.e. polylactic acid (PLA).
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	As only LA is produced, no allocation of emissions is needed, however an economic allocation is applied for the sugar mill to distribute the environmental burden among the raw sugars, molasses and bagasse.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Not mentioned.
Geographic location, if defined	Not defined
Data quality	In the inventory analysis for LA production scenarios, the mass and energy balances from an Aspen Plus simulation were used. The eco-invent database of SimaPro was used for the environmental profile of the auxiliary chemicals

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	such as calcium hydroxide ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$) and for the substrate and nutrients used in fermentation.
Impact assessment method	The software package SimaPro v8.0 and ReCiPe Midpoint(H) methodology were used as tools for the environmental impact assessment.
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	ADP Abiotic Depletion Potential measured in kg of Substance eq. AP Acidification Potential measured in kg SO_2 eq. FWEP Freshwater Eutrophication Potential measured in kg PO_3 eq. GWP Global Warming Potential measured in kg CO_2 eq. ODP Ozone Layer Depletion Potential measured in kg CFC-11 eq. (chlorofluorocarbon) HTP Human Toxicity Potential measured in kg 1,4-DB eq. (DB:dichlorobenzene) FWAETP Fresh Water Aquatic Ecotoxicity Potential measured in kg 1,4-DBeq TETP Terrestrial Ecotoxicity Potential measured in kg 1,4-DB eq. POCP Photochemical Oxidation Potential measured in kg C_2H_4 eq.
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Fig. 2. Simplified process flow charts of alternative processes for lactic acid production from lignocellulosic biomass (SCBL) after the steam explosion pretreatment and separation of the liquid and solid fractions. **Scenario 1:** "Conventional" production of lactic acid from the hemicellulose liquid fraction via fermentation using $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ as neutralizer and producing gypsum (CaSO_4) as solid waste along lactic acid. **Scenario 2:** "Conventional" production of lactic acid from the cellu-lignin solid fraction via SSF using $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ as neutralizer and producing gypsum (CaSO_4) as solid waste along lactic acid. **Scenario 3:** Gypsum free lactic acid production using *isolated acid-tolerant thermophilic bacteria* from the hemicellulose liquid fraction via fermentation. **Scenario 4:** Gypsum free lactic acid production using *isolated acid-tolerant thermophilic bacteria* from the cellu-lignin solid fraction via SSF. **Scenario 5:** Gypsum free lactic acid production from the hemicellulose liquid fraction via fermentation using $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ as neutralizer and triethylamine (R_3N) used to recover $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ from Mg-Lactate . **Scenario 6:** Gypsum free lactic acid production from the cellu-lignin solid fraction via SSF using $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ as neutralizer and triethylamine (R_3N) used to recover $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ from Mg-Lactate .

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Morgan-Sagastume, Fernando, Sara Heimersson, Giuseppe Laera, Alan Werker, and Magdalena Svanström, “Techno-Environmental Assessment of Integrating Polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA) Production with Services of Municipal Wastewater Treatment”, <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 137, 2016, pp. 1368–1381.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): and techno-environmental analysis
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Municipal waste water
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA)
Functional unit	The functional unit was the treatment of the same influent wastewater flow rate with treatment to comply with effluent water quality standard for all process configurations (Table 1)
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	To produce bio-plastic
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): The LCA modelling included the WWT processes with the respective PEs as described in Figure 2, as well as production of all process inputs (energy and chemicals) and sludge transport.
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Not mentioned
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	-

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Data quality	This study is based on publishes data and from GabiProfessional 6 and EcolInvent 3.1 databases
Impact assessment method	GabiProfessional 6
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming potential (GWP), acidification potential (AP), eutrophication potential (EP) for fresh water, marine and terrestrial ecosystems, photo-oxidation formation potential (POFP).
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Table 1

Characteristics of the model influent municipal wastewater and treated effluent quality standards considered for modelling all the WWT process configurations. The effluent quality standards were used as guidelines for maximum allowable discharge concentrations with which each WWT process was made to comply.

Parameter	Influent (mg/L)	Effluent (mg/L)
Total suspended solids (TSS)	220	14
Volatile suspended solids (VSS)	165	10
Chemical oxygen demand (COD)	500	50
Total nitrogen (TN)	40	10
NH ₄ ⁺ -N	–	0.5
NO ₃ ⁻ -N	–	8
Total phosphorus (TP)	5	1

Reference WWT process configuration

Alternative WWT process configuration 1

Alternative WWT process configuration 2

Alternative WWT process configuration 3

Alternative WWT process configuration 4

Fig. 2. Schematic process flow diagrams of the five WWT process configurations evaluated in this study. Process stream flows with a high content of solids (sludge or biomass streams) are indicated by dashed lines.

Table 3
Consumption/generation of energy and dosage of chemicals assumed for each unit operation in the energy balance calculations of the different WWT process configurations and the LCA. "A" stands for Alternative process configuration.

Electric energy			
Unit operation	Consumption	WWT process	Source ^a
Mixing			
Primary settling	0.0005 kW/m ³	Reference	–
Advanced primary treatment		A1, A3, A4	
PE1	0.006 kW/m ³	A1-4	Metcalf and Eddy, 1991
Secondary treatment	0.001 kW/m ³	Reference	–
PE2		A1-4	
PE3		A1-4	
Microfiltration			
Primary treatment (Microsieves)	0.01 kW h/m ³	A3	Remy et al., 2014
Thickening			
Primary treatment (Rotary drum thickener)	0.833 kW/(ton TSS/h)	Reference	–
PE3 (Gravity belt thickener)	0.23 kW/(m ³ /h)	A1-4	
Dewatering			
MAD (Decanting centrifuge)	1.875 kW/(m ³ /h)	All	–
PE3 (Decanting centrifuge)		A1-4	
PE1 (Belt filter press)	0.34 kW/(m ³ /h)	A1-4	
Off-site			
Incineration	330 kW h/ton sludge TS	All	Larsen et al., 2010
Thermal energy			
Unit operation	Consumption	WWT process	Source
Off-site			
Consumption for incineration (30% dry solids content)	820 kW h/ton sludge TS	All	Larsen et al., 2010
Generation for incineration	–620 kW h/ton sludge TS		
Chemicals			
Unit operation	Dose	WWT process	Source ^a
Advanced primary treatment			
FeCl ₃ as coagulant	11 mg Fe ³⁺ /L	A1, A3, A4	Helness et al., 2005
Polyacrylamide (PAM)	3 mg PAM/L		
Thickening			
AlCl ₃ (PAC) – Primary treatment	7.5 mg Al ³⁺ /L	1	–
Dewatering			
AlCl ₃ (PAC) – PE1	7.5 mg Al ³⁺ /L	A1-4	–
AlCl ₃ (PAC) – MAD	0.00495 kg AlCl ₃ /kg TS	All	Ryu et al., 2000
AlCl ₃ (PAC) – PE3		A1-4	
Chemical P removal			
FeCl ₃	11 mg Fe ³⁺ /L	All	–
N removal			
Methanol (MeOH) as C source for denitrification	1.9 g MeOH/g NO ₃ ⁻ -N _{rem}	Reference, A1, A2	–
Chemical treatment			
H ₂ SO ₄ – PE3	355 meq/pH/kg TS	A1-4	Morgan-Sagastume et al., 2015 ^b
Off-site incineration			
Flocculant	0.070 kg/ton TS	All	Larsen et al., 2010
Quarry sand	27.7 kg/ton TS		
Calcium chloride	0.65 kg/ton TS		
Metal capturing agent (TMT15/Na3T)	0.05 kg/ton TS		
Sodium persulphate	0.64 kg/ton TS		
Sodium hydroxide	33.78 kg/ton TS		
Ammonia	1.62 kg/ton TS		
Hydrochloric acid	2 kg/ton TS		
Sulphuric acid	1.2 kg/ton TS		
Sodium chloride	0.59 kg/ton TS		

^a Assumed values for this work based on heuristics/professional experience are left blank (–) in the source column.

^b Testing data generated during the referenced study, but not directly cited there.

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Vink, Erwin T H, Steve Davies, and Jeffrey J Kolstad, “The Eco-Profile for Current Ingeo Polylactide Production”, <i>Industrial Biotechnology</i> , Vol. 6, No. 4, 2010, pp. 212–224.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): and techno-economic analysis
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	corn
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Ingeo polylactide biopolymers
Functional unit	The functional unitL 1 kg of Ingeo 2009 (at factory gate).
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): PLA pelletS
Possible applications	To produce bio-plastic
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): retentate and waste disposal of the process
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Not mentioned
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	Blair, Nebraska, USA
Data quality	Data from NatureWorks, Plastic Europe, actual data available from production facilities, field data
Impact assessment method	Utilising the methodology refered in “Boustead I. Eco-profiles of the European Plastics Industry – Methodology.Plastics Europe. (March 2005). http://www.lca.plasticseurope.org ”
Damage categories (endpoint)	

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming potential, greenhouse gas emissions, nonrenewable energy use
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme

Figure 1. Flow diagram of the manufacture of Ingeo polylactide biopolymers

Figure 2. NatureWorks lactic acid production process

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Groot, Wim J., and Tobias Boren, “Life Cycle Assessment of the Manufacture of Lactide and PLA Biopolymers from Sugarcane in Thailand”, <i>International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment</i> , Vol. 15, No. 9, 2010, pp. 970–984.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): and techno-economic analysis
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	sugarcane
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	lactide and PLA (The materials that are assessed are L-lactide, D-lactide, PLLA, nPLA (PLLA with low levels of PDLA), and scPLA (PLLA with increased levels of PDLA).
Functional unit	The functional unit is 1 tonne of material at the factory gate in Thailand
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	To produce bio-plastic
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): retentate and waste disposal of the process
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	system expansion has been used to avoid allocation for the electricity co-product in the sugar mill process. For all other valuable by-products, economic allocation based on selling prices has been used.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	The methodology is not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	Thailand
Data quality	Use of publicly available databases for agrochemicals, other chemicals, fuels, electricity, transportation and waste treatment, and adapted to conditions in Thailand when deemed relevant. Building and demolition of industrial plants and machines

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

	have been included as well. Average data have been applied for all production activities.
Impact assessment method	Customised methodology
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming potential, energy demand, abiotic depletion potential, acidification potential, eutrophication potential, photochemical ozone depletion potential, human toxicity potential, and farm land use
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Fig. 3 Schematic of the production chain from agriculture to PLA

Table 2 The environmental impact categories and characterization factors applied in the LCIA

Category Flow	GWP100 CO2 eq	AP SO2 eq.	EP generic air/water/soil PO4-3 eq.	POCP C2H4 eq.	ADP Crude oil eq/kg	HTP kg DCB eq.
Emissions to air						
CO2	1					
SOx		1		0.048		0.096
NOx		0.7	0.13	0.028		1.2
CH4	25			0.006		
NM-VOC				0.416		0.058
CFC's						
NH3		1.88	0.35			0.1
N2O	298					
HCl		0.88				0.5
CO						
Particles				0.027		0.246
H2S		1.88				0.22
Emissions to water						
COD			0.022			
BOD						
N-tot			0.42			
NH4-N			0.424			
P-tot			3.06			
AOX						
HC						
SO4-2						
Cl-						
Abiotic depletion data						
Natural gas					1.153	
Crude oil					1	
Hard coal					0.6667	
Brown coal					0.2393	
Biomass					0	
Uranium in ore					0.1428	
Iron in ore					4.194E-06	
Copper in ore					0.09652	
Bauxite					1.045E-07	
Sulfur in ore					0.01781	
Limestone					2.090E-07	

GWP values: IPCC 2007. Other values: Guinée et al. 2002

AP acidification potential, EP eutrophication potential, POCP photochemical ozone creation potential, ADP abiotic resource depletion potential, HTP human toxicity potential

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Koller, Martin, Daniel Sandholzer, Anna Salerno, Gerhart Braunegg, and Michael Narodslawsky, “Biopolymer from Industrial Residues: Life Cycle Assessment of Poly(hydroxyalkanoates) from Whey”, <i>Resources, Conservation and Recycling</i> , Vol. 73, 2013, pp. 64–71. http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2013.01.017 .
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): and techno-economic analysis
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Whey
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Poly(hydroxyalkanoates)
Functional unit	Not defined
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	To produce bio-plastics
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): retentate and waste disposal of the process
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Not described
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	LUC was not considered
Geographic location, if defined	-
Data quality	Evidence and data gathered in laboratory experiments as well as preliminary experiments on the scale of 300 L bioreactors.
Impact assessment method	The software SPIonExcel was developed to make the assessment methodology easily applicable and operator-friendly The SPI was developed by Narodslawsky and Krotscheck (1995) and is based on the assumption that a sustainable economy has its fundamentals on solar radiation as natural income

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Assessment by using the sustainable process index (SPI), a member of the ecological footprint family - Ecological footprint
Other information or comments	Human activities, however, impact on the environment by their need for resources, energy, manpower and area for installations as well as emissions, waste and noise (Schnitzer and Ulgiati, 2007). The SPI evaluates these ecological pressures according to their impact on the availability of our planet's surface to sustainably convert solar income to services for society. It calculates the area necessary to embed an industrial process sustainably into the ecosphere, retaining the water and soil compartments as well as the atmosphere in a sustainable state

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Fig. 1. Process steps, inputs and outputs of the PHA-production process. The broken line incorporates the process steps, the full line the system boundaries of the life cycle assessment.

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Khoo, Hsien Hui, Reginald B H Tan, and Kevin W L Chng, “Environmental Impacts of Conventional Plastic and Bio-Based Carrier Bags”, <i>International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment</i> , Vol. 15, No. 3, 2010, pp. 284–293.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): and techno-economic analysis
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Crop
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Poly(hydroxyalkanoates) or PHA
Functional unit	The functional unit of the LCA is defined as a “standard bag” with the dimensions 10 by 14 in., thickness 0.06 mm. The mass load of a plastic bag, according to its functional unit, is $4.90 \cdot 10^{-3}$ kg.
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	To produce bio-plastic bags
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): retentate and waste disposal of the process
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	At the refinery, mass-based allocation is used to determine the energy requirements and associated emissions of products.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	LUC was not considered
Geographic location, if defined	Singapore
Data quality	The database for the production of raw materials and energy are sourced from various reports and available database
Impact assessment method	The Environmental Development of Industrial Products 2003 impact assessment method is used
Damage categories (endpoint)	

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Impact categories (midpoint) Global warming potential, acidification, and photochemical ozone formation

Other information or comments

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Fig. 2 Life cycle stages of bio-bag production

Table 2 Energy requirements for PP bag production

Fossil fuel production (including other fossil fuel inputs; treatment/processing; compression of natural gas at station)	
Off-shore crude oil exploration and production	24.3 MJ/kg crude oil
Natural gas exploration and production	11.34 MJ/kg natural gas
Refinery processes	
Crude oil distillation + natural gas cracking	4.92 MJ/kg crude oil
PP bag manufacturer	
Monomer production and polymerization (PP)	19.05 MJ/kg PP monomer
Blow film extrusion to produce PP bag	Negligible

Table 4 Air emissions from energy supplied to PP bag production

Emissions (kg/MJ)	Singapore electricity mix: for supply of energy to refinery and plastic manufacturer	Malaysia electricity mix: for supply of energy for natural gas exploration and production	Natural gas-fired power: for supply of energy for crude oil exploration and production
CO	4.94E-05	1.11E-05	7.50E-07
CO ₂	1.56E-01	1.60E-01	2.06E-01
CH ₄	2.26E-06	1.00E-06	5.33E-06
N ₂ O	8.42E-07	n.a.	1.41E-06
NO _x	2.04E-03	1.94E-03	2.64E-05
SO _x	3.31E-04	5.83E-07	5.56E-07
NM VOC	6.03E-06	5.83E-06	2.78E-06

Table 5 Pipeline and marine transport emissions

Emissions (g/ton km)	Nonroad transport		Emissions (g/km)	Road transport EURO 4 truck (distance=20km)
	Pipeline (distance=730km)	Shipment (distance=8,000km)		
CO	0	1.20E-01	CO	6.30E-01
CO ₂	1.00E+01	3.00E+01	CO ₂	3.51E+01
CH ₄	2.00E-02	4.00E-02	CH ₄	6.00E-02
NO _x	2.00E-02	4.00E-01	NO _x	3.30E-01
VOC	2.00E-02	1.00E-01	VOC	4.00E-02

Table 6 Direct emissions to air from agriculture and wet milling stages

Air emissions	Agriculture (kg/kg corn)	Wet milling (kg/kg glucose)
CO ₂	-0.857 (sequestered)	3.5E-01
N ₂ O	6.51E-04	0

Table 7 Energy requirements for bio-bag production

Agriculture/farming	
Corn production	2.5 MJ/kg corn
Wet milling	
Corn→glucose	4.9 MJ/kg glucose
Fermentation and recovery	
PHA	52.53 MJ/kg PHA
Blow film extrusion to produce bio-bag	Negligible

Table 8 Air emissions from energy supplied to bio-bag production

Emission parameters (kg/MJ)	Energy supply scenarios to U.S. agriculture, wet milling, and PHA production (fermentation)			
	U.S. energy mix	Coal-fired power	NGCC	Geothermal
CO	1.97E-05	3.72E-05	7.50E-06	0
CO ₂	1.88E-01	2.69E-01	1.03E-01	2.25E-02
CH ₄	5.04E-06	7.44E-04	1.22E-05	2.08E-04
N ₂ O	2.93E-06	1.70E-06	2.03E-07	0
NO _x	4.19E-04	8.44E-04	2.64E-05	0
SO _x	8.71E-04	1.78E-03	5.56E-07	8.33E-06
NM VOC	2.73E-06	4.40E-06	2.78E-06	0

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Sun, Xiao-Zheng, Tomoaki Minowa, Katsunobu Yamaguchi, and Yutaka Genchi, “Evaluation of Energy Consumption and Greenhouse Gas Emissions from Poly(phenyllactic Acid) Production Using Sweet Sorghum”, <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 87, 2015, pp. 208–215. http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0959652614009718 .
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): and techno-economic analysis
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Sweet Sorghum
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Poly(phenyllactic Acid)
Functional unit	The functional unit in our analysis is 1 kg of produced poly(PhLA) leaving the factory gate.
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	To produce bio-plastic
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): retentate and waste disposal of the process
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Not mentioned
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	Any effect on land use change on the GHG emissions was not included in this study
Geographic location, if defined	Japan
Data quality	This study is based on publishes data mainly from laboratory studies
Impact assessment method	The methodology of this study, a cradle-to-factory-gate analysis, is the same as that of other similar studies conducted on PLA (Gerngross and Slater, 2000; Vink et al., 2010) and PHA (Gerngross, 1999; Harding et al., 2007).

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Fossil energy production, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Fig. 1. Simplified flow diagram of the overall process.

Table 1
Key parameters of sweet sorghum (SS) production (base case).

Parameters	Values	Units	Data source	Emission factor ^a
Seed	11.9	kg/ha	Shimizu et al., 2009	
Nitrogen fertilizer	70.0	kg N/ha	Sun and Yamana, 2012	6.08 kg CO ₂ eq/kg N
Phosphate fertilizer	10.0	kg P/ha	JMAFF, 2010	3.07 kg CO ₂ eq/kg P
Potash fertilizer	10.0	kg K/ha	JMAFF, 2010	0.51 kg CO ₂ eq/kg K
Herbicide	5	L/ha	Shimizu et al., 2009	5.99 kg CO ₂ eq/L
Diesel	240.7	L/ha	Calculated in this study	2.90 kg CO ₂ eq/L
Gasoline	9.1	L/ha	Calculated in this study	2.81 kg CO ₂ eq/L
SS yield	61.4	t/ha	Average value in Japan	
Fuel efficiency	4.04	km/L	20 t diesel truck	
Transportation distance	88.0	km	Calculated in this study	7.20 kg CO ₂ eq/t SS

^a Calculated using IDEA (Inventory Database for Environmental Analysis). 32.9 MJ/L and 36.1 MJ/L were adopted as the lower heating values of gasoline and diesel, respectively.

Table 2

Key parameters of sugar extraction and bagasse generation (base case).

Parameters	Values	Units	Data source
Moisture content of SS ^a	0.76	kg/kg	Sun and Yamana, 2012
Efficiency of sugar extraction	80%		Badalov, 2008
Brix of juice	15%		Nitta et al., 2008
Sucrose:glucose:fructose	7:2:1	(Juice component)	Wu et al., 2010
Invertase input to sucrose	0.6	g/100 g sucrose	Yoshii et al., 1993
Emission factor of invertase	2.63	kg CO ₂ eq/kg	IDEA ^b
Water input	305	kg/t SS	Calculated in this study
Emission factor of water	0.13	kg CO ₂ eq/kg	IDEA
Power consumption of juice extraction	15	kWh/t SS	Zuurbier and Vooren, 2008
Moisture content of bagasse	0.5	kg/kg	Badalov, 2008
Bagasse yield	306.2	kg/t SS	Calculated in this study
LHV ^c of bagasse	7.5	MJ/kg	Sun et al., 2013
Power generation efficiency	17.7%		Sun et al., 2013

^a SS = sweet sorghum.

^b IDEA = Inventory Database for Environmental Analysis.

^c LHV = lower heating value.

Table 3

Key parameters of PhLA fermentation process (base case).

Parameters	Values ^a	Units	Emission factor ^b
PhLA plant scale	2000	t/year	
Operating days of plant	100	days/year	
Reaction temperature	37	°C	
Reaction time	144	h	
Sweet sorghum	100.0	kg/kg PhLA	
Water	40.4	kg/kg PhLA	0.13 kg CO ₂ eq/m ³
Na ₂ HPO ₄	293.5	g/kg PhLA	3.94 kg CO ₂ eq/kg
KH ₂ PO ₄	146.8	g/kg PhLA	3.05 kg CO ₂ eq/kg
NaCl	24.5	g/kg PhLA	0.11 kg CO ₂ eq/kg
NH ₄ Cl	48.9	g/kg PhLA	0.92 kg CO ₂ eq/kg
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	24.5	g/kg PhLA	1.43 kg CO ₂ eq/kg
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	0.7	g/kg PhLA	3.34 kg CO ₂ eq/kg
HCl	2.4	g/kg PhLA	0.58 kg CO ₂ eq/kg
Kanamycin sulfate	0.02	g/kg PhLA	1686 kg CO ₂ eq/kg
Bacto tryptone	489.2	g/kg PhLA	1.85 kg CO ₂ eq/kg
Yeast extract	244.6	g/kg PhLA	2.63 kg CO ₂ eq/kg
NaOH	489.2	g/kg PhLA	1.32 kg CO ₂ eq/kg
PhLA yield/glucose	16.0%		

^a Calculated in this study based on (Konishi and Takaya, 2012; Fujita et al., 2013).

^b Calculated using IDEA (Inventory Database for Environmental Analysis).

Table 4
 Key parameters of PhLA separation and purification (base case).

Parameters	Values	Data source
(Methanol + Hexane)/PhLA (Methanol:Hexane = 1:1)	12:1	Konishi and Takaya, 2012; Nishimura and Ishikawa, 2003
Toluene/PhLA	3.3:1	Nishimura and Ishikawa, 2003
Recovery rate of methanol	98%	Hofen et al., 2006
Emission factor of methanol	1.54	kg CO ₂ eq/kg, IDEA ^a
Recovery of hexane	98%	Nishimura and Ishikawa, 2003
Emission factor of hexane	1.99	kg CO ₂ eq/kg, IDEA
Recovery rate of toluene	96%	Nishimura and Ishikawa, 2003
Emission factor of toluene	1.82	kg CO ₂ eq/kg, IDEA
Efficiency of separation and purification	70%	Takaya, 2013
Hydrochloric acid (HCl, 35%)	4.2	mL/L fermentation liquid
Hydrochloric acid (HCl, 35%)	0.58	kg CO ₂ eq/kg, IDEA
Waste solid	123.5	kg/t SS ^b
LHV ^c of waste solid	6.7	MJ/kg, Eriksson, 2009

^a IDEA = Inventory Database for Environmental Analysis.

^b SS = sweet sorghum.

^c LHV = lower heating value.

(a) Mass balance

(b) Energy balance

Fig. 2. Mass and energy balances of the overall process.

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Mu, Dongyan, Thomas Seager, P. Suresh Rao, and Fu Zhao, “Comparative Life Cycle Assessment of Lignocellulosic Ethanol Production: Biochemical versus Thermochemical Conversion”, <i>Environmental Management</i> , Vol. 46, No. 4, 2010, pp. 565–578.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Lignocellulosic residues from agriculture, forestry and municipal solid waste. 1. poplar wood chips 2. corn stover 3. waste paper 4. wheat straw
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Lignocellulosic Ethanol (basic) Co-products : electricity (for biochemical conversion)- mixed alcohols (for thermochemical conversion) By-products : Linear alcohols
Functional unit	1 L of ethanol produced either through biochemical and thermochemical conversion
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Use of lignocellulosic residues from agriculture, forestry and municipal solid waste can increase ethanol production without competing with food for humans and feed for animals and create another source of revenue for farmers and residents of rural regions, offer immediate and sustained GHG advantages to replace fossil fuels.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): (conversion)
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Substitution method is used (Gnansounou et al., 2009)

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	The productivity of the land and the percent of available land devoted to the production of lignocellulosic feedstocks determine the feedstock availability with in certain economically viable collection radius, which in turn limits the size of an ethanol plant. The study has based on another study by NREL that suggests for corn stover, plant sizes below 2000 tons/day (dry basis) shows rapidly increasing overall costs. Therefore, the biorefineries investigated in the study are selected to have the capacity of processing 2000 ton of dry lignocellulosic feedstock per day.
Geographic location, if defined	US
Data quality	LC inventory data of the material and energy involved are extracted from SimaPro7.1 and Ecoinvent 2.0 database
Impact assessment method	Not defined - sensitivity analysis is performed
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Fossil fuel energy consumption, water consumption, GHG (kg CO ₂ eq.)
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Please insert here additional information such as flow diagram, description of the life cycle stages (notably the transformation steps), tables of inventory data (if available), and technical viability of the production scheme

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of thermochemical conversion and biochemical conversion

Table 1 Characteristics of lignocellulosic feedstock investigated

	Poplar wood chips	Corn stover	Waste paper	Wheat straw
Ultimate analysis				
C %	50.9	45.3	41.3	43.9
H %	6.0	5.6	5.8	5.3
O %	41.9	43.3	51.9	39.8
N %	0.2	0.6	0.0	0.6
S %	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2
Composition (dry basis)				
Cellulose %	43.2	37.4	58.6	32.6
Hemicelluloses %	21.2	27.6	11.2	22.6
Lignin %	23.7	18	28.8	16.9
Others %	11.0	11.8	0.4	17.7
Ash (dry basis) %	0.9	5.2	1.1	10.2
Moisture %	50.0	15.0	11.2	10.1
LHV kJ/kg (dry basis)	18,718	17,957	21,443	17,832

Table 2 Material and energy flows of biochemical and thermochemical conversion facility of 2,000 ton/day capacity (unit: kg/hr if not specified)

	Wood chips	Corn stover	Waste paper	Wheat straw
Thermochemical conversion				
Biomass (wet)	166,667	98,039	93,833	92,696
Water consumption	54,067	52,591	58,811	52,499
Air	325,367	354,742	425,875	355,582
MgO	3	18	4	35
Bed materials	225	225	225	225
Synthesis catalyst	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.9
Tar reforming catalyst	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9
Oxidizer for S recovery	118	132	0	210
Ethanol	22,101	21,203	25,319	21,055
Mixed alcohol	3,988	3,826	4,568	3,799
Sulfur (solid)	49	55	0	87
Sand and ash	1,281	7,243	1,462	14,235
Carbon dioxide	105,800	89,346	67,615	85,441
In-plant power use (kW)	7,994	7,799	8,692	7,767
Biochemical conversion				
Biomass (wet)	166,667	98,039	93,833	92,696
Water consumption	127,166	186,649	231,121	194,022
Enzyme	608	613	658	521
Lime	2,395	2,395	2,395	2,395
Sulfuric acid	3,288	3,288	3,288	3,288
Corn steep liquor	1,288	1,232	1,323	1,048
Diammonium phosphate	152	154	165	131
Wastewater treatment chemicals (10% urea and 90% NaOH)	54	55	59	46
Ethanol	22,686	22,898	24,589	19,470
Electricity output (kW)	19,543	18,284	22,989	20,299
Solid wastes	5,543	6,808	6,808	6,808
Carbon dioxide	111,627	85,765	78,587	96,453

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	González-García, Sara, M. Teresa Moreira, Gumersindo Feijoo, and Richard J. Murphy, “Comparative Life Cycle Assessment of Ethanol Production from Fast-Growing Wood Crops (Black Locust, Eucalyptus and Poplar)”, <i>Biomass and Bioenergy</i> , Vol. 39, 2012, pp. 378–388.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Fast growing wood crops: 1. eucalyptus 2. black locust 3. poplar
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Blend rich Ethanol : E85 (85% ethanol and 15% gasoline by volume)
Functional unit	This paper was sub-divided for convenience into two main parts: i) the first part related to the ethanol production system so the FU was based on 1 kg of ethanol, ii) the second part related to the FFV driving function so the FU was based on 1 km distance driven by a mid-size FFV.
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Use of E85 in flexi-fuel vehicles instead of gasoline (GG)
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	No allocation criteria were applied in this study since feedstock cultivation only yields one product
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	No inclusion of land use change
Geographic location, if defined	-
Data quality	In this study, inventory data for SRC cultivation activities are primary field data,

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

	collected on-site via surveys and interviews
Impact assessment method	CML methodology
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Fossil fuel use (FF), Global warming potential over 100 years (GWP ₁₀₀), photochemical oxidant creation potential (POCP), Acidification potential (AP) and Eutrophication potential (EP).
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Fig. 1 – System boundaries for eucalyptus, black locust and poplar based ethanol E85 life cycle. White boxes are common to all the feedstocks; grey boxes only occur for some.

Table 3 – LCI for 1 t of lignocellulosic ethanol production (S3).

Materials	Unit	Eucalyptus	Black locust	Poplar
Inputs from technosphere				
Feedstock (green biomass)	t	5.92	6.06	4.06
Feedstock (oven dry biomass)	t	3.44	3.64	3.13
Vinyl acetate	kg	1.64	1.73	1.12
Sulphuric acid	kg	92.9	98.2	117.7
Lime	kg	67.7	71.6	85.8
Diammonium phosphate	kg	1.14	1.10	1.15
Corn steep liquor	kg	8.7	8.7	8.9
Enzyme	kg	374	371	299
Nutrient feed	kg	2.21	9.56	2.22
Energy^a				
Electricity	MWh	1.21	1.28	1.10
Steam	GJ	68.2	71.7	61.7
Outputs to technosphere				
Ethanol (99.5%)	t	1.00	1.00	1.00
Wastes to treatment				
Gypsum (to Landfill)	kg	225	239	261
Ash (to Landfill)	kg	130	47.7	64.8

a All assumed to be supplied from on-site co-generation from bio-solids from distillation, syrup and biogas.

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Spatari, Sabrina, David M. Bagley, and Heather L. MacLean, “Life Cycle Evaluation of Emerging Lignocellulosic Ethanol Conversion Technologies”, <i>Bioresource Technology</i> , Vol. 101, No. 2, 2010, pp. 654–667.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	1.corn stover 2.switchgrass
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Lignocellulosic ethanol
Functional unit	<p>All metrics are normalized to the volumetric flowrate QE (L/h) of ethanol produced in the conversion facility, which is also the functional unit:</p> $\dot{Q}_E = \dot{M}_F \frac{\alpha}{\rho_{EtOH}} \times \sum_{i=1}^5 Y_i \times Y_{i,E}. \quad (1)$ <p>In Eq. (1), \dot{M}_F represents the input mass flow rate of feedstock (kg/h); α is the ethanol recovery efficiency following distillation, taken as 99.4% and 99.7%, for near and mid-term models, respectively; and ρ_{EtOH} is the density of ethanol (0.789 kg/L). The term Y_i is the yield (by weight) of sugar i, and $Y_{i,E}$ is the yield (by weight) of ethanol from sugar i where $i = 1$ to 5 corresponds to glucose, xylose, arabinose, galactose and mannose, respectively. The yield of each sugar following pre-treatment for the hemicellulose sugars, and hydrolysis for the glucose in the cellulose fraction is estimated as follows: $Y_i = f_i \times c_j \times \beta_k$, (2) where f_i corresponds to the fraction of the sugar polymer in the feedstock while c_j is the conversion efficiency for converting each sugar polymer to sugar where, $j = 1$ for converting glucan to glucose during hydrolysis, and $j = 2-5$ for converting xylan to xylose, arabinan to arabinose, galactan to galactose and mannan to mannose, respectively, in the pre-treatment step. The term β_k is a stoichiometric conversion parameter for the fermentation of each sugar to ethanol. β_1 and β_2 correspond to six-carbon (C6) and five-carbon (C5) sugars, respectively, and are determined by Eqs. (3) and (4):</p> $\beta_1 = c_{C6} \frac{MW_{C6}}{MW_{C6_polymer}}, \quad (3)$ $\beta_2 = c_{C5} \frac{MW_{C5}}{MW_{C5_polymer}}. \quad (4)$ <p>In Eqs. (3) and (4) c_{C6} is the theoretical conversion of C6 sugars to ethanol (0.511 g ethanol/g C6-sugar) and c_{C5} is the theoretical conversion of C5 sugars to ethanol (0.504 g ethanol/g C5-sugar). $MW_{C6}/MW_{C6_polymer}$ (180/162) and $MW_{C5}/MW_{C5_polymer}$ (150/132) represent the fractions of molecular weights of the C6 sugars to C6 sugar polymers and C5 sugar to C5 sugar polymers, respectively.</p>
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Possible applications	Use of lignocellulosic ethanol in light-duty vehicles compared to gasoline and corn ethanol fueled vehicles.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	No allocation criteria were applied in this study since feedstock cultivation only yields one product
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	No inclusion of land use change
Geographic location, if defined	US
Data quality	One set of input data was developed from laboratory or process development unit (PDU) scale data presented in the literature. For models using this data set, Monte Carlo analysis was applied to consider uncertainty in the predicted performance. The second set of input data is generated from chemical plant designs simulated by ethanol technology developers using Aspen Plus software.
Impact assessment method	LCA (ISO 2006) to compare the energy and material inputs and environmental emissions associated with eight near-term (c. 2010) and two advanced mid-term (c. 2020) lignocellulosic ethanol conversion technologies in the United States.
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Fossil energy use, Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Table 2
LCA variable input specifications (variable range and statistics) used in near-term Monte Carlo simulations and near- and mid-term input specifications for Aspen simulations.

Variable	Variable notation	Monte Carlo simulation				Aspen simulation		
		Range		Mean	Statistic	Distribution	Near-term ^a Point values	Mid-term ^d Point values
		Low 2.5th percentile	High 97.5th percentile					
Feedstocks								
Corn stover (CS)								
Glucan fraction (g glucan/g CS)	f_{glucan}	0.306	0.381	0.361	SD = 0.035	Student T	0.374	
Xylan fraction (g xylan/g CS)	f_{xylan}	0.159	0.216	0.196	SD = 0.015	Logistic	0.211	
Switchgrass (SG)								
Glucan fraction (g glucan/g SG)	f_{glucan}	0.268	0.375	0.334	SD = 0.023	Logistic	0.323	
Xylan fraction (g xylan/g SG)	f_{xylan}	0.176	0.249	0.219	SD = 0.047	Student T	0.211	
Pre-treatment								
Dilute acid (NREL)								
Hemicellulose conversion (g hemicellulose sugar/g hemicellulose)	c_j	0.6	0.75	0.675	SD = 0.038	Normal	0.75	
Hydrolysis conversion (g glucose/g glucan)	c_j	0.616	0.654	0.635	SD = 0.0097	Normal	0.8	
AFEX								
Hemicellulose conversion	c_j	0.65	0.85	0.75	SD = 0.051	Normal	0.776	
Hydrolysis conversion	c_j	0.9	1	0.95	SD = 0.0097	Normal	0.95	
Fermentation								
Glucose-to-ethanol conversion (fraction of theoretical yield)	$Y_{glu,eth}$	0.85	0.95	0.90	SD = 0.026	Normal	0.92 ^b 0.95 ^c	
Xylose-to-ethanol conversion (fraction of theoretical yield)	$Y_{xyl,eth}$	0.5	0.90	0.70	SD = 0.103	Normal	0.85 ^b 0.85 ^c	
Arabinose-to-ethanol conversion (fraction of theoretical yield)	$Y_{a,eth}$	0.01	0.72	0.283	Mode = 0	Triangular	0 ^b 0.85 ^c	
Galactose-to-ethanol conversion (fraction of theoretical yield)	$Y_{gal,eth}$	0.01	0.72	0.283	Mode = 0	Triangular	0 ^b 0.85 ^c	
Mannose-to-ethanol conversion (fraction of theoretical yield)	$Y_{man,eth}$	0.01	0.72	0.283	Mode = 0	Triangular	0 ^b 0.85 ^c	

Notes: SD, standard deviation.

^a Near-term Aspen simulations with the SG feedstock compositions were modified from simulations run with the CS feedstock to adjust for differences in cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin concentrations as was done in previous LCA models (Spatari et al., 2005). Yields of ethanol from glucose, xylose, arabinose, galactose, and mannose for the near-term models were estimated for two scenarios, one in which the fermentation yield in the first line of each row was assumed, and one in which the fermentation yields in the second line shown were assumed.

^b The Aspen simulations whereby only glucose and xylose are fermented (first line) were set to correspond to Aspen model simulations investigated by the CAFI group, and summarized in Wyman et al. (2005a,b), and in costing models by Eggeman and Elander (2005), and represent plausible near-term ethanol yield estimates.

^c The Aspen simulations whereby all five sugars are fermented (second line) were set to correspond to Aspen model simulations reported by Aden et al. (2002) and assumed by Sheehan et al. (2003) in their LCA model of corn stover, and represent more optimistic estimates of ethanol yields relative to the estimates shown in the first line.

^d A Monte Carlo simulation was not undertaken for the mid-term models due to the difficulty in assigning plausible probability distributions to the advanced SG feedstock and mature CBP technology assumed in those models. Only the advanced SG feedstock was examined for the mid-term Aspen simulations based on the model design reported by Laser et al. (2009).

Fig. 1. Plant design model for the biochemical conversion of lignocellulose to ethanol. Notes: The model assumes energy recovery for steam and electricity production from lignocellulose fractions not converted to ethanol. Adapted from model designs described by Aden et al. (2002) and Laser et al. (2009). CBP, consolidated bioprocessing; SSCF, simultaneous saccharification and co-fermentation.

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Singh, Anoop, Deepak Pant, Nicholas E. Korres, Abdul-Sattar Nizami, Shiv Prasad, and Jerry D. Murphy, “Key Issues in Life Cycle Assessment of Ethanol Production from Lignocellulosic Biomass: Challenges and Perspectives”, <i>Bioresource Technology</i> , Vol. 101, No. 13, 2010, pp. 5003–5012. http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0960852409015673
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	1. Grass 2. Residues from arable land 3. Residues from forest 4. Energy crops Possible by products: lignin and pentose sugars
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	lignocellulosic bioethanol
Functional unit	The paper compares different studies and provides the following FU: Per unit energy/per unit land, per km, Mj of fuel equivalent, 1 ha/km, per mg of biomass feedstock
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Lignocellulosic material could support the sustainable production of liquid transportation fuels
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	The paper describes allocation, and suggests that allocation when possible should be avoided (ISO, 2006), either through the division of the whole process into sub-processes related to co-products or by expanding the system boundaries (substitutional approach) to include the additional functions
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for)	The study provides a comparison table that presents studies where LUC is considered and others that LUC is not considered.

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

<i>direct and indirect LUC</i>	
Geographic location, if defined	
Data quality	No data input. The study presents data from other studies
Impact assessment method	ISO 14042, Life cycle impact assessment (ISO, 1998)
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Abiotic depletion, Global warming potential, ozone layer depletion, human toxicity, marine water toxicity, acidification and eutrophication, Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and air pollutant emissions, global climate change, air quality, soil health impacts
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Table 1
Comparison of LCA methodology adopted in various studies.

Criteria	Monti et al. (2009)	Luo et al. (2009b)	Spatari et al. (2005)	Stichnothe and Azapagic (2009)	Sheehan et al. (2004)	Mdaughlin et al. (2002)
Country	Italy	The Netherlands	Canada	UK	USA	USA
Biomass source	Switchgrass, Cynara, Giant reed and Miscanthus	Corn stover	Switchgrass and corn-stover	Household and biodegradable municipal waste	Corn stover	Switchgrass
System adopted	Cradle to farm gate	Energy product to gate	Cradel to wheel	Cradel to grave	Cradel to grave	Cradel to grave
Functional unit	Per unit energy/per unit land	Not defined	Per km	MJ of fuel equivalent	1 ha/1 km	Per mg of biomass feedstock
System boundary	Defined as scope of the study	Well defined	Defined	Defined	Defined	Not defined
Land-use change	Not considered	Not considered	Considered	–	Considered	–
Impact analyzed	Abiotic depletion, global warming potential, ozone layer depletion, human toxicity, marine water toxicity, acidification and eutrophication	–	GHG emissions and air pollutant emissions	Global warming potential	Global climatechange, air quality, and soil health impacts	GHG emissions
Sensitivity analysis	–	–	Present	–	–	–
Reference system	Conventional wheat-maize rotation	–	Low sulfur reformulated gasoline	Petrol	Gasoline	Conventional gasoline or hard coal

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Kim, Seungdo, and Bruce E. Dale, “Life Cycle Assessment of Fuel Ethanol Derived from Corn Grain via Dry Milling”, <i>Bioresource Technology</i> , Vol. 99, No. 12, 2008, pp. 5250–5260.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Corn grain
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Corn based ethanol
Functional unit	The FU is defined as bioethanol derived from corn grain used in an E10 fueled vehicle and the reference flow in this study is defined as 1kg of ethanol
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Lignocellulosic material could support the sustainable production of liquid transportation fuels
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Allocation not mentioned.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	LUC is not considered.
Geographic location, if defined	US: Hardin County in Iowa (referred to as HIA), Fulton County in Illinois (FIL), Tuscola County in Michigan (TMI), Morrison County in Minnesota (MMN), Freeborn County in Minnesota (FMN), Macon County in Missouri (MMO), Hamilton County in Nebraska (HNE), and Codington County in South Dakota (CSD).
Data quality	The study uses four-year average values between 2000 and 2003 for corn yield and agronomic inputs. The inventory information have been collected form the

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

	literature and commercial LCA databases
Impact assessment method	The characterization factors for regional impacts are adapted from the TRACI model. An eco-efficiency analysis is done by plotting the economic index versus the environmental index
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Nonrenewable energy consumption, 100 years Global warming potential, acidification and eutrophication, Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and photochemical smog formation
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Table 2
Data sources

Process	References
Climate and soil data in the cropping site	National Climatic Data Center (2005), NSSC Soil Survey Laboratory (2005)
US electricity production system	Kim and Dale (2005c)
Soybean milling process	Sheehan et al. (1998)
Nitrogen fertilizer/phosphorus fertilizer	Office of Industrial Technologies (2000), Kim and Overcash (2000), International Fertilizer Industry Association (1998, 2001)
Urea	Office of Industrial Technologies (2000), Pagani and Zardi (1994)
Other data (e.g., fuels and potassium fertilizer)	DEAM™ (Ecobilan, 2005)

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Kim, Seungdo, and Bruce Dale, “Ethanol Fuels: E10 or E85 – Life Cycle Perspectives (5 Pp)”, The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment, Vol. 11, No. 2, 2006, pp. 117–121. http://link.springer.com/article/10.1065/lca2005.02.201%5Cnhttp://link.springer.com/content/pdf/10.1065/lca2005.02.201.pdf .
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Corn grain and corn stover
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Ethanol : E10 E85
Functional unit	Two types of functional units are applied in this study: ethanol production-oriented (arable land or quantity of biomass used in ethanol fuel) and traveling distance oriented. An ethanol production-oriented functional unit is defined as 1 kg of ethanol, indicating that the capacity of bioethanol production is a constraint factor, namely, the supply of bioethanol is limited. This functional unit also implies that the availability of agricultural land (or biomass) for ethanol production is constrained. A traveling distance oriented functional unit is defined as 1 km driven by an ethanol fueled vehicle. This functional unit implies that the supply of bioethanol is unlimited. Thus, arable land (or biomass) for producing ethanol is unconstrained in this functional unit.
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Ethanol as substitute transportation fuel for gasoline.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	The avoided product systems for coproducts in wet milling (e.g., corn gluten meal (CGM), corn gluten feed (CGF) and corn oil) are also included in the system boundary to allocate the environmental burdens to ethanol. Therefore, the allocations are done

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

	by introducing alternative product systems – the system expansion approach.
Inclusion of land use change <i>(please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)</i>	LUC is not considered.
Geographic location, if defined	US
Data quality	From literature
Impact assessment method	The characterization factors for regional impacts are adapted from the TRACI model.
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Natural resources used, Nonrenewable energy, Global warming potential, acidification and eutrophication.
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

NAN

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Hsu, David D, Daniel Inman, Garvin A Heath, Edward J Wolfrum, Margaret K Mann, and Andy Aden, “Life Cycle Environmental Impacts of Selected U.S. Ethanol Production and Use Pathways in 2022.”, <i>Environmental Science & Technology</i> , Vol. 44, No. 13, 2010, pp. 5289–97. http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/es100186h .
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Corn grain, corn stover, wheat straw, switchgrass, forest residues
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	ethanol : E85
Functional unit	1 km traveled by a light-duty passenger car operated on E85 in the year 2022
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Use ethanol in passenger car
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Avoided impacts are accounted for using product displacement (boundary expansion). For products that share inputs (e.g. corn grain and corn stover), burdens are allocated between products based on a “product-purpose” approach.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	LUC is not considered.
Geographic location, if defined	US
Data quality	US national average data, published research. Most processes are custom created using primary, publicly available data. In the absence of such data, the Ecoinvent v.2.0 is used.
Impact assessment method	SimaProv7.1 life cycle assessment modeling software

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Greenhouse gas emissions, net energy value
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

TABLE 1. Most Influential Parameters^a as Determined by Partial Least Squares Regression Analysis

input parameter	greenhouse gas emissions					net energy value					total count
	feedstock ^b										
	advanced corn ^c	corn stover	switchgrass	wheat straw	forest residue	advanced corn	corn stover	switchgrass	wheat straw	forest residue	
yield ^d	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X		8
irrigation ^e		X		X		X	X	X	X		6
N ^f	X	X	X			X	X	X			6
removal ^g		X		X			X		X		4
moisture ^h		X			X		X			X	4
C ⁱ		X		X	X					X	4
DDGS ^j	X					X					2
N ₂ O ^k	X	X	X								3
harvest ^l			X					X			2
EtOH ^m					X					X	2
turbine ⁿ		X					X				2
boiler ^o		X					X				2
O ^p										X	1
ash ^q										X	1
hay ^r		X									1
H&P ^s						X					1

^a Only input parameters found to be influential through partial least-squares regression are included. ^b Feedstocks are converted to ethanol via advanced corn dry milling (advanced corn); NREL's *n*th plant, dilute-acid simultaneous saccharification and fermentation process (i.e., biochemical conversion) (corn stover, wheat straw, switchgrass); and NREL's *n*th plant, indirect gasification and mixed alcohol synthesis process (i.e., thermochemical conversion) (forest residue). ^c "Advanced corn" represents improvements in the production of corn grain and corn dry milling facilities projected to the year 2022. ^d Harvested biomass yield. ^e Irrigation rate was allocated to residues for dedicated herbaceous crops for PLS analysis purposes only. ^f Nitrogen fertilizer application rate. ^g Residue removal rate. ^h Harvested feedstock moisture. ⁱ Carbon content in biomass. ^j DDGS substitution ratio for corn, soybeans, and urea. ^k N₂O emission factor assumptions. ^l Harvest efficiency (i.e., harvested biomass lost through machinery inefficiency). ^m Ethanol yield at the biorefinery. ⁿ Efficiency of the biorefinery turbine. ^o Efficiency of the biorefinery boiler. ^p Oxygen content of biomass. ^q Ash content in biomass. ^r Substitution of alternative animal fodder (hay) to replace the energy content of stover used for ethanol. ^s Proportion of national conversion facilities using certain fuel for heat and power (i.e., coal, natural gas, biomass).

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

See example on page 3

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Ponder, Celia, and Michael Overcash, “Cradle-to-Gate Life Cycle Inventory of Vancomycin Hydrochloride”, <i>Science of the Total Environment</i> , Vol. 408, No. 6, 2010, pp. 1331–1337.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Although a variety of nutrient sources can be used (Jung et al., 2007), this inventory uses glucose (dextrose) and soy flour for fermentation as they are industrially available sources of complex nutrients and due to the availability of life cycle data previously studied by this research group.
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Vancomycin Hydrochloride
Functional unit	The functional unit, or basis of all analysis, is 1000 kg vancomycin hydrochloride crystals.
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Develop of tools to help scientists select «greener» solvents in pharmaceutical manufacturing.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	When allocation cannot be avoided by system boundary expansion, mass allocation is used.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	LUC is not considered.
Geographic location, if defined	-
Data quality	Information is gathered from articles, books, patents, company websites and consultations with experts in the field, and then used with established process design

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

	heuristics to arrive at the LCI results.
<i>Impact assessment method</i>	Methodology standards described in ISO 14044. The design-based LCI methodology (Jimenez-Gonzalez, 2000) using process flow diagrams and engineering design principles is used to collect inventory data (e.g. process inputs, process operations, waste generated, etc.) and complete gate-to-gate inventories for each chemical in the supply chain of the API.
<i>Damage categories (endpoint)</i>	
<i>Impact categories (midpoint)</i>	Consumption of raw materials, consumption of energy
<i>Other information or comments</i>	The cradle-to-gate (ctg) life cycle inventory (LCI) for vancomycin hydrochloride presented here was performed as part of a larger life cycle inventory investigating the environmental footprint of treating a nosocomial MRSA infection.

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Fig. 2. GTG process flow diagram of vancomycin hydrochloride production.

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

See example on page 3

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Tufvesson Par, Anna Ekman, Roya R R Sardari, Kristina Engdahl, and Linda Tufvesson, “Economic and Environmental Assessment of Propionic Acid Production by Fermentation Using Different Renewable Raw Materials”, <i>Bioresource Technology</i> , Vol. 149, 2013, pp. 556–564.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): economic and environmental assesement
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Glycerol, sugar from sugar beet, molasses, jerusalem artichoke tuber and potato juice
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Propionic acid
Functional unit	1 tonne of proprionic acid at the factory gate
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	Economic allocation was applied to account for by-products
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	LUC is not considered.
Geographic location, if defined	-
Data quality	Lifecycle inventory data obtained by literature studies and the Ecoinvent database.
Impact assessment method	The LCA performed according to the methodology standards described in ISO 14044.
Damage categories (endpoint)	

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Impact categories (midpoint)	Global warming potential in 100 years perspective
Other information or comments	Capex and opex have been used in the economic assesment

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Fig. 1. Description of the overall production system for propionic acid by fermentation.

Table 4

Cultivation inventory input data for raw materials.

Crop	Yield (tonnes/ha)	Mineral fertiliser (kg/ha) ^g			Energy (GJ/ha)		
		N	P	K	Diesel	Electricity	Other
Rapeseed ^a	3.23	140	25	82	3.6	0.36	0.6 ^b
Sugarbeet ^c	45.9	106	16	44	7.2		
Jerusalem artichoke ^e	30	120	40	160	6.7	4.3	2.3 ^d
Potato ^f	40.4	128	40	127	6.7	4.3	2.3 ^d

^a Cultivation data from Schmidt (2007); production data from Börjesson and Tufvesson (2011).

^b Heat for drying of seeds.

^c Cultivation data from Flysjö et al. (2008); production data from Renouf et al. (2008).

^d Energy for machines.

^e Svensson (2012).

^f Cultivation and production data from Ekman and Börjesson (2011).

^g For all crops, data for the production of mineral fertiliser is according to Schmidt (2007). It was assumed that 55% of the N-fertiliser used was produced with catalytic cleaning of N₂O and 45% was produced by conventional methods without cleaning and the data for fertiliser production was adjusted according to this assumption.

T2.1 Literature review – template for reporting a reference

1) Summary table

See example on page 3

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Morales, Merten, Pierre Y Dapsens, Isabella Giovinazzo, Julia Witte, Cecilia Mondelli, Stavros Papadokonstantakis, Konrad Hungerbuhler, and Javier Perez-Ramirez, “Environmental and Economic Assessment of Lactic Acid Production from Glycerol Using Cascade Bio- and Chemocatalysis”, <i>Energy & Environmental Science</i> , Vol. 8, No. 2, 2015, pp. 558–567. http://http://pubs.rsc.org/en/Content/ArticleLanding/2015/EE/c4ee03352c .
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): economic and environmental assesement
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Glycerol
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Lactic acid
Functional unit	1 kg of LA
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Lactic acid from glycerol can be polymerized into a novel biodegradable plastic suitable for packaging i.e. polylactide (PLA)
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	For the allocation of environmental impacts to crude glycerol as a co-product of the biodiesel production the approach and assumptions proposed by Weideman et. al were followed. Thus, crude glycerol was considered as a partially utilised co-product from a consequential LCA perspective.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	LUC is not mentioned
Geographic location, if defined	-

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Data quality	Ecoinvent database + Literature
Impact assessment method	Not mentioned
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Cumulative energy demand, global warming potential ,ecoinicator 99 (EI99),operating costs
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Fig. 1 Flowsheet for the DHA production process from crude glycerol according to the DHA-2,3 models.

Fig. 2 Flowsheet for the chemocatalytic LA production process from DHA using the Sn-MFI catalyst in (a) water and (b) methanol.

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Ekman, Anna, and Pal Börjesson, “Environmental Assessment of Propionic Acid Produced in an Agricultural Biomass-Based Biorefinery System”, <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 19, No. 11, 2011, pp. 1257–1265.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Glycerol from biodiesel production (by-product). Residues from the production of Potato starch.
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	Propionic acid
Functional unit	1 kg of propionic acid at the factory gate.
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Develop an optimized biorefinery concept based on existing industrial by-products.
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	It is assumed that the input materials used will be only by-products from existing production of biodiesel and potato starch. The economic value of main products and by-products differs significantly, which motivates the use of economic allocation as the base case in this study. The environmental load allocated to the different product streams is presented in Table 2.
Inclusion of land use change (please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)	In this study, the effect of direct land-use changes is considered in the sensitivity analysis when sugar from sugar beet is assumed to be used as primary feedstock instead of glycerol. However, there are several models for the calculations of GHGs arising by land-use changes and there is not yet consensus which one to prefer and therefore it is still difficult to include effects of especially indirect land-use changes in regular LCAs. More research in this area is needed
Geographic location, if defined	Southern Sweden

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

Data quality	literature
Impact assessment method	The environmental assessment is based on life-cycle methodology, described in the standards ISO 14040 and 14044 (2006). The main character of the study is an accounting LCA.
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Primary Energy Consumption, expressed as MJ/FU, Global Warming Potential (GWP), expressed as g CO ₂ -equivalents/FU, and Eutrophication Potential (EP), expressed as g PO ₃ ⁻⁴ – equivalents/FU.
Other information or comments	

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

Fig. 1. Flowchart of the biorefinery concept (see text for a more detailed explanation).

Table 2

Allocated load to the different products in the biorefinery production system.

Product	Allocated load –Economic (%)	Allocated load –Mass (%)	Allocated load –Energy (%) ^f
Rapeseed oil ^{a,b,c}	72	45	65
Rapeseed meal ^{a,b,c}	28	55	35
RME ^d	96.5	90	95
Glycerol ^d	3.5	10	5
Potato starch ^e	92	81	99
Potato juice ^e	0,3	10	0
Other potato products ^e	7,7	9	1

^a Cederberg and Flysjö, 2008.

^b Mårtensson and Svensson, 2009.

^c Börjesson and Tufvesson, 2011.

^d Hultgren, 2010.

^e Ståhl, 2009.

^f Lower Heating Value.

T2.1 Literature review

1) Summary table

Item	Case study
Reference (full citation – please use the “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide”) ¹	Juneja, Ankita, Deepak Kumar, and Ganti S. Murthy, “Economic Feasibility and Environmental Life Cycle Assessment of Ethanol Production from Lignocellulosic Feedstock in Pacific Northwest U.S.”, <i>Journal of Renewable and Sustainable Energy</i> , Vol. 5, Vol. 5, 2013.
Type of study (check at least 1)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Input-output analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Life Cycle Costing <input type="checkbox"/> Social Life Cycle Assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): and techno-economic analysis
Crop or product (or waste) used as bio-based feedstock	Perennial ryegrass straw Wheat straw
Bio-products and form (please cite all co- and by-products)	ethanol
Functional unit	10.000 MJ of available energy in ethanol at the pump
Product family (check at least 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Fibres <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic polymers (non-fibre) <input type="checkbox"/> Oils (non-polymerized) <input type="checkbox"/> Sugars and starch (non-polymerized) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fine chemicals <input type="checkbox"/> Proteins <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Possible applications	Used as fuel to vehicles
Boundaries (check all included stages)	<input type="checkbox"/> R&D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture / forestry <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Logistics and transportation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Transformation steps (to be detailed in the report section) <input type="checkbox"/> Conditioning <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Packaging and distribution <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Use stage <input type="checkbox"/> End-of-life <input type="checkbox"/> Advertisement and other overheads <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Approach (leave blank if unclear)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attributional <input type="checkbox"/> Consequential
Carbon accounting (check 1)	<input type="checkbox"/> Carbon capture is taken into account, biogenic emissions are not neutral <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biogenic CO ₂ is considered neutral, capture is ignored <input type="checkbox"/> There is inconsistency or the study is unclear about that
Allocation procedure for multifunctionality	There are two multiproduct processes in the ethanol production cycle: straw and crop, and ethanol and lignin energy. Grass straw is a co-product of grass seed production; therefore, energy use and emissions during agricultural production were allocated between grass seed and straw using economic based allocation method. Steam and electricity produced from lignin residues are co-products in ethanol production process. System expansion (displacement) approach was used to calculate coproduct credits, which assumes that the steam and electricity produced from lignin residue replace the process steam and electricity required for the plant operations and offset the energy use and GHG emissions to produce these utilities using fossil fuels.
Inclusion of land use change	LUC was not considered

¹ The “European Union Interinstitutional Style Guide” is available in most bibliographic management tools and compatible with <http://citationstyles.org/>. See also www.citationmachine.net/european-union-interinstitutional-style-guide/cite-a-other (for instance) for automated citation formatting.

<i>(please specify the methodology for direct and indirect LUC)</i>	
Geographic location, if defined	Oregon, US
Data quality	Data from Oregon Enterprise Budget, published reports and research papers, local farmers, data from process model simulations, Energy Use in Transportation (GREET) 1.8D model, US life-cycle inventory database.
Impact assessment method	Superpro design
Damage categories (endpoint)	
Impact categories (midpoint)	Energy use, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions
Other information or comments	Costs of other equipment were calculated based on the built-in cost models in SuperPro designer. Installation costs of the equipment, and cost of utilities and consumables were estimated from recent techno-economic studies. Detailed assumptions used in the process models to calculate direct cost, indirect cost and direct fixed cost are provided elsewhere.

2) Short report (1 or 2 pages)

FIG. 2. Schematic illustration of modeled ethanol production process.

TABLE II. Bulk material amount and cost during ethanol production from the plant with 250 000 metric ton/year biomass processing (2012 prices).

Material	Unit cost (\$/kg)	PR straw		Wheat straw	
		amount (kg 1000×)	Cost (€/l EtOH)	amount (kg 1000×)	Cost (€/l EtOH)
Biomass	0.050	250 000	21.45	250 000	17.00
Sulfuric acid	0.035	12 255.48	0.74	7702.27	0.37
Ca hydroxide	0.100	5967.72	1.02	3078.45	0.42
Diammonium phosphate (DAP)	0.210	79.20	0.03	79.20	0.02
Cellulase	0.517	12 583.34	11.16	18 193.10	12.79
Yeast	2.300	198.00	0.78	198.00	0.62
Gasoline (denaturation)	0.800	476.77	0.66	601.31	0.82

TABLE III. Amount and cost of overall utilities used in ethanol making process from the plant with 250 000 metric ton/year biomass processing.

Utility	PR straw			Wheat straw		
	Annual amount (10 ⁶ ×)	Amount (kg/l EtOH)	Cost (€/l EtOH)	Annual amount (10 ⁶ ×)	Amount (kg/l EtOH)	Cost (€/l EtOH)
Electricity ^a (kW h)	33.36	0.57	4.01	33.97	0.46	3.23
Steam (kg)	346.09	5.94	0.000	384.72	5.23	0.00
Cooling water (kg)	29 537.08	506.91	2.54	33 668.88	457.97	2.29
Chilled water (kg)	35.02	0.60	0.02	50.63	0.69	0.03
CT water (kg)	5 295.75	90.89	0.64	5 295.75	72.03	0.50
Steam (high P) (kg)	25.15	0.43	0.000	29.41	0.40	0.00

^aElectricity values did not account for power required for cooling and chilled water.

FIG. 6. System boundary for life cycle analysis of ethanol production from PR and wheat straw.